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- Review of Standards for integrating BIPV-modules in building façade and roof-

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1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives

The content of WP2 includes a detailed review of standards and guidelines (deliverable D2). The general objective of this report D2.2 is a wide-ranging overview of standards for integrating building-integrated photovoltaic (BIPV)-modules in building façades and roofs. Moreover, this report provides a common working basis for the project and its further course. In particular, it will also be of major importance for the upcoming work packages. Apart from general information about the building sector, some identified problems with building-integrated photovoltaics will be addressed as well.

1.2 Summary

This report is partly based on the results of task 1.1 'Identification of requirements for the building from the point of view of architects, photovoltaic (PV) producers, plant manufacturers and construction companies. Based on the individual mounting categories A-E regarding prEN 50583, the research was expanded and subsequently completed with European and national standards.

This research covers the general European legal situation of the building code and some national building codes in detail.. In addition to France, Greece, Switzerland, Italy, Spain, the Netherlands and Austria, the German standard situation and its legal process will be mainly discussed.

The report consists mostly of collection of all relevant European standards, national standards and national guidelines. It is written in tabular form, with regard to WP1. The separate listing of every nation is necessary because there are several differences of standards and the usage of construction products. There was a collaboration with "bfirst" and "smartflex", both of which are also research projects within the 7th European Research Framework program.

Furthermore, lists of standards from the 6th European Research Framework Program 'BIPV CIS' were updated and sorted into the table. Additionally, databases such as 'perinorm' or 'beuth' were scanned for all relevant standards regarding BIPV and sorted into the table as well.

This report serves as a source of information and should build the basis for making informed decisions.

This report is divided into 6 chapters.

1. Introduction
2. Research of building requirements – interface building shell - PV –
3. Standardization of BIPV
4. Legal situation of different national countries of dealing with construction products
5. Review of standards for integrating BIPV-modules into façade and roof
6. Review of testing standards for integrating BIPV-modules
7. References

The first chapter deals with the requirements of ventilated façades in general as we are focused on that type of façades in our project. Many requirements for ventilated façades are defined in German or European standards. These standards and guidelines regarding (not only ventilated façades but also glass) are listed in tabular form in chapter 5. Chapter 3 concern itself with the European regulation of construction products and the legal basis of harmonization in Europe.

The European situation with regard to standardization and regulations is still not legally defined. An approach for a European standard is given with the draft EN standard 50583 which is a basis for the WP1 and at least for this report. Furthermore, the legal situation of different national standards will be discussed in chapter 4. An overview of European and national standards and guidelines is given in chapters 5 and 6.

2 Review of requirements for BIPV systems

2.1 Short list of general requirements of a ventilated façade with PV

2.1.1 Introduction

Façade constructions in the past were mostly passive building elements from the energetic point of view. Due to the integration of photovoltaics in the façade, it is possible to cross over from the passive point of view to an active one. Façades have a considerable potential for energy production.

Typical constructions that can be used for BIPV are:

- Ventilated façades
- Prefabricated façades
- Double-leaf façades
- Transom-Mullion façade

For BIPV cold façades, as a ventilated façade, are preferred for the use. The PV-element performs the function of both cladding element and weather protection. Through the ventilation space between insulation and cladding, moisture is removed together with the ascending air from the wall. The air cushion also contributes to improvement of sound insulation and may reduce the temperature of the modules.

In transom-mullion constructions, PV-elements can be fit onto mainly opaque areas. Depending on the design concept, different options are possible. Moreover, safety and security requirements have to be fulfilled when the construction as such is considered.

Ventilated façade

A ventilated façade is a multi-layered closed façade or exterior wall construction.

According to DIN 18516-1, a ventilated façade consists of the following different layers:

- Cladding plus ventilation cavity
- Supporting construction
- Anchorage elements
- Layer of insulating material
- Supplementary parts of the cladding

Figure 1: Cladding wall according to DIN 18516

In part 1 of DIN 18516, the verification principles are regulated. PV modules hide the thermal construction, so that opaque glass-layer laminates or glass-glass laminates can be used. The cladding materials, i.e. panels, metal or ceramic are attached to the supporting construction.

Façades which are made of glass must be fixed totally separately and may be clamped (linear or point supported). Heat-soaked toughened safety glass (ESG-H) must be used according to the standard 18516-4. However, sometimes PV modules do not meet the required standards and have to be agreed upon by the building authorities.

Several Photovoltaic Elements with a ventilated façade according to DIN 18516 are available on the market. Most of them are regulated by a national technical approval or approved as a regulated construction form according to DIN 18516.

Most of them are permissible to a façade height of 100 m. Mounting systems are usually point or linear supported. It is possible to fit in concealed fittings on the back, so that the glass edge cover disappears. (Picture 2) The glass edges in general have to be verified before fitting. The thickness of glass panels should not be less than 6 mm, and the edges have to be covered, so that all sharp pieces are removed.

- a) Cover glass
- b) PV cells (here: thin film)
- c) Backing glass
- d) Mounting plate
- e) T-section
- f) Insulation

Figure 2: PV in front of a ventilated façade, the cladding is secured by concealed hook-fixings (Agraffe)

2.1.2 Short List of General Requirements of a Ventilated Façade with PV

2.1.2.1 Structural-physical Requirements

Ventilation

Ventilation is necessary to reduce humidity, deposition, discharge of condensation water and for other aspects.

Distance: at least 20 mm from the exterior wall

Distance can be reduced to a minimum of 5 mm (roughness of the wall)

Free cross section of the ventilation: at least 200 cm²/m

Breather hole: at least 50 cm²/1 m length of wall

The ventilated façade is included to the group of stress III according to DIN 4108-3, and it is resistant to driving rain. In the worst case, the driving rain can drain off at the backside of the cover. Thus, the thermal insulation is not drenched, and it is possible to design ventilated façades with open horizontal joints.

DIN 18516-4

DIN 4108-3

DIN EN 12152, 2002-08

Curtain wall – air permeability – performance requirements and categorization;
German version EN 12152:2002

DIN EN 12153, 2000-09

Curtain wall – air permeability – test procedure;
German version EN 12153:2000

Driving rain: *DIN EN 12154 2000-6*
DIN EN 12155 2000-10
DIN EN 13050 2011-09
DIN EN 13051 2001-11

DIN EN 12154, 2000-06

Curtain wall – air permeability – performance requirements and categorization;
German version EN 12154:1999

DIN EN 12155, 2000-10

Curtain wall – leak-proof in case of driving rain – laboratory test under static pressure;
German version EN 12155:2000

DIN EN 13050, 2011-09

Curtain wall – leak-proof in case of driving rain – laboratory test with changing barometric pressure
and sprinkling with water;
German version prEN 13050:2006

DIN EN 13051, 2001-11

Curtain wall – leak-proof in case of driving rain – test in place;
German version EN 13051:2001

Sound insulation

The requirements of the sound insulation are achieved by the calm-shell constructions, especially by the connection with massive main walls. Sound insulation can be increased to 14dB, depending on the thickness of the insulation, the mass of the casing and the percentage of open joints.

DIN 4109

Insect protection

A grate has to be attached to avoid the infiltration by insects or birds.

Remaining minimum cross section: 2 ‰ or 1/500 of the wall area according to 68800-2

DIN 68800-2

Coefficient of heat

DIN EN 13947, edition: 2007-07

Thermotechnical behavior of curtain walls – calculation of the thermal transmission coefficient;
German version EN 13947:2006
corrected document (previous document DIN EN 13947:2007-03)

2.1.2.2 Construction Requirements

The casing of the exterior wall has to be mounted by using fixed and sliding spots, so that it is free of constraint forces. Thus, local separation as a result of deformations can be avoided as well as possible noise development due to wind and thermal stress.

Dividing the casings in districts of 50 m²

Distances horizontal, every 8 m
 vertical, every 2 levels

Edge distance of connection and fastening in the casing: at least 10 mm

DIN 18516-4

2.1.2.3 Load Assumption

Windload

Joints of the cladding max. 20 mm

Arrangement of a windstop

DIN 1055-4 (EN 1990/1991)

Separation into pressure zones

Obstruction of strong airstreams on the edges of the building and in areas with variable wind pressures

Requirements:

- Every pressure zone contains adequately sized ventiducts (according to the volume)
- Division of the pressure zone:
 - Horizontal to floor level
 - Vertical maximal every 6 meter
 - Vertical: every 1.5 m in the edges
 - Vertical: 300 mm from the edges of the building
- Partially pressure stops are reasonable to moderate the pressure balance

Figure 3: Wind barrier according to DIN 18516

DIN 18516-5

DIN EN 12179, 2000-09

Curtain wall – resistance to wind load – testing procedure;

German version EN 12179:2000

DIN EN 13116, 2001-11

Curtain wall – resistance to wind load – performance requirements;

German version EN 13116:2001

Snow load – Ice load

Snow and ice load according to DIN 1055-5 (DIN EN 1990/1991): 0.1 kN/m²

DIN 1055-5 (DIN EN 1990/1991)

Special load

Special loads have to be carried into the cladding of the exterior wall and, if necessary, be proved.

DIN 18516-5

Deformation

Structures in general can be deformed and the subsoil can be settled because of temperature.

DIN 18516-5

2.1.2.4 Stability Proof

Cladding

Cladding elements must be fixed separately. The cladding must not touch the insulation, the mounting system or the wall in case of its deformation. The stiffness ratio between the substructure and the cladding needs to be considered (Hees, Zuber).

DIN 18516-6

Subconstruction [link according to DIN 18202 (Tolerances in building construction)]

The stability of the load bearing dowel must be covered by the national technical approval (AbZ). Metal substructures are mounted on support profiles according to DIN 18202.

DIN 18516-6

DIN 18202

2.1.2.5 Building Material

Insulation

Layer of insulation according to 4108-10

Closed and free of cavities mounting

Mineral insulation according to DIN EN 13162

DIN 18516-7

DIN 4108-10

DIN EN 13162

2.1.2.6 Lightning Protection

Requirements for lightning protection have become increasingly important. Lightning conductors may not be applicable to an electrically conductive substructure made of aluminum. Thus, electromagnetic shielding is needed. The protection of the electronic system in the building is warranted.

2.1.2.7 Fire safety

- Prevention of fire spread over the space between:
 - Timber depth of the gap < 50 mm
 - Metal depth of the gap < 150 mm
 - Horizontal fire barrier on each second floor > classification of fire zones > low damaging in case of fire
 - Interruption of the gap of the fire walls > Packing with fire resistant insulation (polystyrene foam [EPS] is not permitted)

DIN MLTB 09/2009, Attachment 2.6/11

DIN EN 1364-3, 2006-12

Fire resistance proof of non-supporting components – Part 3: curtain wall;
German version EN 1364-3:2006

DIN EN 1364-4, 2007-06

Fire resistance proof of non-supporting components – Part 3: curtain wall;
German version EN 1364-4:2007

2.1.2.8 Cladding

Claddings are divided into two categories:

- Small modules with a size < 0.4 m² and a weight of up to 5.0 kg and bigger modules (see: Construction Products List Part C) (BRL-Teil C).
- In Germany, a license is only needed for big modules. In other European countries, there are no regulations regarding the size of the modules.

DIN 18516

DIN 4113

Impact loading and dynamic stress

Protection against shock can be fixed to a height of 2.8 m.

EN 14019:2004

DIN EN 14019, 2004-09

Curtain walls – impact strength – performance requirements;
German version EN 14019:2004

2.1.2.9 Thermal Bridge

The profiles must be cut off thermic from the wall.

Link to the guidelines: 'Codes of thermodynamic influences of thermal bridges of curtain walls'

2.1.2.10 Recyclability

One crucial factor for sustainability is the recyclability of structural components and building materials. The components of ventilated facades can be disassembled, and those elements can be recycled.

2.1.2.11 Additional Standards – Ventilated Façades

DIN EN 13119, 2007-07

Curtain walls - terminology EN 13119:2007

DIN EN 949, 1999-05

Windows, Doors, roller shutter, curtain walls – resistance calculation of doors against shock
German version EN 949:1998

DIN EN 13830, 2003-11

Curtain walls – Product standard
German version EN 13830:2003

DIN

18351,

2010-04

VOB German construction contract procedure, Part C: General technical conditions of contract
Ventilated façades

2.1.2.12 Glass in Building

PV elements have to comply with the requirements of DIN 18008-1, DIN 18088-2 (so far TRLV), TRPV (in the future DIN 18008-3) or TRAV (in the future 18008-4) depending on their usage.

There are some variations:

- For the calculation of the effect of combinations according to DIN 18008-1 with regard to laminated insulating glazing, a higher temperature difference of $\Delta T_{add} + 35 \text{ K}$ (Summer term) needs to be considered according to PV modules.
- Construction materials can be used as composite materials with a relevant ability.

- A temperature of 60 degrees is to be used for the calculation of the ultimate limit state of load bearing capacity according to 18008-1
- The glass thickness can be chosen according to DIN EN 12150-1 for fully tempered glass (ESG) and EN 1863-1 for heat-strengthened glass (TVG)
- Glass drill holes that are not used for the mechanical fixing, can be chosen according to DIN EN 12150-1 for fully tempered glass (ESG) and EN 1863-1 for heat-strengthened glass (TVG)

The usage of glass panels is acceptable according to the construction product list (BRL).

Abridged version of DIN 18008 part 1, part 2 and part 3

DIN 18008-1 Glass in building – Terms and general rules

This standard is not applicable to individual panels of nominal glass thicknesses of less than 3 mm and more than 19 mm.

Mounting systems are usually point or linear supported. It is possible to fit in concealed fittings on the back, so that the glass edge cover disappears.

The glass edges in general have to be verified before fitting.

The thickness of glass should not be less than 6 mm, and the edges must be covered that all sharp pieces are covered.

Damages must not go further than 15 % of the thickness of the glass panels into the whole glass body. The mounting of point-supported tempered safety glass (ESG) higher than 8 m is inspected by an institute accredited by the building authorities.

The rated value of the support resistance by using laminated and laminated safety glass can be increased by 10%.

With regard to glass drill holes and recesses:

Glass drill holes and recesses should be continuous and should only be produced in glass which is subsequently thermally toughened or heat strengthened.

Note: For laminated glass and laminated safety glass, the term ‘continuous’ refers to the individual monolithic panels.

The remaining width of glass between drill holes or recesses and adjacent drill holes or recesses should be 80 mm as a minimum.

In case of the remaining width of glass between the edges of the drill holes or between the edges of the drill holes and the edges of the glass being less than 80 mm, the design value of the load-bearing resistance of the respective base glass shall be taken as a basis for design at the edge of the drill hole.

DIN 18008-2 Glass in building - Linear supported glazing

The glass bite shall be chosen such that long-term structural stability of the glazing is ensured. Unless specified otherwise in the following, a minimum edge cover of 10 mm is required.

The linear support should be bilaterally effective (for pressure and suction) on at least two opposite sides, usually to the plane of the panels. For multiple layers, the linear support shall be effective for all panels.

Monolithic single glazing made of types of glass that break into large pieces (e.g. float glass, heat-strengthened glass (TVG), drawn sheet glass, patterned glass) and laminated glass (VG), whose upper edge lies more than 4 m above any public areas, has to be supported on all sides.

Monolithic single glazing made of fully toughened safety glass (ESG), whose upper edge lies more than 4 m above any public areas, has to be heat soaked toughened safety glass (ESG-H). This also applies to monolithic toughened safety glass in insulating glass units.

DIN 18008-3 Glass in building - Point fixed glazing

Additional provision for vertical glazing:

The following glazing can be used for vertical glazing:

- Laminated safety glass made of fully toughened safety glass,
- Laminated safety glass made of heat soaked toughened safety glass,
- Laminated safety glass made of heat-strengthened glass
(each drilled or clamped)

For vertical glazing that is supported by clamps, the following glass can be used:

- heat soaked toughened safety glass with a normal thickness of 6 mm,
- insulating glass made of heat soaked toughened safety glass, heat-strengthened glass
TVG or float glass,
- Laminated safety glass made of float glass

Glass edge of fully toughened safety glass, heat soaked toughened safety glass and heat-strengthened glass require a seam. Glass edges of float glass require sanding.

3 Procedures for the approval of construction products in Europe – an overview

BauPVO	Construction Products Regulation ('Bauproduktenverordnung')
BPR	Construction Products Directive ('Bauproduktenrichtlinie')
CE	European Conformity
CEN	European Committee for Standardization ('Comité Européen de Normalisation')
CENELEC	European Committee for electrical Engineering Standardization
CPD	Construction Products Directive
CUAP	Common Understanding of Assessment Procedure
DIN	German Institute for Standardization ('Deutsches Institut für Normung')
DKE	German commission for electrical engineering ('Deutsche Kommission für Elektrotechnik')
DoP	Declaration of Performance
EC	Euro Code
EEA	European Economic Association
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
ENV	European pre-Standards
EOTA	European Organisation for Technical Approvals
ETA (ETB)	European Technical Approval ('Europäische Technische Bewertung')
ETAG	European Technical Approvals Guidelines
ETSI	European Institute for Standards in Telecommunication
hEN	harmonized European Standard
NAD	National Application Document
NPD	No Performance Determined
OTBS	Organisation of technical Assessment Bodies ('Organisation Technischer Bewertungsstellen')
prEN	Preliminary European Standard
SSGS	Structural Sealant Glazing Systems
TC	Technical Committee

3.1 Introduction

Eurocodes (EC) are Europe-wide unified regulations for the design in construction engineering. These European standards were developed by the member states of the European Committee for Standardization (CEN), European Committee for Electrical Engineering Standardization (CENELEC) or European Institute for Standards in Telecommunication (ETSI). One part of European standardization is the partial safety factor concept. Eurocodes are published by the CEN in three main languages: English, German and French. The original texts can be translated by national institutes for standardization.

In the course of unifying the standards, ten different Eurocodes (EC) have been published. The ECs are grouped in the main topics of construction engineering, e.g. Steel Structures, Glazing Structures etc. Furthermore, each EC is divided into different parts, e.g. linear-supported glazing, point-supported glazing etc. Additionally, the member states can add 'National Annexes' (NA) for each Eurocode. Additional information, parameters and requirements, e.g. partial safety factors, can be defined in those National Annexes.

Member states can adopt the Eurocodes as European standards (EN). For instance, EC's are adopted as DIN-EN standards in Germany. EN are regulations which are ratified by one of the european committees for standardization.

- Eurocode 0 - Basis of Structural Design (EN 1990)
- Eurocode 1 - Actions on Structures (EN 1991)
- Eurocode 2 - Design of Concrete Structures (EN 1992)
- Eurocode 3 - Design of Steel Structures (EN 1993)
- Eurocode 4 - Design of Composite Steel and Concrete Structures (EN 1994)
- Eurocode 5 - Design of timber structures (EN 1995)
- Eurocode 6 - Design of Masonry Structures (EN 1996)
- Eurocode 7 - Geotechnical Design (EN 1997)
- Eurocode 8 - Design of Structures for Earthquake Resistance (EN 1998)
- Eurocode 9 - Design of Aluminium Structures (EN 1999)

The aims of the harmonisation of standards in Europe are necessary conditions for research and development in all member states. Moreover, the harmonisation of regulations for the building industry would considerably improve the European building market. In order to achieve these aims, the published ECs are to be adapted by the member states without modifications. Conflicting national standards are to be withdrawn.

International standards can be adopted as European standards by the European standard committees (CEN, CENELEC and ETSI). If no international standard which could be adopted exists, the committee responsible develops a draft of such a standard. The national standardization organisations release the draft for public discussions in all member states. Depending on the response, the draft can be transferred to final European Standard or is to be revised. In the latter case, the revised draft has to be public discussed again.

To keep the development process manageable, the process is scheduled for a maximum of three years. In order to keep in schedule, time targets need to be predefined. Extension of times targets have to be applied for.

3.2 European way of dealing with construction products

3.2.1 EOTA - European Organisation for Technical Approvals

European Technical Approvals (ETA) need to be issued by European Organisation of technical Approvals (EOTA). EOTA is a group of approval bodies that are authorised by the EU member states and the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) states, which agreed to the European Economic Area Agreement. EOTA is mainly responsible for granting ETAs and for drafting ETA Guidelines (ETAG).

For several tasks, EOTA can be supported by the European Commission, EFTA, CEN, European trade associations and industrial organisations as observer. A list of the agreeing states and their national approval authorities is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Approval Bodies of the national EOTA members

Country	National EOTA Member
Austria	- Österreichisches Institut Für Bautechniker (OIB)
Belgium	- BUtgb-Directie Goedkeuring en Voorschriften (DGV) - UBAtc-Direction Agrément et Spécifications (DAS)
Czech Republic	- Technický a zkusební ústav stavební Praha, s.p. (TZUS) - Centrum stavebního inženýrství a.s. (CSI)
Denmark	- ETA-Denmark A/S
Estonia	- Tallinna Tehnikaülikool, Tallinn University of Technology (TUT)
Finland	- Valtion Teknillinen Tutkimuskeskus (VTT)
France	- Centre Scientifique et Technique du Batiment (CSTB) - Service d'Etudes Techniques des Routes et Autoroutes (SETRA)
Germany	- Deutsches Institut für Bautechnik (DIBt)
Greece	- Hellenic Organization for Standardization (ELOT)
Hungary	- Építésügyi Minőségellenőrző Innovációs Kht (ÉMI Kht)
Iceland	- The Iceland Building Research Institute (IBRI)
Ireland	- Irish Agrément Board (IAB)
Italy	- Servizio Tecnico Centrale della Presidenza del Consiglio Superiore LL.PP. (STC) - Centro Studi ed Esperienze Antincendi dell Corpo Nazionale dei Vigili del Fuoco (CSEA) - Istituto per le Tecnologie della Costruzione (ITC)
Latvia	- ETA-Latvia
Lithuania	- Statybos Produkcijos Sertifikavimo Centras (SPSC)
Luxemburg	- Laboratoire des Ponts et Chaussées
Netherlands	- Stichting Bouwkwaliiteit (SBK)
Norway	- Norwegian Building Research Institute (NBI)
Poland	- Instytut Techniki Budowlanej (ITB)
Portugal	- Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (LNEC)
Slovak Republic	- Technický a Skúšobný Ústav Stavebný (TSUS)

Slovenia	- Zavod za Gradbeništvo Slovenije (ZAG)
Spain	- Instituto de Ciencias de la Construcción EduardoTorroja (IETcc) - Institut de Tecnologia de la Contrucció de Catalunya (ITeC)
Sweden	- Swedish Institute for Technical Approval in Construction (SITAC)
United Kingdom	- British Board of Agrément (BBA) - BRE Certification Limited Incorporating LPCB & WIMLAS - UK CARES - BM Trada Certification Ltd. - Warrington Certification Ltd.

3.2.2 ETAG - European Technical Approval Guideline

European Technical Approval Guidelines (ETAG) are issued by EOTA and can be initiated by the European Commission and EFTA. The guidelines regulate the approval procedure regarding requirements for construction products and forms of construction. The approval bodies follow. According to the Construction Products Directive (CPD), guidelines have to consist of:

- A list of the relevant interpretative documents,
- Specific requirements for products within the meaning of the essential requirements
- Test procedures
- Methods of assessing test results
- Procedures related to the attestation of conformity
- Period of validity of approval

For the status as a binding document, it is necessary that the ETAGs are approved by EOTA, consulted by a standing committee and published by the member states.

To ensure technical relevance, EOTA co-operates with other institutions, e.g. industrial organisations. Depending on the complexity of a topic, specialists from each relevant area of expertise can be consulted.

With regard to building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPV), there is only one relevant ETA Guideline. ETAG-002 refers to structural sealant glazing systems (SSGS) and therefore influences the conditions of Construct PV.

3.2.3 ETA - European Technical Approval

To apply for a European technical Approvals (ETA), the relevant products are covered by any of the existing harmonized European Standards or those are still in progress.

For ETA, six essential requirements have to be fulfilled according to the Construction Products Directive 89/106/ECC (CPD):

- Mechanical resistance and stability
- Safety in case of fire
- Hygiene, health and protection of the environment
- Safety in use
- Protection against noise
- Energy economy and heat retention

Prerequisite for placing Construction Products and Forms of Condition on the European market is to have a European technical Approval (ETA) or is to confirm to the harmonised European standards or to non-harmonised technical specifications which are accepted on EC level. Construction Products that are approved by the ETA and also fulfil the requirements of conformity regulations can be CE marked. The CE mark is necessary for placing construction products or Forms of construction on the European market. The producer can apply for an ETA by themselves or the producer can authorise an agent to make an application for an ETA to any of the EOTA members. The number of requested EOTA members is limited to only one.

A designated application form has to be used. In addition to the application form, some required technical explanation information need to be attached. This attachment has to contain the construction product description, specifications, drawings and test reports.

For building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) and for Construct PV in particular, there is one relevant ETA. The relevant ETA regulate structural sealant glazing and point-supported glass.

Special Case: ETA without ETAG

For products that are not covered by the ETAG, ETA can be issued by EOTA authorities and the European Commission via the Common Understanding of Assessment Procedure (CUAP). CUAP set out the assessment criteria for the product and its intended use.

3.3 Legal Basis of Harmonization in Europe

To improve the European building sector, the members of the European Union (EU) laid down harmonized conditions for the marketing of construction products. Amongst other harmonized regularities (e.g. harmonized design standards and application standards), the Council of the European Union (EU) and the European Parliament concluded the agreement on harmonizing the building regularities, called 'Bauproduktenverordnung' (The BauPVO) (Construction Products

Regulation). BauPVO repeals Bauproduktenrichtlinie (BPR) (Construction Products Directive). As BPR before, BauPVO provides reliable information on Construction Products in relation to their performance. Uniform assessment methods are offered for the construction products used in the European building sector. The information in BauPVO provide a basis for the European Conformity mark (CE) (French: Conformité Européenne).

3.3.1 hEN - European harmonized Standards

Requirements for special performances (e.g. fire protection requirements) are primarily found in 'harmonisierte Europäische Normen' (hEN) (harmonized European Standards). The hEN are initialised by the 'European Committee for Standardization' (CEN) (French: 'Comité Européen de Normalisation'), if required in co-operation with 'European Committee for electrotechnical Standardization' (CENELEC) (French: 'Comité Européen de Normalisation Électrotechnique'). The resulting hEN provide assessments of construction products in relation to their performances and also provide testing procedures and procedures of calculation.

Authoritative requirements are defined in annex AZ of the hEN. Additional requirements and classifications can be defined in principal part of the hEN.

If the construction products cannot clearly be classified according to the hENs, these construction products will be classified individually in accordance with the BauPVO. For the individual classification according to the BauPVO, the producer need to apply 'Europäisch Technische Bewertung' (ETB) (European Technical Assessment) to the technical authorities Organisation Technischer Bewertungsstellen (OTBS), (Organisation of technical Assessment Bodies).

For bringing construction products onto the market a Declaration of Performance (DoP) ('Leistungserklärung') is required. The DoP is based on the producers' binding assessment of the construction product on the basis of harmonized technical specifications, means hEN or ETB if available. If a single performance is not regulated by either the hEN or the ETB, the producer has to make a declaration of 'No Performance Determined' (NPD).

In addition, the product's performance has to conform to the requirements of the BauPVO, and if possible, to the respective EU guidelines. The Product's conformity to the declared performances is indicated by the CE mark. The producer is responsible for the accurateness of the mark. Exceptions include building site products, made-to-specification products and products for landmarked buildings.

3.3.2 BauPVO - National Authorities

From a legal point of view, for the classification of the BauPVO is a statement for placing construction products on the market. The BauPVO provides performance requirements for classification and specification of construction products to offer uniform assessment methods for the European building sector. The CE marking of construction products according to the BauPVO enables the process of bringing products to the market. BauPVO does not rule the construction product and its performance.

However, the BauPVO offers performances for product assessing to ensure the abidance and comparability of required product performance and construction product's actual performance.

Whereas the CE marks according to most guidelines attest the abidance of required product performances, the CE marks according to the BauPVO attest the compliance with both the required performance of the construction product and the product's actual performance. Each member state has to determine the level of performance for construction products.

Member states supervise the CE markings in order to ensure the uniformity of construction product's quality. If CE-marked construction products do not conform to the CE guidelines, the authorities can impose correction measures on the producer, prompt product recalls or withdraw the product from market.

4 National legal situation concerning the technical approval of BIPV modules and systems in different European countries

The following table shows the contributions of the participating partners for this deliverable.

Table 2: Participating partners

Country	Partner
Germany	TUD (Dresden, University of Technology)
France	MB (Meyer Burger AG)
Greece	NTUA (National Technical University of Athens)
Switzerland, Netherlands	SUPSI (Scuola Universitaria Professionale Della Svizzera Italiana), MB (Meyer Burger AG)
Italy, Spain	DAPP (D'Appolonia)
Austria	ZUEB (Ed. Züblin AG)

The “Technische Universität Dresden” has edited the texts, but each partner is responsible of the content.

4.1 National Situation in Germany

List of abbreviations:

AbP	National Approved Certificate (‘Allgemeines bauaufsichtliches Pruefzeugnis’)
AbZ	National Technical Approval (‘Allgemeine bauaufsichtliche Zulassung’)
BauPVO	Construction Products Regulation (‘Bauproduktenverordnung’)
BIPV	Building integrated Photovoltaic
BRL	Construction Products List (‘Bauregelliste’)
CE	European Conformity
CEN	European Committee for Standardization (‘Comité Européen de Normalisation’)
DIBt	German Institute of Building Technology (‘Deutsches Institut für Bautechnik’)
DIN	German Institute for Standardization (‘Deutsches Institut für Normung’)
ETA (ETB)	European Technical Approval (‘Europäische Technische Bewertung’)
ETAG	European Technical Approvals Guidelines
hEN	Harmonized European Standard
LBO	Federal State Building Regulations (‘Landesbauordnung’)
LTB	List of technical Building Regulations (‘Liste der Technischen Baubestimmungen’)
MBO	Model (Federal State) Building Regulations (‘Musterbauordnung’)
MLTB	Model List of technical Building Regulations (‘Muster-Liste der technischen Baubestimmung’)
NABau	German Committee for Standards of Civil Engineering (‘Normenausschuss Bauwesen’)

PÜZ	Testing, Monitoring and Certification Authority ('Prüf-, Überwachungs- und Zertifizierungsstellen')
PVB	Polyvinylbutyral
TBS	National technical Assessment Authority ('Nationale technische Bewertungsstelle')
TRAV	Technical Regulations for Safety Barrier Glazing ('Technische Regeln zur Verwendung von absturzsichernden Verglasungen')
TRLV	Technical Regulations for Use of linear-supported Glazing ('Technische Regeln zur Verwendung von linienförmig gelagerten Verglasungen')
TRPV	Technical Regulations for the Design and Execution of point-supported Glazing ('Technische Regeln für die Bemessung und Ausführung punktförmig gelagerter Verglasungen')
TVG	heat-strengthened glass (Teilvorgespanntes Glas)
Ü	Attestation of Conformity ('Übereinstimmungskennzeichen')
VSG	Laminated Safety Glass ('Verbundsicherheitsglas')
ZiE	Approval in Individual Cases ('Zustimmung im Einzelfall')

4.1.1 General Aspects

To keep the regulations manageable, the European and national standards referred to guidelines for detailed regularities in relation to technical and constructional details. Thus, each authority level has influence a defined regulation level, from European authorities through national authorities to federal states' authorities. In general European product standards and European testing standards need to be released by European authorities. Member states are adopt the European product standards and European testing standards to National standards. Already existing national standards that conflict with European standards need to be withdrawn.

Furthermore, individual regulations can be defined by all member states in national annexes of European standards or in national application standards within the limits defined by European standards for individual additions. Additionally, national authorities and federal states' authorities can regulate the application of construction products, means forms of construction, but cannot regulate the construction product itself.

National standards in Germany are released by the department 'Normenausschuss Bauwesen' (NABau) (German Committee for Standards of Civil Engineering) of 'Deutsches Institut für Normung' (DIN) (German Institute for Standardization). If no standard is available, technical guidelines for civil engineering, e.g. released by DIBt, have to be used. Application standards and application guidelines provide regulations for construction planning without complex system analyses. Standards are legally binding if explicit approvals are given by legal authorities or if they are explicitly mentioned in project contracts. German construction supervising authorities for civil engineering and DIBt can release 'Regeln der Technik' (rules of technology) as 'Technische Baubestimmungen' (technical building regulations).

Standards and guidelines are “bauaufsichtlich eingeführt” (officially approved), if listed in the BRL or LTB. The status “bauaufsichtlich eingeführt” promotes standards or guidelines to “Allgemein anerkannte Regeln der Technik” (generally approved rules of technology).

4.1.2 LBO and MBO - Forms of Construction and Construction Products

In Germany, the requirements for construction products and forms of construction are regulated in the building regulations of “Bundesländer” (federal states). The provisions of the “Landesbauordnung” (LBO) (Federal State Building Regulations) are essentially identical because LBO is based on “Musterbauordnung” (MBO) (Model (Federal State) Building Regulations). According to this principle, LBO determines which construction products cannot be used and where they are allowed to be used. It also determines whether a component can be installed or which permissions need to be taken into account and must be applied for. The same applies to forms of construction but in addition of “Liste der Technischen Baubestimmungen” (LTB) (List of technical Building Regulations) that is based on the “Muster-Liste der technischen Baubestimmungen” (MLTB) (Model List of technical Building Regulations).

In the MBO construction products are defined as ‘building materials, building components and constructions that are produced for permanent use in buildings and structures’ as well as ‘prefabricated constructions made of building materials and building components’ (please see 4.1.3). Whereas forms of construction are defined in the MBO as “the assembly of Construction Products to form buildings or structures or parts thereof” (please see 4.1.4).

The Landesbauordnung (LBO) (federal state building code) only determines the application of Construction Products and forms of construction that fulfill a required “Gebrauchstauglichkeit” (serviceability). It means the fulfilling of required performances with a specified period of time. Serviceability is divided into “Verwendbarkeit” (suitability) for construction products and “Anwendbarkeit” (applicability) for forms of construction.

In general, the serviceability is fulfilled for “regulated construction products”, “Other construction products”, “construction products of list C as well as for “forms of Construction” that meet the required performance standards according to the MBO (please see Table 3). CE-marked construction products according to the BauPVO (and the previous regulation of the BPR) are approved for use.

Non-regulated construction products, non-regulated forms of construction and both construction products and forms of construction that differ from main parts of BRL A part 1 or the LTB are not completely excluded from use. As they are approved by the AbZ, the AbP or the ZiE according to the MBO, they also can be used as well.

- AbZ – ‚Allgemeine bauaufsichtliche Zulassung‘ (acc. to §18 of the MBO) (general technical approval) (please see 4.1.4.1)
- AbP – ‚Allgemeines bauaufsichtliches Prüfzeugnis‘ (acc. to §19 of the MBO) (general technical certificate) (please see 4.1.4.2)
- ZiE – ‚Zustimmung im Einzelfall‘ (acc. to §20 of MBO) (approval in individual case) (please see 4.1.4.3)

These instruments regulate the use of new and innovative forms of construction that are not regulated by general regulations. The AbZ, the AbP and the ZiE approvals are given by authorized inspectors or ‘Prüf-, Überwachungs- und Zertifizierungsstellen’ (PÜZ-Stellen) (testing, monitoring and certification authorities). The approvals depend on serviceability proved by authorization inspections, calculative proofs and experimental proofs if necessary.

The list of products is published annually on ‘Bauregelliste’ (BRL) (construction products lists) by ‘Deutsches Institut für Bautechnik’ (DIBt) (german institute for building technology). The list consists of parts A, B and C, in which the corresponding technical rules are made known.

Table 2 gives a review of german and European regulations in dependence of the kind of construction product.

Table 3: Distinction in regulated, non-regulated and other construction products in Germany

Construction products	German regulations				European regulations		
	Regulated products and systems	General	Non-regulated products Inconsiderable requirements and general accepted testing procedures	Constructional subordinated significance	Other products	Regulated products	Non-regulated products
Publication	BRL A Part 1	-	BRL A Part 2	BRL C	Generally approved engineering rules	BRL B	BRL B
Proof of applicability	Technical rules from BRL A	ZiE or AbZ	AbP	No proof of applicability	No proof of applicability	hEN with restriction of applicability	ETA with restriction of applicability
Attestation of conformity	Ü Mark			No Ü Mark		CE Mark	

Building-integrated PV (BIPV) modules are generally not regulated and require proof of application, AbZ or ZiE - if neither standards nor ‘Technical Approval’ exist. These complex and sometimes very costly tests of applicability complicate the marketing and thus the spread of BIPV. For photovoltaic modules that are not installed on the roof, there is no legal security in the traditional sense of.

Therefore, planning authorities must often decide on the construction procedure depending on the individual situation.

The authorized applicability documents define the criteria for construction products and forms of construction. For forms of constructions, the documents specify the composition, dimension limits, installation situation, testing results and quality control terms. All construction products used need to be clearly clarified and the conformity to regulations has to be proved.

4.1.3 Regulated Construction Products

The European Committee for Standardization (CEN) or the “Deutsches Institut für Normung” (DIN) (German Institute for Standardization) can initiate new standards. The draft has to be published for evaluation. During a defined period of time, objections against the draft of the standard can be lodged. After considering the objections, the introduction of the new standard begins. The procedure of introduction for German standards is different from the procedure for European standards. Republished German standards have to be introduced individually by each “Bundesland” (Federal State), i.e. each “Bundesland” is at liberty to decide whether a German standard should be introduced or not.

To introduce a new European standard, first of all the acknowledgment of CEN is necessary. All CEN-members are obliged to accept the European standard as a national standard. Standards of construction products are transferred into national standards without any changes. National CEN-members are allowed to adapt specific European standards, particularly for design and calculation rules, to national standards (e.g. adaption of the partial safety factor). Due to the complex federal system of Germany the procedure of drawing up or introduction can take a lot of time, even several years.

The “Deutsches Institut für Bautechnik” (DIBt) (German Institute of Building Technology) publishes the “Bauregelliste” (BRL) (construction products list) once a year. All national regulations and standards for regulated construction products are referenced in BRL Part A. In BRL Part B the European regulations and standards for regulated construction products are listed.

According to the BRL Part A, regulated construction products and non-regulated construction products with attestation of conformity get labeled with Ü-Mark.

BRL B part 1 and B part 2 list systems that may be placed by provisions of the member states of the European Union and the states parties through the economy to implement the directives of the European communities in traffic and trade. Their detection is a CE marking.

At same time construction products with CE marking alone are not classed as regulated in Germany. For a classification as “regulated” products need to be consistent with national application standards or national guidelines.

The normative description of the construction is limited to the composition, and the properties of the product and an application must be made for a technical building regulation. If this is not the case, it is a non-regulated Construction Product.

Part C of BRL includes construction products for which there are neither technical building regulations nor generally recognized rules of technology. Furthermore, there is a small group of 'other construction'.

Normally, every building project in Germany proceeds in accordance with the existing standards in order to save time and minimize costs. The conformity of the product to the technical rules has to be supervised. These supervisions are self-controls at operational level. In addition, some products as well as structural calculations need to be examined by external authorities, which are examined by an authorised engineer, a so-called structural safety engineer.

4.1.4 Non-regulated Construction Products and Forms of Construction

Besides regulated construction products, non-regulated construction products can also be used in Germany. Non-regulated construction product means that either no standard is valid or the construction product strongly deviates from standards. There are three main ways to deal with non-regulated construction products. As already mentioned in Chapter 4.1.2 there are AbZ, AbP and ZiE.

The more features the PV modules take into the building envelope, the higher the requirements of the LBO and MBO are for PV modules as construction products and forms of construction.

Basically, for every construction, a proof of applicability is required. The proof depends on the kind of construction product. The construction products can be either regulated or non-regulated.

However, the following instruments also allow products and constructions without proof of conformity. In addition, building authorities have a certain scope of action in individual cases.

- 'Allgemeines bauaufsichtliches Prüfzeugnis' (AbP) (general appraisal certificate)
- 'Allgemeine bauaufsichtliche Zulassung' (AbZ) (national technical approval)
- 'European Technical Approval' (ETA or building permit)
- 'Zustimmung im Einzelfall' (ZiE) (approval in individual cases)

Authoritative approvals regulate the designing, dimensioning and constructing. The AbZ, the AbP and the ZiE have reference to technical regulations and passed individual approvals for non-regulated requirements. According to the AbZ general approvals can be done related to capacity and serviceability by tests if there are no performance regulations. Whereas the ZiE is only an individual approval within an individual project. For a selection of other construction products an AbP can be granted. On the European Level, there can ETA be applied for relevant products that are not covered by harmonized European Standard (please see 3.2.3).

4.1.4.1 AbZ - General Technical Approval - 'Allgemeine bauaufsichtliche Zulassung' (AbZ)

General technical Approvals (AbZ) for construction products or Forms of Construction to be granted by German Institute of Building Technology (DIBt). The approval procedure to be applied by the producer and expires after five years, but validity can be extended. Prerequisite is that the products are not covered by European harmonized regulations or National regulations.

In case of very complex construction products and forms of construction the DIBt gets supported by Sachverständigenausschuss (SVA) (Group of authorized Experts). SVA is a group of official building authorities, researchers, testing institutes and economy members.

The AbZ is advantageous for construction products and forms of construction that are used in the same manner for different projects. If a product is the AbZ approved, the approval is only valid for the applying producer and the relevant product. That means that the AbZ approval is not valid for identical products from other producers.

A construction product with the AbZ has an advantage in the German market in comparison to a product without this approval, because the client needs not to apply for an approval in individual cases. This procedure is common e.g. for PV-elements used as laminated safety glass in legal sense. A national technical approval contains all technical relevant dates, which are necessary for an accurate production, for possibly required calculation as well as for the construction on the building site. The DIBt invites the applicant for an intern discussion about the details and requirements of the approval. As a result, necessary calculations, tests and formal requirements are fixed. The test methods have to be regulated in standards or guidelines of approvals. Otherwise, the DIBt to define the conditions of testing. In both cases, the DIBt authorises a testing institute to execute the tests.

The producer of the Construction Product has to cover the costs of the application. The national technical approval is particular useful for manufacturers that deal with perseverative dimensions of a Construction Product. The applicant defines the extent of the approval, which influences, combined with the test complexity, the costs. The other party, the institute that grants the approval, controls the accuracy of statement. In addition to the extent of application, the duration of this process depends also on the capacity of responsible sections of the DIBt. The whole procedure is quite longsome.

Approvals in the field of glass construction exist for overhead glazing, structural sealant glazing, heat-strengthened glass, glass in barriers protecting against a fall from height and glazing supported by point fixings. For glazings with integrated PV modules, there exists currently one national technical approval. The company RWE SCHOTT Solar GmbH received an approval for overhead glazing with the PV module 'ASITHRU-30-SG'. This approval is only valid for glass panes with a maximum size of 1000 mm x 600 mm.

The application of the national technical approval is on the lines of the application of a standard. It is only valid for the therein formulated statements. If anything during the building process clearly deviates from the approval (e.g. other dimensions), it is not valid for this case.

In addition to the national technical approvals, the first European Technical Approvals (ETA) already exist, whose number will certainly increase. ETAs are adapted to national approvals by specific terms of application.

4.1.4.2 AbP – General Technical Certificate – ‘Allgemeines bauaufsichtliches Prüfzeugnis’

The 'Allgemeines bauaufsichtliches Prüfzeugnis' (AbP) (general technical certificate) covers non-regulated construction products with low relevance to safety or, construction products that meet BRL A part 2 or part 3. This kind of proof requires less analysis work than AbZ. The construction product gets tested and certificated by PÜZ Authorities (please see 4.1.5.2). This procedure is common e.g. for the classification of PV as ‘Hard Roofing’ to simplify the application of PV on roofs with regard to regulations. The required approval procedure is determined by the BRL.

4.1.4.3 ZiE - Approval in Individual case - ‘Zustimmung im Einzelfall’ (ZiE)

An alternative to general approvals (AbZ and AbP) is the Approval in individual case (ZiE). The individual approval has to be applied from supervisory authority in charge of the responsible federal state and is nationwide valid for 5 years. The required approval and test procedures depend on the individual safety requirements. Those requirements can vary from one federal state to another. The ZiE is project specific and is not transferable to another, even though the products or systems are identical.

The ZiE is necessary if neither a standard nor a national technical approval exists. The application has to be filed to the supreme construction supervising authority of the appropriate ‘Bundesland’ (federal state) by the building owner. Every application has to contain the name of the planned construction. Amongst calculation and significant drawings, tests are necessary as well. The complexity of these tests depends on the experience and past tests of the authority. If identical building constructions are perseverative, a test repeating of the construction product is generally not necessary. At the beginning of the planning should be already fixed, which requirements of the authority to be met. The approval is not transferable. Every building owner needs a new ZiE for his building object. The building owner has to bear the risk and the costs for the ZiE. Indeed, a proper help of structural engineer and manufacturer is advantageous. Details and responsibilities to be defined in a contract for work and services. The procedure of approval can be simplified if there are experiences available from other building projects.

The application can be quite informal but needs to be documented and has to include the following: (if possible with references):

- Object of application (construction product)
- Construction project
- Applicant
- Building owner
- Designer
- Responsible lower construction supervising authority
- Originator of the static stability calculation and supervising authority of structural safety (office of structural safety or structural safety engineer)
- If necessary authorized expert of testing or authorized testing laboratory of the respective non-regulated construction product

Concerning the content, attention has to be paid for:

- The meaningful and complete description of the non-regulated construction product
- Complete and accordingly prepared documents for the proof of applicability
- No controversial statements
- Timeliness of application

Furthermore, block plans with coloured signs which show the exact positions in the building, detailed drawings and design drawings should be included in the description of the non-regulated construction product.

The proof of application has to be attached to the application form. The proof of static stability will be checked by an office of structural safety or by a structural safety engineer with regard to the category of the building project. The resulting inspection report is needed in the application process as well.

The proof of applicability of non-regulated construction products may require tests and test reports. Tests have to be carried out and analysed by an authorized testing engineer or an authorized testing institution. The test program of special structural components (e.g. façade of structural glass system) has to be arranged with the supreme construction supervising authority.

An expert's report might be needed to evaluate the situation of the usability of the non-regulated construction product. If similar results of comparable tests exist, the tests might not be necessary. The comparability of the results needs to be proven in the expert's report.

The supreme supervising authority for construction gives information which expert of testing or which testing laboratory is authorised for the respective non-regulated construction product.

The fees for the ZiE range between 30 € and 3000 €. The fees depend on administration effort, on importance of the object of application and on economic and further interests of the applicant. The authority demands no fees for public work projects.

Most of the ZiE test methods fulfil demands of safety requirements of the planning and building law. Furthermore, special safety requirements exist for overhead glazing which shall be temporary

accessible for cleaning and inspections. For this kind of glazing the rules of the employers liability insurance association are important. Therefore, attention has to be paid to the safety of people as well.

4.1.5 Ü and CE Mark - Declaration, Certificate and Proof of Conformity

One of the main parts of the building process is the quality control and its binding traceability. It is necessary to keep track of the construction product's quality in order to make sure that the used construction products meets the quality requirements and can be maintained according to the maintenance documents.

If the results of declaration of conformity or the certification of conformity are positive, the product to be CE marked (please see 4.1.5.1). Alternatively to the international CE marking there is the national Ü mark (please see 4.1.5.2).

The national application proofs and Ü marks are only available for Construction Products that are not covered by the harmonized European Standards (hEN) and that are not covered by ETB and as well as for forms of construction that are not covered by application standards.

4.1.5.1 CE - European Proof of Conformity ('Conformité Européenne')

To ensure the identification of the products' conformity to declaration of performance, the BauPVO and as the case may be, some additional EU regulations, the producer to mark the products with CE marks. The conformity is attested by CE mark only, no other mark is admitted for attesting the conformity according to the BauPVO. Figure 4 shows the standardized CE mark.

Figure 4: CE Mark

The conforming products to be CE marked clearly visible, legibly and permanent. The CE mark has to be affixed either to the product itself or a label attached to the product. If no other option is available, the CE mark can be affixed to the packing of product or to the accompanying documents.

European conformity according to the BauPVO is based on five conformity systems. According to this, the conformity can be classified to system 1+, 1, 2+, 3 and 4. The systems regulate the verification of the consistency of the product's performance, the assessment of the product

performances and the monitoring of production. The minimum conformity system is system 4, which covers product's initial testing by producer and producer's self-employed production supervision. Depending on the safety requirements, one of the five systems is used. The higher the safety requirements, the stricter the system is. Information about the authoritative system are given by ETB and Annex ZA of harmonized European Standards (hEN). In view of that the requirements can be e.g. supervision by external authorities, non-recurring or recurring supervisions of production by external authorities and sample product tests by external authorities. The producer is responsible for the accurateness of CE marking. According to this, the producer has sole responsibility for deciding if a new certification process is necessary after product modifications.

Special Case: National Approval can be required although CE Mark

Construction products that are not conform to the hEN can be approved for the European market by ETB according to BauPVO. ETB approved Construction Products can be used as hEN-conform Construction Product. The ETB certificate is valid in each member state.

For the ETB approval, the manufacturer has to apply to a national technical assessment authority that is authorized by all member states. In Germany, the DIBt (German Institute of Building Technique) is authorized as ‚Nationale Technische Bewertungsstelle‘ (TBS) (National technical Approval Authority). For more information about technical approvals, please see chapter 3.2.

Both the hEN and the ETB only regulate the compounding, configurations, performance and the binding marking of Construction Products, but they do not regulate the application and assessment of the construction products as a part of Form of Construction. Due to this fact Construction Products according to the BauPVO or the hEN are only accepted as a part of Form of Construction in Germany, if they meet National Application Standards and National Application Regularities, including LTB (List of Technical Building Regulations). If the construction do not meet the requirements, the construction is classified as ‘non-regulated construction’. As a non-regulated construction, the used construction products to be approved for application by national (German) authorities although the construction products are CE marked according to the BauPVO or the hEN. An example for this procedure is the use of teilvorgespanntes Glas (TVG) (heat-strengthened glass) according to the hEN 1863. The main part of heat-strengthened glass applications are out of the admissible field of application by the LTB and to be approved according to the AbZ.

4.1.5.2 Ü - Declaration and Certificate of Conformity (‘Übereinstimmungsnachweis’)

Products that are not covered by harmonized the European standards (hEN) and that are not approved by ETB (European technical Assessment), can be approved by national regularities and Ü marked. The same applies to forms of construction that are not covered by application standards. Furthermore construction products according to BRL B part 2 has to be Ü marked in addition to CE marking since the international regulations do not define construction-related performances requirements.

The Ü mark has to be visibly and permanently affixed to the product itself, the package of the product or to an additional label – or even to the accompanying documents.

On the Ü mark, the producers name and the name of the accompanying document have to added. (please see Figure 5). Forms of construction do not need to be Ü marked. Construction products declared as “other products” and construction products of BRL C, that do not require application proof or proof of conformity, to be not Ü-marked, even if they meet the material requirements of the LBO.

Figure 5: Ü Mark

The quality control system according to the LBO makes sure that each used construction product and form of construction used meets the requirements of BRL A part 1 or the requirement in the BRL A part 1, e.g. DIN standards or individual approvals according to the AbZ, the AbP or the ZiE. Depending on the individual safety requirements, the BRL, the AbZ, the AbP and the ZiE determine the required conformity system:

- ÜH - Declaration of conformity by the manufacturer
(‘Übereinstimmungserklärung des Herstellers‘ acc. To §23 para. 1 MBO)
- ÜHP - Declaration of conformity by the manufacturer and accredited testing authority
(‘Übereinstimmungserklärung des Herstellers nach vorheriger Prüfung des Bauprodukts durch eine anerkannte Prüfstelle‘ acc. to §23 para. 2 MBO)
- ÜZ - Certificate of conformity by accredited certifying authority
(‘Übereinstimmungszertifikat durch eine anerkannte Zertifizierungsstelle‘ acc. to § 24 MBO)

The conformity system ÜH is based on the producers’ non-recurring self-employed product assessment, the monitoring of the product quality and the production process. In simple cases the manufacturer can declare the ÜH conformity of his products by his own.

In addition to ÜH the ÜHP requires a non-recurring product assessment by an accredited testing authority. For the ÜZ the non-recurring assessment and additional recurring product assessments have to be done by accredited certifying authorities. Depending on the results, the accredited certifying authority can issue the required certificate.

4.1.6 BIPV – Building-integrated Photovoltaic

Photovoltaic modules are not explicitly mentioned in the Building Regulations List (BRL). The CE mark has no legal relevance with regard to building regulation. CE markings can be classified differently depending on the construction and use. PV modules with 'conventional design with mechanically held discs, which have no other design features that are included in other Construction Products. DIN EN 61215 or DIN 61646 and EN 61730 are used as codes of technique. A proof of applicability is not necessary. According to the German construction law PV modules are part of glass construction regulations. The regulations for constructive glass building to be fulfilled. For PV modules that are integrated in roofs, it is fundamental whether the glass products are regulated or non-regulated Construction Products. The additional installation of PV cells (to glass panels) can be substantially neglected, because the Form of Construction is similar to the structural determinations. Design, capacity and durability of construction to be not negatively affected by the additional installation of PV cells.

In general, the design of glass constructions to be based on 'Technische Regeln für die Verwendung von linienförmig gelagerten Verglasungen' (TRLV) (technical rules for the use of the linear-mounted glazing) and 'Technische Regeln für die Bemessung und Ausführung punktförmig gelagerter Verglasungen' (TRPV) (technical rules for the design and execution of point-supported glazing). For vertical glazing, e.g. façades and windows, laminated glass from regulated based glasses and interlayers can also be used. Furthermore, glass-glass laminates with integrated PV cells and PVB layers can be used as well. Requirements for point supported glazing systems are higher, because only 'Verbund-sicherheitsglas' (VSG) (laminated safety glass) is approved for.

VSG are glasses with composite layers of exclusively Polyvinylbutyral (PVB). According to that, PV modules do not comply with the BRL and thus require the AbZ or even the ZiE. Hence, there is no general approval for the use of BIPV modules.

For a general approval for BIPV-laminates the BIPV must fulfill the material characteristics of VSG, according to EN ISO 12543 / EN 14441 by testing of small specimens. It covers all different build-ups of laminates (e.g. layer thicknesses, layer materials). Extensive tests to be done. If the test results of the BIPV are comparable to the VSG with PVB and if the PV lamination has comparable material characteristics to PVB, the BIPV can be used as VSG as defined by required glass regulations.

Part of an individual approval is the proof of structural and safety issues of BIPV, e.g. BIPV must fulfil the material characteristics (strength, residual strength) of VSG. There will be a test of full-size specimens to demonstrate residual strength and load-bearing capacity of intact or broken PV panels.

4.2 National Situation in France

Legend:

ADEME	Environment and Energy Managing Agency ('Agence de l'Environnement et de la maîtrise de l'Energie')
AFAQ	French Association for Quality Certification ('Association Française pour l'Assurance de la Qualité')
AFNOR	French Association of Standardization ('Association Française de Normalisation')
BN	Standardization Bureau ('Bureaux de Normalisation')
BNM	State Metrology Bureau ('Bureau National de Métrologie')
COFRAC	French Accreditation Committee ('Comité Français d'Accréditation')
CCTG	Note-book of Technical General Clauses ('Cahier des Clauses Techniques Générales')
CCTP	Special Documents of Market ('Documents Particuliers du Marché')
CSTB	Scientific and Technical Building Centre ('Centre Scientifique et Technique du Bâtiment')
CTI	Network of Industrial Technical Centres ('Réseau des Centres Techniques Industriels')
DTU	Unified Technical Documents ('Documents Techniques Unifiés')
INERIS	State Institution of Industrial Environment and Risks ('Institut National de l'Environnement Industriel et des Risques')
LCIE	Central Laboratory of Electrical Industries ('Laboratoire Central des Industries Electriques')
LNE	State Trial Laboratory ('Laboratoire National d'Essais')
NF	French standard ('Norme française homologue')
UTE	Technical Union of Electricity ('Union Technique de l'Electricité')
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
IWA	Industry Workshop Agreement

4.2.1 Authorization Framework

The following information is the result of an inquiry submitted to CSTB (Centre Scientifique et Technique du Bâtiment) in France pertaining to the requirements, which are set on PV-façades. Furthermore, information about a possible certifications and permissions is provided.

4.2.1.1 Avis Technique (ATEC), « Technical opinion »

It is possible to request a general avis technique for a PV-façade system. The procedure is similar to requesting an « allgemeine bauaufsichtliche Zulassung » in Germany, even though CSTB is not an authority as DIBT. An ATEC is not required by law, but opens the market. No ATECs for PV-façades have been established yet in contrast to BIPV roofs (approx. 32). Even though they already have ideas about it, the exact procedure on how to qualify a PV-façade would be elaborated by CSTB upon request for a specific system. A granted ATEC will be published.

4.2.1.2 Appréciation Technique d'Expérimentation (ATEX), « Technical appreciation of experimentation »

It is also possible to ask for a qualification for a single project, similar to the German « Zustimmung im Einzelfall ». There are several of these ATEX in preparation. An ATEX must be demanded ahead of the construction, and can be demanded by the contractor, the owner, an insurance company or a technical supervisor. A site visit is required. In contrast to an ATEC, an ATEX is not published.

Possibly relevant norms and standards

- DTU 33.1 (Façades rideaux : curtain walls)
- DTU 39 (Building works - Glazing and mirror glass works)
- EN 13830 (curtain walls)
- EN 12155 (Curtain walling. Watertightness. Laboratory test under static pressure)
- EN 12211 (Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method)
- EN 12179 (Curtain walling. Resistance to wind load. Test method)
- EN12543-4 (Glass in building - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 4: Test methods for durability)

Cahiers du CSTB

- 3075 (Éléments de remplissage de façades légères faisant l'objet d'un Avis Technique - Conditions générales de mise en œuvre)
- 3488 V2 (VEC) (Vitrages extérieurs collés - Cahier des prescriptions techniques)
- 3574 V2 (VEA) (Vitrages extérieurs attachés (VEA) faisant l'objet d'un Avis Technique - Conditions générales de conception, fabrication et de mise en œuvre)
- 3242 (Conditions climatiques à considérer pour le calcul des températures minimales et maximales des vitrages)
- ETAG002

4.2.1.3 Preceding audit

Since a PV-façade does not entirely fit into the framework of standards and rules pertaining to conventional façades, the establisher of a PV-façade must therefore assure compliance with existing standards. An ATEC or ATEX is very helpful in this regards. CSTB also offers an 'Audit' to assess the requirements on a specific PV-façade product, to name the relevant tests to be passed and to list the proofs to be obtained.

4.2.2 Technical aspects

4.2.2.1 Structural sealant glazing (SSG)

SSG is a delicate subject in France. Some requests of producers have already been rejected by the experts group of CSTB due to lack of convincing proofs. The requirements are outlined in VEC3488V2. It is rather unlikely that PV-modules using a polymer backsheet would get an approval.

4.2.2.2 Proof of durability of a glass/glass PV-module (suggestion CSTB)

General requirements without taking into account properties of a specific module design, which might necessitate further tests:

- High temperature boiling water test during 8 h (operating mode B + 6 h) according to EN 12543-4
- UV-test 2000 h according to EN 12543-4
- Bake test 100°C 48 h + 110-140°C / 4 x 1 h according standards of CSTB
- Measurement of coefficients of transmission and reflection of the modules according to EN 410 for calculating the maximal temperatures. For each project a calculation is demanded according to the conditions defined in CSTB3242 to prove that the maximal temperature does not exceed 80°C.

These tests can be done at the CSTB labs.

4.2.2.3 Other tests of façade modules (suggestion CSTB)

The tests related to the compound glass/glass of the PV-module itself are complemented by test related to the functionality of the installation in the façade. These test depend on the type of the façade (ventilated façade, watertight or not, ssg, ...) and on the boundary conditions (height of the glazing, accessibility, protection against falling, balustrade...). Shock tests according to CSTB3228 with 700 to 1200'J might be necessary. For structurally glazed elements, the guideline 'VEC" must be observed (ETAG N°002 and CSTB n°3488), while a 'pass VEC" is recommended. Seismic effects must also be considered and compliance with the related prescriptions must be proven. Furthermore the rules for fire protection must be observed, even though tests are not necessary to achieve an ATEC.

For ventilated façades, tests for air- and water tightness must be foreseen, as well as wind load resistance.

4.3 National Situation in Greece

Legend:

MSP	'Mean System Price'
RES	'Renewable Energy Sources'
DEDDIE S.A	the Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator
PPC	'Public Power Corporation'
THD	'Total Harmonic Distortion'
VDE	'Verband der Elektrotechnik Elektronik Informationstechnik' (German association of electrotechnic, electric applications and information technology)
NTUA	'National Technical University of Athens'
SMA	'SMA Solar Technology AG' German company (inverters)

The current legislation about the authorization procedure, installation, use and income earned from PV systems in Greece is well depicted in the following laws:

- Law 3468/2006: 'Generation of Electricity using Renewable Energy Sources and High-Efficiency Cogeneration of Electricity and Heat and Miscellaneous Provisions'
- Law 3734/2009: 'Promotion of Cogeneration two or more useful forms of energy, regulation of issues related to the Hydroelectric Project Mesochora and other provisions'
- Law 3851/2010: 'Concerning The Acceleration Of The Development Of Renewable Energy Sources'
- Law 4067/2012: 'New Building Code'

It should be noted that there are also several accompanying ministerial decisions and explanatory circulars that elaborate on certain legislative aspects, with the most important being:

- Ministerial decision 13717/4.6.2009: 'Special Program of PV Systems Development in building facilities and especially in flat roofs'
- Ministerial decision 36720/6.9.2010: 'Approval of special terms for the installation of PV and solar systems in buildings and sites within urban planning areas and settlements'
- Ministerial decision 40158/22.9.2010: 'Approval of special terms for the installation of PV and solar systems in buildings and sites outside urban planning areas'
- Ministerial decision 16934/10.8.2012: 'Amendment of Special Program of PV Systems Development in building facilities and especially in flat roofs'

It is clear that there has been an increased number of new policies during the last 5 to 10 years concerning the production of energy from Renewable Energy Sources. However, there still are some aspects that are not dealt with in the existing legal framework.

The most notable omission concerns the safety issues and responsibilities that arise from a PV system. It is clear that during the construction and installation phases the responsibility lies with the company that performs the necessary works, which is obligated to appoint a certified engineer.

However, once the PV system has been completed and is operational there is no clarification concerning who is responsible for any accidents that may occur in the current legislation. As common practice, the owner/manager of the building/property that the PV system is installed holds the responsibility.

In the following sections a detailed presentation of the legal framework is presented, regarding the authorization procedure for the installation of a PV system, the technical requirements and regulations that the PV system must meet as well as the feed-in-tariff system for a connected PV system.

Feed-in-Tariff System

The Feed-in-Tariff system represents the income a producer is going to receive for every produced MWh after the sale contract. This price is constant for 25 years and is dependent on the date that the sale contract is going to be signed (Table 2).

Table 4: Feed-in-Tariff system prices per MWh

	Grid-connected system	
	>100 KW	≤100 KW
August 2012	180.00 (€/MWh)	225.00 (€/MWh)
February 2013	171.90 (€/MWh)	214.88 (€/MWh)
August 2013	164.16 (€/MWh)	205.21 (€/MWh)
February 2013	156.78 (€/MWh)	195.97 (€/MWh)
August 2014	149.72 (€/MWh)	187.15 (€/MWh)
For every year n from 2015 and beyond	1.3 x MSP _{n-1} (€/MWh)	1.4 x MSP _{n-1} (€/MWh)
	<i>MSP: the Mean System Price for the previous year (n-1)</i>	

4.3.1 Authorization Framework

In general, the power generation facilities using RES as well as any other works appurtenant to their construction and operation, including the access roads and the connection lines to the System or the Network shall be allowed to be installed and operate on a lot or an area whereon the applicant has the right of lawful use.

For installations less than, or equal to 10 KW_{peak} that are going to be implemented into building facilities that have residential or commercial use of very small enterprises (enterprises with less than ten (10) employees) the following are in force:

- The existence of a legal and operational electricity connection that belongs to the owner of the building facility is obligatory.
- Part of the thermal load for hot water has to be provided from another renewable energy source, i.e. use of thermal collector.
- Declaration from a certified engineer regarding the installation process and the characteristics of the PV system is required.
- A grid connection contract between the owner of the system and the local Network Distribution Manager, namely the DEDDIE S.A., is established.

- A sale contract between the owner of the system and the Electricity Provider, namely the Public Power Corporation (PPC), determines the constant price that the owner of the installation receives for every KWh_e . The difference between the energy used from the owner and the produced energy from the installation, namely the excess of energy, is the energy that is going to be paid. This contract is valid for 25 years.
- The owner is forbidden to proceed in any change to the installed capacity or to the components of the system for as long as the contract is valid. Only maintenance or repair labor is allowed.

For installations above $10 \text{ KW}_{\text{peak}}$ and less than, or equal to $100 \text{ KW}_{\text{peak}}$ all the above mentioned are being in force and especially:

- A grid connection contract between the owner of the system and the local Network Distribution Manager, namely the DEDDIE S.A., is established.
- A sale contract between the owner of the system and the Electricity Provider, namely the Public Power Corporation (PPC), determines the constant price that the owner of the installation receives for every KWh_e . The difference between the energy used from the owner and the produced energy from the installation, namely the excess of energy, is the energy that is going to be paid. This contract is valid for 25 years.

For installations above $100 \text{ KW}_{\text{peak}}$ and less than, or equal to $1 \text{ MW}_{\text{peak}}$ all the above mentioned are being in force and especially:

- An approval of small-scale construction works by the local authorities is needed.
- A grid connection contract between the owner of the system and the local Network Distribution Manager, namely the DEDDIE S.A., is established.
- A sale contract between the owner of the system and the Electricity Provider, namely the Public Power Corporation (PPC), determines the constant price that the owner of the installation receives for every KWh_e . The difference between the energy used from the owner and the produced energy from the installation, namely the excess of energy, is the energy that is going to be paid. This contract is valid for 25 years.

The following categories are exempted from the obligation of being granted a production authorization:

- persons who own electricity production installations from PV systems of stations with an installed capacity less than or equal to one hundred and fifty ($150 \text{ kW}_{\text{peak}}$), and these installations are located to their property
- PV plants with an installed capacity up to five (5 MWe) built by educational or research bodies of the public or private sector as long as these plants operate exclusively for educational or research purposes
- Autonomous power generation plants using RES without any connection to the System or the Network with an installed capacity less than or equal to five (5 MWe)

- No installation and operation permits are required for power generations plants using RES which are exempted from the obligation of being granted a production authorization. In all cases, for those plants environmental permitting is necessary according to the laws in force. Installations with an installed capacity less than, or equal to twenty (20) KW_{peak} are exempted from an environmental permitting.

Summarizing, the authorization procedure up until the installation and operation of the PV system consists of the following steps:

Table 5: Authorization procedure for PV systems in Greece

1. Appraisal	
2. Preliminary design	2.1 Project definition
	2.2 On-site inspection and measurements
3. Final design	3.1 Full technical & implementation report
	3.2 Tender finalization
4a. Construction permit	≤ 100 kW only declaration from certified engineer
	> 100 kW construction permit required
4b. Environmental permit	≤ 20 kW not required
	> 20 kW environmental permit required
5. Approval of grid connection contract	
6. Sale contract	
7. System installation	
8. System final inspection and approval	
9. System connected to the grid	
10. System operation and maintenance (not mandatory by legislation)	

4.3.1.1 Urban planning regulations

According to the current legislation all PV systems that are going to be installed should meet the following:

- A PV system can be installed to a sloped or flat roof of a legal building including areas such as façades, shadings, terrace's shelter and auxiliary areas such as storeroom and parking areas.
- In case of a sloped roof, the installation must follow this slope and be within the perimetrical borders of the roof.

- In case of a flat roof, the installation must be at least 0.5 m inner from the roof's handrail for safety reasons.
- PV system must be in accordance with the other structures of the building, so that any architectural distortion is avoided.
- Over the ending of stairways or elevator dams any installation is prohibited.

4.3.2 Technical requirements

- PV installations up to five (5) KW_{peak} are connected to the low-voltage grid through one-phase current supply and PV installations up to ten (10) KW_{peak} are connected to the low-voltage grid through three-phase current supply.
- The marginal default settings values for voltage and frequency for protection of the inverter, measured in the output of the inverter are:
 - Voltage: from +15% to -20% of the nominal value (230 V)
 - Frequency: ± 0.5 Hz of the nominal value (50 Hz)
 - Over these marginal values the inverter should be automatically disconnected in 0.5 sec and reconnected after 3 min.
- Current Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) of the inverters should not exceed 5%.
- In case where no isolation transformer exists, current infusion should be no more than 0.5% of the nominal value.
- Protection over the islanding phenomenon is obligatory. Technical report for avoiding this phenomenon must be provided according to norm VDE 0126.
- All the technical specifications regarding the electrical installation and the components of the PV system (PV modules, inverter etc.) through producers' brochures must be provided within the application file.

4.3.3 Examples of BIPV façade systems in Greece

Up until now this novel installation technology is not very well known in Greece and because of that there are only a couple of examples that use integrated PV system to the building structure. A short presentation of two characteristic examples is given below.

4.3.3.1 National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Chemical Engineering Department, located in Zografou, Athens – Greece

In the building of the Chemical Engineering Department in Zografou campus, a PV system of 50 KW_{peak} installed capacity has been integrated in the façade (Figure 1). The PV system consists of mono- and polycrystalline PV modules from SUNLIGHT Corporation, arranged both in portrait and

landscape inclinations (although mainly landscape inclination has been used). Moreover for the conversion of the produced DC current to AC current, Fronius IG family inverters are used. The façade of the building has south orientation which assures increased performance of the system.

Figure 6: BIPV system in the façade of the building of Chemical Engineering Department (NTUA), Zografou campus [Photovoltaic Systems integrated in Buildings, Technical Guide and examples, University of Crete]

This project has been co-funded from the program ‘Thermie’ (40%), NTUA and the Ministry of Development (60%).

4.3.3.2 Retrofitting of apartment block, located in Tauros municipal, Athens – Greece

In this case, during a retrofitting of an apartment block building located in Athens, a PV system has been integrated into the façade of the structure. Different size modules and modules with different technical characteristics (voltage and current) have been used, providing a high freedom factor to the design (Figure 2).

Figure 7: BIPV system installation during retrofitting in an apartment block in Greece [Photovoltaic Systems integrated in Buildings, Technical Guide and examples, University of Crete]

The total installed capacity is 11.9 KW_{peak}. The system consists of (manufacturer: Naps Systems Oy):

- 82 PV modules with nominal power output 100 W (24 V per module)
- 74 PV module with nominal power output 50 W (12 V per module)

For the conversion of the DC current to AC current, SMA inverters are used. The PV system has been integrated in the south side of the building so as to achieve increased performance.

The shape of the PV system forms two inverse pyramids and is connected to the rest of the building structure using a metal frame, giving a modern aesthetic result to the building. The sizing of the PV system was calculated in order to cover the electrical loads that are used for electrolyzing the lighting system of the communal spaces.

- Photovoltaic Systems integrated in Buildings, Technical Guide and examples, University of Crete

4.4 National Situation in Switzerland

Legend:

SIA	Schweizerischer Ingenieur und Architektenverein (Swiss society of engineers and architects)
BauPG	Bauproduktegesetz (Construction Product regulation)
RPG	Raumplanungsgesetz (Swiss federal Land Use Planning Law)
BRL	'Bauregelliste' ('Construction products lists', consisting of part A, B and C)
ZiE	'Zustimmung im Einzelfall' (Approval in individual cases)
AbZ	'Allgemeine bauaufsichtliche Zulassung' ('national technical approval')
AbP	'Allgemeines bauaufsichtliches Prüfzeugnis' ('national approved certificate')
hEN	'harmonisierte Europäische Norm' (harmonised European standard)
ETA	'Europäische Technische Zulassung' (European technical approval)
Ü	'Übereinstimmungsnachweis' (attestation of conformity)
CE	'Conformité Européenne' (European proof of conformity)

4.4.1 General aspects

Buildings in Switzerland are regulated in federal laws as well as in the laws and ordinances of the Cantons. Since Switzerland is a federal state comprised of 26 Cantons, there are 26 different Building Laws. Building permits are usually obtained from the local authority where the construction work is to be performed. The local authority coordinates with the authorities of the Canton and all other instances involved in issuing the building permit.

Building Law or Construction Law in a narrower sense is primarily addressed to all entities (private or public) that wish to construct, modify or demolish a building of any kind.

Buildings, structures and their surroundings have to be designed in such a manner that they, each for themselves and in combination with each other as a whole, give a favorable or pleasing impression. In particular, special attention has to be paid to buildings and land under cultural heritage protection or nature conservation areas.

Buildings also have to comply with these rules:

- the recognized rules of construction have to be adhered to
- no materials may be used that can cause health impediments
- the home hygiene and work hygiene rules have to be adhered to
- adequate fire prevention and protection measures are to be provided
- buildings are to be insulated to achieve as high an energy-efficiency as possible

Switzerland is not a member of the EU, but a member of the European Free Trade Association (EFTA). To facilitate free trade with the EU, Swiss legislation is adapted to EU law in several areas. Switzerland has different requirements related to product safety and unlike the EU, CE marking is not mandatory in Switzerland but if your product has a CE mark can be imported in Switzerland.

In principle, products that are authorised in Switzerland are described by product-specific regulations. The Swiss Technical Regulations Portal lists different products and their related Swiss regulations. In particular for metal for building construction component we have to refer to industrial products and Construction Products that according to the Federal Law on Construction Products (SR 933.0), is defined as any product manufactured with a view to being permanently incorporated into a building or a civil engineering construction.

First, products to be imported to Switzerland have to comply with the Swiss requirements regarding product safety. The distributor (manufacturer or importer) is responsible for the safety of the product. The requirements concerning product safety (of products to be imported into Switzerland) are laid down in:

- Federal Act on Product Safety SR 930.11 of 12 June 2009 (original title: Loi fédérale sur la sécurité des produits).
- Ordinance on the Marketing of Products Manufactured According to Foreign Requirements SR 946.513.8 of 19 May 2010 (original title: Ordonnance réglant la mise sur le marché de produits fabriqués selon des prescriptions techniques étrangères et la surveillance du marché de ceux-ci).

The authority that control the Construction Product market in Switzerland is the Bundesamt für Bauten und Logistik (BBL). It is responsible for the application of the CE mark for building product. Moreover other official bodies in Switzerland are:

- The Canton that provide the law framework for a building construction
- SIA (for the building shell in particular 232-1 and 232-2) which standardized the building construction
- VKF the cantonal association for the fire insurance. It is also the organization of certification accredited by the Swiss confederation for products and persons in the field of fire protection and the head of the cantonal authorities organization and of 19 cantonal institutions of insurance.
- SUVA Swiss Accident Insurance Fund. Suva's business activities are based on the accident insurance law.
- ESTI Eidgenössisches Starkstrominspektorat. The mission of the Federal Inspectorate for Heavy Current Installations ESTI is the safe use of electricity. If you build a PV plant with more than 30 kVA you have to ask a permit to the ESTI and comply with their rules.
- Swissgrid, the national grid company. In its capacity as owner of the transmission system it ensures the secure, reliable and cost-effective operation of the Swiss high-voltage grid. The PV-feed system is administered by Swissgrid.

According to information provided by the Swiss Government for Swiss Exporters the CE Mark is not compulsory in Switzerland except for products for export to the European Union.

4.4.2 Related Standard and guidelines

Normally, every building project in Switzerland proceeds in accordance with the existing standards in order to save time and money. If a standard is used, the requirements of production, calculation or testing have to be kept.

The conformity between the technical rules and the product has to be controlled. These controls are self-controls at operational level.

In Switzerland the requirements for construction works are defined by a company of private law named SIA (Swiss society of engineers and architects), and are typically considered as state of the art. Some of the standards or part of their content are referenced by the law, and are therefore mandatory. SIA has a federalist structure and is composed of active sections on a regional level, four occupational classes and specialized companies which encourage the exchange at the occupational level. Moreover, more than one hundred commissions and working groups take care of the development and the update of the collection of standards SIA in different languages and the representation of the Swiss interests within the framework of European standardization.

The standards collection of the SIA is subdivided into contractual standards, technical standards and standards aimed at the understanding. The technical standards are positioned at product level, building elements (systems), build works and society.

Special attention is given in Switzerland to the fire issues. The coordinator of the fire protection is AEAI 'Association des établissements cantonaux d'assurance incendie', is also the organization of certification accredited by the Swiss confederation for products and persons in the field of fire protection and the head of the cantonal authorities organization and of 19 cantonal institutions of insurance (source Electrosuisse, IP Performance WP6.1).

Electrosuisse is the recognised professional association for electrical, energy and information technology, and also heads the ESTI and publishes electrotechnical standards. Amongst these standards are the low voltage directive, including a section specifically addressed to PV-installations, as well as guidelines for grounding and lightning protection.

The Swiss solar association Swissolar publishes factsheets and a state of the art paper, which summarizes the actual requirements to PV mainly in view of safety aspects, with special attention to fire safety. The last edition of Oct. 2012 however is already outdated, and Swissolar has published some factsheets as update.

According to the Federal Law on Construction Products (SR 933.0), a construction product is defined as any product manufactured with a view to being permanently incorporated into a building or a civil engineering construction. This definition is broad and includes anything from simple materials such

as sand and cement to finished products such as e.g. a prefabricated garage. For lifts, see the chapter on 'Machinery and Equipment'.

In particular in Switzerland there is no BIPV standard or official regulation. This means that normally a BiPV system is considered as the system it is replacing, such as a curtain wall façade or a pitched roof element.

The *Bundesgesetz über die Raumplanung* and in particular the *article 18a* stated that: 'In urban area and agricultural landsites the authorization is given only for the installation of solar system carefully integrated in roofs and/or façades, provided that this entails not affected cultural or natural monuments with cantonal or national importance".

The marketing and in particular the conformity assessment of construction products such as windows or façades are in Switzerland in construction products (Construction Products, SR 933.0) and in the Construction Products Regulation (BauPV, SR.933.01) regulated. According to this Law and the Regulation for the construction windows and façades

4.4.3 Federal Law on Construction (Bauproduktegesetz, BauPG)

This Act regulates the marketing of construction products.

For the purposes of this Act shall be considered as construction products manufactured products to be permanently incorporated in construction works or civil engineering.

Construction products are suitable to be installed if the works (or construction) for which they are properly employed agree with the CPR regulation and in particular satisfy the following requirement:

- mechanical resistance and stability;
- Safety in case of fire;
- hygiene, health and environmental protection;
- safety in use;
- protection against noise;
- economical and efficient use of energy.

Construction products can be either regulated or non-regulated. Harmonized standard are recommended. If you do not exist or are not in preparation specific harmonized standards (on an international level), independent Swiss standardization bodies may be instructed to draw up technical standards.

Evidence of conformity to technical specifications is based on an assessment of compliance and is provided by means of a declaration of conformity by the manufacturer and, where appropriate, by a certificate of conformity issued by a conformity assessment body.

The conformity assessment assumes that the manufacturer has a system of internal control of production.

4.4.4 Construction product regulation (Bauproduktenverordnung, BauPV)

If a construction product is manufactured according to a technical specification, its conformity to the latter must be examined as part of a conformity assessment. Depending on the technical specification should preferably apply one of the following conformity assessment procedures:

- assessment of conformity by the manufacturer;
- conformity assessment by a conformity assessment body accredited

The declaration of conformity is drawn up in an official language of Switzerland or in English. It contains the following information:

- name and address of the manufacturer or his representative domiciled in Switzerland;
- description of the construction product (type, designation, use);
- requirements and technical specifications applied; where appropriate, any special instructions for use;
- if applicable, the name and address of the body for testing or conformity assessment;
- name and position of the person signing the declaration of conformity, the manufacturer or his representative domiciled in Switzerland.

The official body authorized for approval is the Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Testing and Research (EMPA). The Federal Council may designate other private bodies authorized for this purpose.

The technical authorization is valid for five years.

4.4.5 Photovoltaic in buildings

99% of the installation in Switzerland are roof installation and in particular PV system added on flat or sloped roofs and PV system integrated on the roof as multifunctional component (solar tiles).

This is mainly due to the Feed-in Tariff (KEV) which distinguish between: Ground mounted, Building Added and Building integrated.

To date, photovoltaic modules are not explicitly addressed as buildings components in the Swiss construction standards, except for some requirements to the under construction of roofs or fire safety issues. Since this situation leaves to much room for uncertainty, guidelines for how to use PV in buildings are in preparation.

Similar to Germany the CE mark has no legal building regulation relevance. Construction products can be classified differently depending on the construction and use. EN 61215 or DIN 61646 and EN 61730 are used as codes of technique for the photovoltaic part.

According to the type of installation (façades or roof for example) PV modules can be treated as glazing system so the construction rules of constructive glass building must be met. Since concrete Swiss glazing rules do not exist, often German standards are used.

It is included below a summary of the principal rules and the principal regulations, which relate to the development of solar systems in buildings¹:

- In the area of building regulations
 - Swiss building regulations [SIA380/1:2009].
- In the area of fire protection, natural hazards and construction
 - Fire prevention regulations VKF (AICAA)
 - Guide VKF (AICAA) for protective measures of objects
- For the electrical equipment industry
 - Ordinance on the procedure for approval of plans of electrical OPIE (RS 734.25), OLEI (RS 734.31)
 - Ordinance on electrical low voltage NEV (OPIE) (RS 734.26)
 - Ordinance on electrical low voltage NIV (OPBT) (RS 734.2 - RS 734.27)
 - Standard for low voltage installations NIBT (SEV 1000:2010, chapter 7.12 / STI 233.1104)
 - Principles on the systems of lightning protection (SEV 4022:2008)
 - Supplement of SEV4022:2008 for PV-systems
 - Conditions for attachment of the network operator responsible (company rules)
 - IEC and EN regulations
- For the field of installation, operation and maintenance²
 - Ordinance on construction works (OLCostr):
 - Reminder SUVA
- Environment and planning
 - Federal legislation on spatial planning (LPT; RS 700)
 - Federal Law on the protection of the environment (LPAmb RS 814.01) and also the Law on the protection of nature and landscape (RS 451) together with respective ordinances.

¹ NIBT, Standard for low voltage installations

² FCOS Guide Guide to workplace safety issued by the CFSL; <http://guida.cfsi.ch/Default.aspx?LG=it-CH>

WasWo, Brochures, check lists, guidelines and published by Suva, the CFSL and other organizations. <http://www.suva.ch/waswo-i>

4.5 National Situation in Italy

Legend:

CEI	Electrotechnical Italian Committee ('Comitato Elettrotecnico Italiano')
CNMR	Reference Material State Centre ('Centro Nazionale Materiali di Riferimento')
CTI	Italian Thermotechnical Committee ('Comitato Termotecnico Italiano')
EAC	European Accreditation of Certification
SINAL	Laboratory Accreditation State System ('Sistema Nazionale Accreditamento Laboratori')
SINCERT	Certification Organ Accreditation State System ('Sistema Nazionale Accreditamento Organismi di Certificazione')
SIT	Italian Calibration System ('Sistema Nazionale di Taratura')
STANIMUC	Standards for the Manufacturing Industry ('Standard per l'Industria Manifatturiera - Utilizzatori e Costruttori')
UNI	Italian State Standardization Bureau ('Ente Nazionale Italiano di Unificazione')
UNICEMENTO	Agency for Standardization of Hydraulic binder, Mortar, Concrete and Reinforced Concrete ('Ente di Normazione dei Leganti Idraulici, Malte, Calcestruzzi e Cemento Armato')
UNIMET	Standardization of Non-ferrous Metals ('Unificazione Metalli non Ferrosi')
UNIPLAST	Italian Agency for the Standardization of Plastics ('Ente Italiano di Unificazione nelle Materie Plastiche')
UNSIDER	Italian Agency for the Standardization of Metallurgic Materials ('Ente Italiano di Unificazione Siderurgica')
WELAC	Western European Laboratory Accreditation Cooperation

In Italy buildings have to fulfill the requirements prescribed within the Italian law in force. **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** presents a general overview of the main Italian building codes in force while **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** reports the Eurocodes also in force in Italy.

Table 6: Italian law in force

Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni (2008) <i>Building Regulations Italian Code</i>	<u>D.M. 14/01/2008 (Ministerial Decree)</u>	 Ministero delle Infrastrutture
	<u>Nuove Norme Tecniche (New Technical Codes)</u>	
	<u>Allegati e Tabelle (Attachments and tables)</u>	
	<u>Circolare n. 617 del 2/02/2009: Istruzioni per l'applicazione delle Nuove Norme Tecniche per le costruzioni di cui al D.M. 14/01/2008, G.U. n. 47 del 26/2/2009</u>	

Table 7: Eurocodes

Eurocode 1	Actions on structures - Part 1-1: General actions - Densities, self-weight, imposed loads for buildings	
	Actions on structures - Part 2: Traffic loads on bridges	
Eurocode 2	Design of concrete structures - Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings	
Eurocode 3	Progettazione delle strutture di acciaio - Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings	
Eurocode 4	Design of composite steel and concrete structures - Part 1.1: General rules and rules for buildings	
Eurocode 8	Design of structures for earthquake resistance - Part 1: General rules, seismic actions and rules for buildings	
	Design of structures for earthquake resistance Part 3: Assessment and retrofitting of buildings	
	Design of structures for earthquake resistance - Part 5: Foundations, retaining structures and geotechnical aspects	
	Design of structures for earthquake resistance - Part 6: Towers, masts and chimneys	
Eurocode 9	<u>Part 1-1: General - Common rules</u>	
	<u>Part 1-2: General - Structural fire design</u>	
	<u>Part 1-3: Additional rules for structures susceptible to fatigue</u>	
	<u>Part 1-4: Supplementary rules for trapezoidal sheeting</u>	
	<u>Part 1-5: Supplementary rules for shell structures</u>	

Photovoltaic modules are not explicitly mentioned in the Building Regulations Italian Code (Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni (2008)). Indeed the document addresses the following topics:

Foreword

1 Scope and object

2 Safety and expected performance

3 Actions over buildings

4 Residential and commercial buildings

4.1 Construction of concrete

4.2 Construction of steel.

4.3 Construction of composite steel - concrete

- 4.4 Construction of wood
- 4.5 Construction of masonry
- 5 Bridges
- 6 Geotechnical design
- 7 Earthquake design
- 8 Existing buildings
- 9 Static test
- 10 Drawing of structural designs and computation
- 11 Materials and products for structural application
- 12 Technical references
- Annex a: Earthquake
- Annex b: Parameters characterizing the earthquake

The main requirements that the Construction Sector should satisfy (for instance in terms of forces combination, loads, tests, etc) are described according to the typology of construction and to the materials they are made of.

Within the current Italian Building Code no BIPV standard is mentioned, as well as specific legislation for BIPV systems exists. BIPV is not considered as glazing within the Italian law and should be designed in order to fulfill the requirements of the structure (envelope or roof) to whose it is integrated.

4.5.1 Energy Strategy

In Italy the Energy Strategy for the production of electricity from renewable energy sources was introduced in 2005 by **Ministerial Decree of 28 July 2005** (1st feed-in scheme). The feed-in scheme is the programme which grants incentives for electricity generated by photovoltaic (PV) plants connected to the grid.

The scheme is now regulated by the **Ministerial Decree of 5 July 2012** (5th feed-in scheme). The feed in scheme represents the income a producer is going to receive for every produced MWh after the sale contract has been signed.

The scheme below represents the feed-in tariffs (FiT) systems that have been adopted from 2005 to 2013.

Table 8: Energy Strategy: Feed-in Tariff scheme

4.5.2 The fifth feed-in scheme

The **Ministerial Decree of 5 July 2012** (published in ‘Gazzetta Ufficiale’ no. 159 of 10 Jul. 2012) - the so-called 5th feed-in scheme - redefines the rules on support for solar photovoltaic power generation. The new rules entered into force on 27 Aug. 2012, i.e. 45 calendar days after the publication of the relevant Decision adopted by ‘Autorità per l’energia elettrica e il gas’ (AEEG, the Italian electricity and gas regulator).

The tariffs of the 5th feed-in scheme are granted to the following types of plants:
PV plants, divided by type of installation (art. 7, Ministerial Decree of 5 Jul. 2012);
BIPV plants with innovative features (art. 8);
CSP plants (art. 9).

Under the above-mentioned Decree, the plants eligible for feed-in tariffs may be new, upgraded, or totally renovated.

To benefit from feed-in tariffs, PV plants must fulfill the requirements specified in articles 7, 8 and 9 of the Ministerial Decree of 5 July 2012 and in the document ‘Regole Applicative per l’iscrizione al Registro e per il riconoscimento delle tariffe incentivanti’ (implementing rules on enrolment into the Registry and granting of feed-in tariffs).

The catalogue is structured according to the categories indicated in the Guide, like innovative modules (divided into different types of products) and innovative components. Within each category, pages are listed according to different PV module producers and are composed by pictures, site and capacity of the plants, together with remarks showing criteria to be used during their design and installation; products characteristics data of the PV module and the mounting system (if any) are shown. The last part of the catalogue contains a list of single projects of PV façades with the main characteristics of the plants.

Unlike the previous support schemes, the 5th feed-in scheme grants **an all-inclusive feed-in tariff** to the share of net electricity injected into the grid and a **premium tariff** to the share of net electricity consumed on site. The incentives for the BIPV will be in force till the achievement of 6 billions e 700 millions of Euros. This threshold value has been achieved on the 6th of June 2013 and according to the Ministerial Decree 5 July 2012, the expiry of the 5th feed-in scheme is to be specified in the 30th calendar day from the threshold is reached, and consequently the deadline was July 6, 2013.

Probably there will not be a new energy feed in scheme: thus to get to the so-called ‘grid parity’ (ie, when the energy from photovoltaic sources has a cost equal to or less than that produced by the power supply) the market will rely solely on tax bonus of 36% for recovery (50% until 31 December 2013), in addition to discounts for the exchange on the spot already in force.

With the last Decree D.L. 69/2013, the so called ‘Decreto del fare’, actions will be taken for the electrical market in order to reduce the cost of the power bill for consumer. A revision of the incentives scheme for renewables is also foreseen in the near future, although at the moment no details have been provided.

4.5.3 Authorization Framework

Legislative Decree No 112/1998 made the regions responsible for the administrative duties relating to energy - including renewable sources, electricity, oil and gas – which were not reserved for the State or assigned to local authorities. **Constitutional Law No 3/2001** altered the division of responsibilities between the State and the regions. As a result, within the renewable energy sector, the State has legislative power whilst the regions have administrative power. Under the new system, matters relating to ‘production, transportation and national distribution of energy’ are assigned to the concurrent legislation of the State and the regions. It therefore falls to the State to establish, through its own laws, the fundamental principles for each subject, and to the regions to exercise their legislative power within the limits of the fundamental principles expressly set out by the State.

There is a great deal of overlap and interaction between spatial planning and planning in this sector (for energy use, waste, land reclamation, transport, water, etc.), and this can be particularly complex.

Law No 10/1991 ‘*Regulations for the implementation of the National Energy Plan in matters of rational energy use, energy saving and development of renewable energy sources*’ introduced the **Regional Energy Plan** to the planning context. Using this measure, regions are planning their interventions in the energy field, governing the actions of local authorities and harmonizing the decisions taken at the various levels of spatial planning. The Energy Plan contains the starting points, short-, medium- and long-term strategic objectives, practical instructions, tools available, legislative and regulatory reference frameworks, funding opportunities, constraints, obligations, and rights of economic operators in the sector, of large-scale consumers and of normal users. In short the Energy Plan represents the main reference point for public and private entities intending to take energy-related initiatives within the territory covered by the Plan. The regional energy plans, although based on free entrepreneurial initiative, also aim to give some direction to operations in the sector. Moreover, as well as having environmental implications, energy choices must also be combined with spatial management decisions. It is not by chance that many of the plans are entitled ‘Regional Energy and Environment Plan’.

The regulatory references for photovoltaic authorization procedures vary depending on whether the operation relates to electricity production, heating and cooling, biofuels or networks. The authorization procedure for photovoltaic systems is reported in the table below.

Table 9: Authorization procedure for photovoltaic systems

Source	Operational mode of installation	Procedure according to the urban plan	Competent authority
Photovoltaic	Photovoltaic systems fixed to or (partially) integrated into building roofs on the same slope and with the same orientation as the pitch and whose components do not alter the outlook of the buildings themselves	No one. Free building activity. (ordinary maintenance)	Communication/ notification to Municipality
	Integrated photovoltaic systems on the same slope and with the same orientation as the pitch and whose components do alter the outlook of the buildings themselves	DIA (Commencement notice)	Municipality
	Systems not integrated (>20kW)	DIA (Commencement notice)	Municipality
	Systems not integrated (<20kW)	Single Authorization	Province (single authorization)

According to the specific type of works to be carried out some of the authorization procedures indicated could also foresee the completion of the environmental impact assessment procedure.

More specifically, these are the types of operation covered by Legislative Decree No 152/2006: Projects subject to environmental impact assessment for which the State is responsible:

- power plants and other combustion plants with a heating capacity of at least 300 MW;

Projects subject to environmental impact assessment for which the Region is responsible:

- power plants for the production of electricity, steam and hot water with total heat capacity greater than 150 MW;

Projects subject to applicability screening for which the Region is responsible:

- power plants for the production of electricity, steam and hot water with total heat capacity greater than 50 MW;

For the implementation of plans and schemes which may have a significant environmental impact (including, for example, the Electricity Network Development Plan), Legislative Decree No 152/2006 also provides for screening for the applicability of the Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) defined under Directive 2001/42/EC.

The authorization procedure for the production of electricity from renewable energy sources was introduced by Legislative Decree No 387/2003, implementing Directive 2001/77/EC. Article 12 of this regulation (included in Annex 4.2.1.B) provides that the construction and operation of electricity production plants powered by renewable sources, and modification, expansion, total or partial reconstruction, and reactivation operations and connected works, as well as those connected to infrastructure essential for the construction and operation of the same plants are subject to a single

authorization. This document concludes a procedure lasting a maximum of 180 days. The main aim of introducing this procedure was the rationalization and simplification of the authorization procedure for production plants using renewable sources. In fact, the single authorization is issued in accordance with the current regulations for the protection of the environment, landscape and historical / artistic heritage within a single procedure in which all the authorities concerned participate. Where necessary, the plant and connected infrastructure must comply with environmental impact assessment regulations.

The single authorization grants the right to construct and operate the plant in accordance with the approved plans and, where necessary, with the declaration of public interest, necessity and urgency. The single authorization is in itself a change to the urban planning instrument. The requirements of countryside protection plans remain mandatory. The authorization cites any conditions applicable to the construction and operation of the plant; it also defines the procedures to be followed for the rehabilitation of the site once the plant is decommissioned (or, for hydroelectric plants, procedures for fulfilling the obligation to take environmental recovery and reintegration measures). The single authorization sets deadlines for the start and end of works, and once these have passed the authorization ceases to be effective, unless it is extended.

This simplified procedure applies to plants with a generation capacity below the thresholds indicated in the table below included in an annex to Legislative Decree No 387/2003.

Table 10: Generation capacity

TECHNOLOGY	THRESHOLD (kW)
Wind	60
Solar Photovoltaic	20
Hydraulic	100
Biomass	200
Landfill gas, residual gases from purification processes and biogas	250

For plants which do not exceed the thresholds indicated above, the commencement notice requirement applies in accordance with Presidential Decree No 380/2001. A decree from the Ministry for Economic Development, in consultation with the Ministry for the Environment, Land and Sea and in agreement with the Unified Conference, could define higher generation capacity thresholds and additional installation site characteristics to which the same commencement notice requirement would apply. The Community Law of 2009 made the Italian Government responsible for extending the use of commencement notices to renewable energy plants with a capacity below 1 MW. Article 11 of Legislative Decree No 115/2008 introduced further simplification and rationalization measures for photovoltaic systems fixed to or integrated into building roofs on the same slope and with the same orientation as the pitch and whose components do not alter the outlook of the buildings themselves.

For plants installed in buildings or on sites protected by town-planning constraints or heritage or countryside protection measures, the necessary local permits must be attached to the commencement notice, for example the countryside protection or National Park Authority clearance. There are two types of architectural restriction which apply to refurbishment work, both provided by

the Cultural Heritage Code (Decree-Law No 42 of 22 January 2004). The first is the **countryside protection measure**, which is imposed by local authorities through the Regulatory Plans or at times through specific Countryside Plans. The other constraint is the **cultural heritage protection measure**, which protects elements of artistic, historical, archeological or ethnological value. This constraint applies to individual 'objects', which include buildings, and is imposed by the state, through the Services of the Ministry for Cultural Heritage. The installation of such systems is in fact considered an ordinary maintenance operation and is therefore not subject to the commencement notice requirement.

Decree-Law No 40 of 25 March 2010 recently amended Article 6 of Presidential Decree No 380/2001 by establishing that all photovoltaic panels serving buildings outside category A areas (historic centres) can be installed without any authorization being required. Lastly, Article 27(20) of **Law No 99/2009** established that the installation and operation of micro-cogeneration systems (no larger than 50 kW) are subject only to notification, to be given to the competent authority under Presidential Decree No 380/2001. In accordance with **Legislative Decree No 56/2010**, the installation and operation of units of up to 1 MW or 3 MWt are subject to the commencement notice requirement.

To summarize several authorities are involved in giving authorization: the Ministry for Economic Development and the Ministry for the Environment, Land and Sea for the construction and operation of infrastructure which falls within the national transmission network development plan; the regions for network infrastructure which does not fall within the national transmission network development plan; the regions and provinces, when appointed by the regions, for renewable energy plants; the municipalities for works which can be carried out by giving notification or a commencement notice. With the exception of plants which can be created by giving simple notification, the authorities responsible for the protection of specific interests are also involved. To ensure coordination between the administrative bodies made responsible for protecting various matters of public interest within a single administrative procedure, the authority responsible for the procedure convenes a Services Conference in order to facilitate horizontal and vertical coordination between the various administrations and entities involved.

4.5.4 Technical aspects

According to the attachment 1-A to DM 5/7/12 – ‘Technical codes’, PV modules should be approved and verified by accredited laboratories, for specific modules approval, according to UNI CEI EN ISO/IEC 17025.

Such laboratories must be approved by ‘European Accreditation Agreement’ (Organismi di accreditamento appartenenti all'EA) or must have established mutual recognition agreements with EA or about ILAC (International Laboratory Accreditation Cooperation).

PV and BIPV modules must comply with prescriptions included into the following technical regulations, including any variants, upgrades and extensions subsequently adopted by the regulatory bodies mentioned.

Photovoltaic modules

- CEI EN 61215 (CEI 82-8): Crystalline silicon PV modules for terrestrial applications. Design qualification and type approval;
- CEI EN 61646 (CEI 82-12): Photovoltaic (PV) thin-film modules for terrestrial uses - Design qualification and type approval;
- CEI EN 62108 (CEI 82-30): Modules and concentrated photovoltaic systems (CPV) - Design qualification and type approval;
- CEI EN 61730-1 (CEI 82-27): Qualification for the safety of photovoltaic (PV) modules - Part 1: Requirements for the construction;
- CEI EN 61730-2 (CEI 82-28): Qualification for the safety of photovoltaic (PV) modules - Part 1: Requirements for tests;
- CEI EN 60904: Photovoltaic devices - Series;
- CEI EN 50380 (CEI 82-22): Information sheets for photovoltaic modules;
- CEI EN 50521 (CEI 82-31): Connectors for photovoltaic systems - Safety requirements and testing;
- CEI UNI EN ISO/IEC 17025:2008: General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories.

Other components of photovoltaic systems

- CEI EN 62093 (CEI 82-24): PV system components - modules excluded (BOS) - Design qualification under natural environmental conditions;
- CEI EN 50524 (CEI 82-34): Information sheets photovoltaic converters;
- CEI EN 50530 (CEI 82-35): Overall efficiency of inverters for photovoltaic plants connected to the grid;
- EN 62116 Test procedure of islanding prevention measures for utility-interconnected photovoltaic inverters.

According to the attachment 1-B to DM 5/7/12 – ‘Technical codes’ PV modules should be designed with components that comply with the requirements included into Guida CEI 82-25.

Electrical and photovoltaic systems and the related design must comply with prescriptions included into the technical regulations reported below, including any variations, upgrades and extensions subsequently adopted by the regulatory bodies mentioned.

Photovoltaic design

- CEI 82-25: Guide to the realization of photovoltaic power generation systems connected to the electricity networks of medium and low voltage;
- CEI 0-2: Guide for the definition of project documentation for electrical installations;
- UNI 10349: Buildings heating and cooling. Climatic data;
- UNI/TR 11328-1:2009 ‘ Solar energy - calculation of contributions for building applications - Part 1: Evaluation of radiant energy received ‘

Electric and photovoltaic systems

- CEI EN 61724 (CEI 82-15): Measurement of the performance of PV systems - Guidelines for the measurement, exchange and analysis of data;
- EN 62446 (CEI 82-38): Grid connected photovoltaic systems - Minimum requirements for system documentation, commissioning tests and inspection;
- CEI 64-8: Electrical systems using a nominal voltage not exceeding 1000 V ac and 1500 V dc;
- CEI EN 60445 (CEI 16-2): Basic and safety principles for man-machine interface, marking and identification - Identification of equipment terminals and conductor ends and designated and general rules for an alphanumeric system;
- CEI EN 60529 (CEI 70-1): Degrees of protection provided by enclosures (IP code);
- CEI EN 60555-1 (CEI 77-2): Disturbances in supply systems caused by household appliances and similar electrical equipment - Part 1: Definitions);
- CEI EN 61000-3-2 (CEI 110-31): Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) - Part 3: Limits - Section 2: Limits for harmonic current emissions (equipment input current ≤ 16 A per phase);
- CEI 13-4: Measurement systems in electricity - Composition, accuracy and verification;
- CEI EN 62053-21 (CEI 13-43): Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Particular requirements - Part 21: Static meters for active energy (classes 1 and 2);
- CEI EN 62053-23 (CEI 13-45): Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Particular requirements - Part 23: Static meters for reactive energy (classes 2 and 3);
- CEI EN 50470-1 (CEI 13-52): Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Part 1: General requirements, tests and test conditions - Metering equipment (class indexes A, B and C);
- CEI EN 50470-3 (CEI 13-54): Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Part 3: Particular requirements - Static meters for active energy (class indexes A, B and C);
- CEI EN 62305 (CEI 81-10): Protection against lightning, series;
- CEI 81-3: Mean values of the number of lightning strikes per year and on the ground per square kilometer;
- CEI EN 60099-1 (CEI 37-1): Arresters - Part 1: unloaders nonlinear resistors with spark gaps for ac systems;
- CEI EN 60439 (CEI 17-13): Gear assemblies and control equipment for low voltage (LV switchboards), series;
- CEI 20-19: Rubber insulated cables with a rated voltage not exceeding 450/750V;
- CEI 20-20: PVC insulated cables with a rated voltage not exceeding 450/750V;
- CEI 20-91: Electric cables insulated and sheathed with halogen-free elastomeric, flame retardant with a rated voltage not exceeding 1000 V ac and 1500 V dc for photovoltaic applications.

Photovoltaic connection to the grid

- CEI 0-16: Reference technical rules for connecting active and passive users to HV and MV electricity distribution companies;
- CEI 0-21: Reference technical rules for connecting active and passive users BT networks of electricity distribution companies;
- CEI EN 50438 (CEI 311-1): Requirements for the connection of micro-generators in parallel with the public supply systems in low voltage.

Furthermore, according to the attachment 4 to DM 5/7/12 – ‘Prescriptions’ the following characteristics and installation procedures for building integrated innovative systems should be fulfilled.

Indeed, to be eligible for the tariffs, PV systems must use modules and components having the following characteristics:

1. innovative modules and components which are specifically designed to integrate and replace architectural elements of buildings with a calculable energy performance, such as:
 - a) roofings of buildings;
 - b) vertical opaque surfaces;
 - c) transparent or semi-transparent surfaces on coverings;
 - d) open able and like surfaces, e.g. doors, windows and glazings (even if they are not
 - open able) including frames.
2. modules and components with significant technological innovations;
3. modules which are industrially designed and manufactured in order to guarantee both the energy production as well as architectural functions like:
 - a) protection or thermal regulation of the building. The module or the component
 - must preserve the building energy needs and have a thermal transmittance
 - equivalent to that of the architectural component replaced.
 - b) modules and components designed and installed to ensure the water-tight seal
 - of the building structure.
 - c) modules and components designed and installed to ensure a mechanical seal
 - equivalent to that of the building element replaced.

Then to be eligible for the tariffs, modules and components must be installed according to the following criteria and installation procedures:

1. they must replace architectural components of buildings;
 2. they must also have a coating role of parts of the structure, replacing other building elements that otherwise are not used for the production of electricity;
- from an aesthetic point of view, the PV system must in any case fit harmoniously to the architecture of the building.

From **fire safety** point of view the installation of photovoltaic systems in itself is not among the activities subject to fire prevention inspections but it may pose a risk to the safety of emergency rescue to extinguish a fire or in case of other type of accident, increasing the level of fire risk if a service activity subject to controls.

The Department of Fire published in February 2012 **a guide to the installation of photovoltaic systems**. The current regulations related to the installation of photovoltaic systems are not always compatible with those related to the building envelope. The building envelope elements, for example, must be fire resistant and photovoltaic panels today are not. Another critical aspect concerns the impact resistance: a photovoltaic system integrated in the building must be able to resist a strong impact while maintaining high safety standards. This means that the glass can break, but should not in any way injure persons or to be crossed by any sources of danger to the occupants of the building.

4.5.5 Conclusion

In Italy there are no specific codes related to BIPV in particular as well as particular procedures for assembling PV modules in the building envelopes. BIPV is not considered as glazing in the law and it doesn't requires any special PV-product approvals. BIPV should respect the requirements imposed by the envelope/roof structure it is applied to. It's also important to take into account, especially in Italy, that in historical towns there could exist specific requirement set by the public authority.

Concerning responsibilities issues, in case something goes wrong and the maintenance has been carried out as planned, the responsibility falls on the consultant. In the case of lack of maintenance, the responsibility falls on the owner / user.

4.6 National Situation in Spain

4.6.1 Authorization Framework

In Spain, PV is mentioned in the Building Code Basic Document DB HE, chapter 5 (http://www.codigotecnico.org/cte/export/sites/default/web/galerias/archivos/documentosCTE/DB_HE/DBHE-2013-11-08.pdf). Anyway the document is more related to where these PV systems are ‘mandatory’ (if it can propose other renewable alternative it is ok) depending on type of building (Commercial, Public residential, administrative, industrial, etc) and its size (floor area m²). Indeed the document also specify:

- Capacity of the installation depending on the climatic area in Spain.
- Power loss limitation because of bad orientation or tilt and shadows from other buildings.

BIPV is not considered as glazing in the law, in the sense that if the PV module is not part of the building envelope it should be designed (the panel and the structure) to support the action of exterior ambient agents such as wind, snow, rain and hail. In case it's part of the building envelope (integration) it should also comply with airtightness, water tightness, fire protection, etc., the same as any other façade module.

4.6.2 Requirements

Therefore if the PV-module is fully integrated can be considered a regular part of the building. In the table below the requirements in Spanish Building Code for a Curtain Wall and an external cladding system which are consider the most common construction systems for PV modules integration into the façade are shown.

The building law only refers to Spanish Building Code. Within the document there is not any mention to the procedures for assembling PV in the building envelope in your country.

There are two EU Standards that are considered relevant for application of PV modules into the façade: EN 61215:2006 and EN 61646:2009.

Table 11: Requirements for curtain walls

ER	SPANISH BUILDING CODE	EN-13830		
		Class/Declared value	EU Standard	
2	Reaction to fire	B-s3-d2	Euroclasses A – E	EN 13501-1
	Fire resistance	EI60	E15 - E90 / EI15 - EI90	EN 13501-2
3	Water tightness	Impermeability ratio: GI5	R4 - RExxx	EN 12154
		Dilatation joints: sealant depth >= 1cm. Relation depth/width: 0,5 to 2		
		Thermal insulation material: water repellent.		
Water vapour permeability	Superficial condensation RH <= 80%	No performance determined		
	Internal condensation: Avoiding material damages			
Content and/or release of dangerous substances	No exigence	No performance determined		
4	Overloading mechanical resistance	C5 = 3 (kN/m)	Horizontal live load resistance	EN 1991-1-1
		C3, C4, E, F = 1,6 (kN/m)		
		Others = 0,8 (kN/m)		
Wind load resistance	Maximum pressure load = 2600 (Pa)	Design wind pressure (L/200 or 15mm)	EN-12179	
Mechanical resistance	EN 1991-1-1	Design dead load (L/500 or 3mm)	EN 1991-1-1	
Resistance to seismic actions	National standard (NSCE)	National regulation		
Dynamic load resistance; large soft body impact	No exigence	Internal Impact (I0 - I5)	EN-12600	EN-14019
		External Impact (E0 - E5)		
Dynamic load resistance; small hard body impact	No exigence	No performance determined		
Equipotentiality	No exigence	Declared value (Ω)	EN-13830	
Eccentric vertical load resistance	Not relevant	No performance determined		
5 Airborne sound insulation	$R_{A,tr} = 53$ dBA	$R_w (C;C_{tr})$	EN ISO 717-1	
6 Thermal transmittance	No exigence	U_{cw}	EN 13947:2011	
Air permeability	$27 \text{ m}^3/(\text{h}\cdot\text{m}^2)$ at 100 Pa	A1 - AE	EN 12152	

Table 12: Requirements for cladding

ER	SPANISH BUILDING CODE	ETAG-034		
		Class/Use category/Numeric value	EU Standard	
2	Reaction to fire	B-s3-d2	Euroclasses A – E	
	Fire resistance	No exigence	Not relevant	
3	Content and/or release of dangerous substances	No exigence	Indication of dangerous substances incl. concentration	
	Water tightness	No exigence	Not relevant	
	Water vapour permeability	No exigence	Not relevant	
4	Overloading mechanical resistance	Not relevant	Pass/Fail	
	Wind load resistance	Maximum pressure load = 2600 (Pa)	Failing Pressure load (Q)	
	Mechanical resistance	EN 1991-1-1	Bending strength, modulus of elasticity and rupture of the cladding element.	ETAG-034
			Pull-out resistance of fixings.	ETAG-034
	Resistance to seismic actions	National standard (NSCE)	National regulation	
	Dynamic load resistance; large soft body impact	No exigence	Use category I, II, III or IV	ISO 7892:1988 ISO/DIS 7893:1990
	Dynamic load resistance; small hard body impact	No exigence		ISO 7892:1988 ISO/DIS 7893:1990
	Eccentric vertical load resistance	Not relevant	Not relevant	
5	Airborne sound insulation	No exigence	Not relevant	
6	Thermal transmittance	No exigence	Not relevant	

4.7 National Situation in the Netherlands

Legend:

BRL	Nationale Beoordelingsrichtlijnen - Dutch Guideline
ECN	Energy Research Centre of the Netherlands
KOMO	Dutch Quality Mark
NEN	Dutch Committee for Standardization / Dutch Standards
NTA	Nederlandse Technische Afspraak
NVN	Dutch pre-standard
TNO	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research
VMRG	Vereniging Metalen Ramen en Gevelbranche - Dutch organisation in the cladding industry

This chapter is part of Deliverable 6.1 of the EU project IP Performance. The document will be update in the future.

In the Netherlands all buildings have to fulfill the requirements laid down in ‘het Bouwbesluit’ (<http://vrom.bouwbesluit.com/>), the Building Code, which is part of the Dutch Housing Law ‘Woningwet’. This building code describes all technical prescriptions both for new buildings and renovation buildings. The regulations are divided into two groups: usage specific requirements and building specific requirements.

The Dutch Building Code contains requirements for safety, health, usability, energy conservation, and environment. The first version originates from 1st January 2003. The current version is updated on 1st July 2013, with some more stringent constraints on energy isolation. The municipal authority is always checking if the building plans are conform the Building Code, before granting a building permit. The Building Code refers for the largest part to building standards and quality certificates. Standards are coming from the Dutch Normalization Institute, which is called ‘Nederlands Normalisatie Instituut’ and abbreviated by NEN (<http://www.nen.nl/>). The Building Code also refers to the European Eurocodes.

Quality certificates may be given by institutions that are recognized by the National Council of Accreditation. Within the Netherlands, there are about ten institutes that have this accreditation. Examples (not exhaustive list) are: KOMO, KIWA, IKO-BKB, BDA, and Bureau Veritas⁸.

From August 2007 dates the first Dutch Pre-norm for BIPV: NVN7250. The deadline for a final feedback session on the official text has just passed in mid November 2013. A few months might be needed to deal with this feedback. After that in the first quarter of 2014, the official version will be expected. In the abbreviation the ‘V’ stands for ‘pre’ and will be replaced by ‘E’ for netherlands, therefore this norm will be called NEN7250:2014. Like in the Building Code, the norm refers to all the relevant Dutch building standards (NEN) and the relevant Eurocodes.

Already since 2005 there is a best practices installation guideline called ‘ISSO78: Handleiding Zonnestroom voor Ontwerper en Installateur’. Because of the raising interest in good quality PV-

installation, the major stakeholders and knowledge institutes of the Netherlands have joined hands to extend this guideline. This resulted in the comprehensive book 'Zonne-energie: bouwkundige- en installatietechnische richtlijnen voor zonne-energiesystemen'⁹, which contains all relevant background, explanations, and practical guidelines for the installers. Since 2011, the 'Duurzame Energie Prestatie Keur (DEPK)' has a certification mark for solar thermal systems and installation companies. Since mid 2013, this certification mark has been extended to solar PV systems.

4.8 National Situation in Austria

Legend:

BGG	‘Salzburger Bebauungsgrundlagengesetz‘ (Federal law about basic building principles)
LGBI	‘Landesgesetzblatt‘ (Federal state law sheet)
BauPolG	‘Salzburger Baupolizeigesetz‘ (Federal building regulation law)
OSchG	‘Salzburger Ortsbildschutzgesetz‘ (Federal law for the protection of the townscape)
ROG	‘Salzburger Raumordnungsgesetz‘ (Federal land-use planning law)
ÖNORM	Norm of the Austrian Standard Institute
ETA	‘European technical approval‘
ÖTZ	‘Österreichisch technische Zulassung‘ (Austrian technical approval)
OIB	‘Österreichisches Institut für Bautechnik‘ (Austrian Institute for building technique)
ÖA	‘Baustoffliste ÖA‘ (list of building materials conforming with Austrian law)
CE	‘Conformité Européenne‘ (European proof of conformity)
ÜA	‘übereinstimmung Austria‘ (mark for building materials conforming with ÖA-list)
ÖE	‘Baustoffliste ÖE‘ (list of building materials conforming with European law)
ÖVE	‘Österreichischer Verband für Elektrotechnik‘ (Austrian association for electrical engineering)

In Austria the federal states are responsible for the building law respectively for the construction law. Exemplary below listed the building laws for the federal state of Salzburg³:

- Salzburger Bebauungsgrundlagengesetz (BGG) v. 27. Juni 1968. Letzte Aktualisierung: LGBI 118/2009.
- Salzburger Baupolizeigesetz 1997 (BauPolG) letzte Änderung: LGBI 20/2010,
- Salzburger Bautechnikgesetz (BauTG),
- Salzburger Garagen-Verordnung, letzte Änderung StF: LGBL Nr 1/2004
- Salzburger Ortsbildschutzgesetz 1999 - (OSchG), letzte Änderung: LGBI.Nr. 58/2009.
- Salzburger Raumordnungsgesetz (ROG 2009)

Furthermore there is the Austrian institute for Construction engineering (Österreichisches Institut für Bautechnik – OIB)⁴. The OIB is coordinating platform for the federal states of Austria regarding construction standards and building laws, especially for the implementation of the new EU construction products regulation.

³ <http://www.bauordnungen.de/html/osterreich.html>

⁴ <http://www.oib.or.at/>

4.8.1 Authorization Framework

In Austria exists the ÖNORM, which is in technical terms of use the pendant to the German DIN. Some German norms are already overtaken by the ÖNORM.

4.8.1.1 Building products regulations

In case of non-regulated building products the OIB is the accreditation body for standard and calibration tests for building products as well as the national institute for European technical approvals (ETA).

The federal states are responsible for the national technical approvals (österreichisch technische Zulassung – ÖTZ) and the OIB is responsible for the publication of these approvals.

Furthermore the OIB publishes the Austrian list of building materials (ÖA). The ÖA determines the required approval for their use to building materials which are not subjected to the CE mark. Visually documented and thus becomes recognizable to the user of the building materials to meet these requirements with the installation mark ÜA, which must be affixed to the product in a suitable form. Basis for the attachment of the mounting mark ÜA by the manufacturer is presenting a positive certificate of conformity or a manufacturer's declaration.

The materials list ÖA of the Austrian Institute of Construction Engineering (OIB) is issued as a regulation.

The use of CE-marked construction products in Austria is regulated by the material list ÖE, published by the Austrian Institute for Building Technology as the 'Order of the Austrian Institute for Building on the material list ÖE'.

4.8.1.2 Standards for PV and BIPV

Basically subject photovoltaic systems building law, under which all connected with the ground plants produced from construction and fall. With the ever-increasing share of Integration into the building envelope are therefore increased the building code requirements for Photovoltaic modules, in addition to federal regulations, in particular the country's legal Provisions of the individual states are important.

Electrical standards

Since there is no applicable standards for building-integrated modules must when installing on conventional Standards be used . Generally, the following rules are important:

- ÖVE / ÖNORM E 8001 (protection measures in the field of electricity),
- ÖVE / ÖNORM E 2750 (general requirements , requirements modules , wiring, Inverters, etc.) ,

- ÖVE / ÖNORM EN 61730 (Design and material of the modules) ,
- ÖVE / ÖNORM EN 61215 (Design qualification and approval - crystalline modules) and
- ÖVE / ÖNORM EN 61646 (Design qualification and approval - Thin-film modules)

Standards for the use of glass in construction

- EN 14449 (Laminated glass and laminated safety glass of conformity / Product standard)
- EN 12600 (Pendulum test - Impact test method and classification for flat glass)
- EN 356 (safety glazing - Testing and classification of resistance against manual attack)
- EN 12150-2 (Thermally toughened soda lime silicate safety glass - Part 2 : Evaluation of conformity / Product standard)
- EN 1863-2 (Heat strengthened soda lime silicate glass - Part 2 : Evaluation of conformity / Product standard)
- EN ISO 1279 (insulating glass)
- EN ISO 12543 (Laminated glass and laminated safety glass)
- EN 1063 (Safety glazing - Testing and classification of resistance against fire)⁵

⁵ Hubert Fechner, Erik Sehnal, FH Technikum Wien, Univ.Prof. Reinhard Haas, Assun López-Polo, TU Wien unter Mitwirkung von Daniela Kletzan-Slamanig, WIFO - Gebäudeintegrierte Photovoltaik Teil 1, Technologiestatus, Erfahrungen, Best Practice-Beispiele und Visionen der GIPV Technologie

5 Review of Standards for Integrating BIPV-Modules in Building Façade and Roof

On the following pages all relevant standards for integrated BIPV-modules in building facade and roof are listed. Due to the huge number of standards, two variations of tables are shown in the present document. In chapter 5 the standards are listed in tables, optimized for paper size DIN A4. In attachment the original table is shown, optimized for work on computer screen.

5.1 European standards

		Category A Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	Category B Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	Category C transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	Category D transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	Category E cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
safety	electrical safety	<p><u>PV-standards:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 50380 - Evaluation of conformity/Product standard ● prEN 50583 - Photovoltaic in buildings (not concentrator photovoltaic): Basic properties and specifications, electrical and mounting requirements 	<p><u>PV-standards:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prEN 50583 - Photovoltaic in buildings (not concentrator photovoltaic): Basic properties and specifications, electrical and mounting requirements ● EN 61173 - Overvoltage protection for systems generating 	<p><u>PV-standards:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 50380 - Evaluation of conformity/Product standard ● prEN 50583 - Photovoltaic in buildings (not concentrator photovoltaic): Basic properties and specifications, electrical and mounting requirements ● EN 61173 - 	<p><u>PV-standards:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 50380 - Evaluation of conformity/Product standard ● prEN 50583 - Photovoltaic in buildings (not concentrator photovoltaic): Basic properties and specifications, electrical and mounting requirements ● EN 61173 - 	<p><u>PV-standards:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 50380 - Evaluation of conformity/Product standard ● prEN 50583 - Photovoltaic in buildings (not concentrator photovoltaic): Basic properties and specifications, electrical and mounting requirements ● EN 61173 -

	<p>requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 61173 - Overvoltage protection for systems generating electricity out of PV ● EN 61215 - Crystalline silicium terrestrial photovoltaic modules: Design qualification and type approval, tests ● EN 61683 - PV- systems: Procedure for measuring efficiency EN 61727 - PV- systems: Characteristics of the utility interface ● EN 61730-1 A1 - PV- modules – safety qualification Part 1: Requirements for the installation ● EN 61730-2 A1 - PV- modules – safety 	<p>electricity out of PV</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 61215 - Crystalline silicium terrestrial photovoltaic modules: Design qualification and type approval, tests ● EN 61683 - PV- systems: Procedure for measuring efficiency EN 61727 - PV- systems: Characteristics of the utility interface ● EN 61730-1 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 1: Requirements for the installation ● EN 61730-2 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 2:Requirements for the testing (the tests of EN/IEC 61730 and EN/IEC 61215 take into account variable 	<p>Overvoltage protection for systems generating electricity out of PV</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 61215 - Crystalline silicium terrestrial photovoltaic modules: Design qualification and type approval, tests ● EN 61683 - PV- systems: Procedure for measuring efficiency EN 61727 - PV- systems: Characteristics of the utility interface ● EN 61730-1 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 1: Requirements for the installation ● EN 61730-2 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 2:Requirements for the testing (the tests of EN/IEC 61730 and EN/IEC 61215 take into account 	<p>Overvoltage protection for systems generating electricity out of PV</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 61215 - Crystalline silicium terrestrial photovoltaic modules: Design qualification and type approval, tests ● EN 61683 - PV- systems: Procedure for measuring efficiency EN 61727 - PV- systems: Characteristics of the utility interface ● EN 61730-1 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 1: Requirements for the installation ● EN 61730-2 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 2:Requirements for the testing (the tests of 	<p>Overvoltage protection for systems generating electricity out of PV</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 61215 - Crystalline silicium terrestrial photovoltaic modules: Design qualification and type approval, tests ● EN 61683 - PV- systems: Procedure for measuring efficiency EN 61727 - PV- systems: Characteristics of the utility interface ● EN 61730-1 A1 - PV- modules – safety qualification Part 1: Requirements for the installation ● EN 61730-2 A1 - PV- modules – safety qualification Part 2:Requirements
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	<p>qualification Part 2: Requirements for the testing (the tests of EN/IEC 61730 and EN/IEC 61215 take into account variable climatic conditions but national climatic load requirements might be higher than the IEC standard loads)</p>	<p>climatic conditions but national climatic load requirements might be higher than the IEC standard loads)</p>	<p>variable climatic conditions but national climatic load requirements might be higher than the IEC standard loads)</p>	<p>EN/IEC 61730 and EN/IEC 61215 take into account variable climatic conditions but national climatic load requirements might be higher than the IEC standard loads)</p>	<p>for the testing (the tests of EN/IEC 61730 and EN/IEC 61215 take into account variable climatic conditions but national climatic load requirements might be higher than the IEC standard loads)</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 62446 - PV-systems connected to the power network: Minimum requirements for the documentation of the system, commissioning test and returning tests ● EN 50530+A1 - Overall efficiency of grid connected photovoltaic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 62446 - PV-systems connected to the power network: Minimum requirements for the documentation of the system, commissioning test and returning tests ● EN 50530+A1 - Overall efficiency of grid connected photovoltaic inverters ● EN 62109-1 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 62446 - PV-systems connected to the power network: Minimum requirements for the documentation of the system, commissioning test and returning tests ● EN 50530+A1 - Overall efficiency of grid connected photovoltaic inverters ● EN 62109-1 - Safety of power converters for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 62446 - PV-systems connected to the power network: Minimum requirements for the documentation of the system, commissioning test and returning tests ● EN 50530+A1 - Overall efficiency of grid connected photovoltaic inverters ● EN 62109-1 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 62446 - PV-systems connected to the power network: Minimum requirements for the documentation of the system, commissioning test and returning tests ● EN 50530+A1 - Overall efficiency of grid connected photovoltaic inverters ● EN 62109-1 -

	<p>inverters</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 62109-1 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems, general requirements • EN 62109-2 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems, particular requirements for inverters • EN 62116 - Test procedure of islanding prevention measures for utility-interconnected photovoltaic inverters • EN 60364-7-712 - Low-voltage electrical installations- Part 7-712: Requirements for special installations or locations – photovoltaic power systems 	<p>Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems, general requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 62109-2 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems, particular requirements for inverters • EN 62116 - Test procedure of islanding prevention measures for utility-interconnected photovoltaic inverters • EN 60364-7-712 - Low-voltage electrical installations- Part 7-712: Requirements for special installations or locations – photovoltaic power systems 	<p>use in photovoltaic power systems, general requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 62109-2 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems, particular requirements for inverters • EN 62116 - Test procedure of islanding prevention measures for utility-interconnected photovoltaic inverters • EN 60364-7-712 - Low-voltage electrical installations- Part 7-712: Requirements for special installations or locations – photovoltaic power systems 	<p>Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems, general requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 62109-2 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems, particular requirements for inverters • EN 62116 - Test procedure of islanding prevention measures for utility-interconnected photovoltaic inverters • EN 60364-7-712 - Low-voltage electrical installations- Part 7-712: Requirements for special installations or locations – photovoltaic power systems 	<p>Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems, general requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 62109-2 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems, particular requirements for inverters • EN 62116 - Test procedure of islanding prevention measures for utility-interconnected photovoltaic inverters • EN 60364-7-712 - Low-voltage electrical installations- Part 7-712: Requirements for special installations or locations – photovoltaic power systems
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		locations – photovoltaic power systems				
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 60445 - Basic and safety principles for man-machine interface, marking and identification - Identification of equipment terminals and conductor ends and designated and general rules for an alphanumeric system ● EN 60529 - Degrees of protection provided by enclosures <p><u>For the assembly of PV-systems:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 60904-1 to EN 60904-9 - Photovoltaic devices ● EN 50521 - Connectors for photovoltaic systems - Safety requirements and testing ● EN 17025 - General requirements and testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 60445 - Basic and safety principles for man-machine interface, marking and identification - Identification of equipment terminals and conductor ends and designated and general rules for an alphanumeric system ● EN 60529 - Degrees of protection provided by enclosures <p><u>For the assembly of PV-systems:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 60904-1 to EN 60904-9 - Photovoltaic devices ● EN 50521 - Connectors for photovoltaic systems - Safety requirements and testing ● EN 17025 - General requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 60445 - Basic and safety principles for man-machine interface, marking and identification - Identification of equipment terminals and conductor ends and designated and general rules for an alphanumeric system ● EN 60529 - Degrees of protection provided by enclosures <p><u>For the assembly of PV-systems:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 60904-1 to EN 60904-9 - Photovoltaic devices ● EN 50521 - Connectors for photovoltaic systems - Safety requirements and testing ● EN 17025 - General requirements for the competence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 60445 - Basic and safety principles for man-machine interface, marking and identification - Identification of equipment terminals and conductor ends and designated and general rules for an alphanumeric system ● EN 60529 - Degrees of protection provided by enclosures <p><u>For the assembly of PV-systems:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 60904-1 to EN 60904-9 - Photovoltaic devices ● EN 50521 - Connectors for photovoltaic systems - Safety requirements and testing ● EN 17025 - General requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 60445 - Basic and safety principles for man-machine interface, marking and identification - Identification of equipment terminals and conductor ends and designated and general rules for an alphanumeric system ● EN 60529 - Degrees of protection provided by enclosures <p><u>For the assembly of PV-systems:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 60904-1 to EN 60904-9 - Photovoltaic devices ● EN 50521 - Connectors for photovoltaic systems - Safety requirements and testing ● EN 17025 - General requirements

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 17025 - General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories • EN 62093 - PV system components - modules excluded (BOS) - Design qualification under natural environmental conditions <p><u>For the connection with the grid:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 60555 - Disturbances in supply systems caused by household appliances and similar electrical equipment • EN 62053 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Part 21: Static meters for 	<p>for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 62093 - PV system components - modules excluded (BOS) - Design qualification under natural environmental conditions <p><u>For the connection with the grid:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 60555 - Disturbances in supply systems caused by household appliances and similar electrical equipment • EN 62053 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Part 21: Static meters for active energy (classes 1 and 2) • EN 50470-1 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) - 	<p>of testing and calibration laboratories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 62093 - PV system components - modules excluded (BOS) - Design qualification under natural environmental conditions <p><u>For the connection with the grid:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 60555 - Disturbances in supply systems caused by household appliances and similar electrical equipment • EN 62053 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Part 21: Static meters for active energy (classes 1 and 2) • EN 50470-1 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Part 1: General requirements, tests and test 	<p>for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 62093 - PV system components - modules excluded (BOS) - Design qualification under natural environmental conditions <p><u>For the connection with the grid:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 60555 - Disturbances in supply systems caused by household appliances and similar electrical equipment • EN 62053 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Part 21: Static meters for active energy (classes 1 and 2) • EN 50470-1 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) - 	<p>for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 62093 - PV system components - modules excluded (BOS) - Design qualification under natural environmental conditions <p><u>For the connection with the grid:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 60555 - Disturbances in supply systems caused by household appliances and similar electrical equipment • EN 62053 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Part 21: Static meters for active energy (classes 1 and 2) • EN 50470-1 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) -
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	<p>active energy (classes 1 and 2)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 50470-1 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Part 1: General requirements, tests and test conditions - Metering equipment (class indexes A, B and C) 	<p>Part 1: General requirements, tests and test conditions - Metering equipment (class indexes A, B and C)</p>	<p>conditions - Metering equipment (class indexes A, B and C)</p>	<p>Part 1: General requirements, tests and test conditions - Metering equipment (class indexes A, B and C)</p>	<p>- Part 1: General requirements, tests and test conditions - Metering equipment (class indexes A, B and C)</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 50470-3 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Part 3: Particular requirements - Static meters for active energy (class indexes A, B and C) ● EN 6099-1 - Arresters - Part 1: unloaders nonlinear resistors with spark gaps for ac systems ● EN 60439 - Gear assemblies and control equipment for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 50470-3 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Part 3: Particular requirements - Static meters for active energy (class indexes A, B and C) ● EN 6099-1 - Arresters - Part 1: unloaders nonlinear resistors with spark gaps for ac systems ● EN 60439 - Gear assemblies and control equipment for low voltage (LV switchboards), 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 50470-3 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Part 3: Particular requirements - Static meters for active energy (class indexes A, B and C) ● EN 6099-1 - Arresters - Part 1: unloaders nonlinear resistors with spark gaps for ac systems ● EN 60439 - Gear assemblies and control equipment for low voltage (LV switchboards), series ● EN50438 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 50470-3 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Part 3: Particular requirements - Static meters for active energy (class indexes A, B and C) ● EN 6099-1 - Arresters - Part 1: unloaders nonlinear resistors with spark gaps for ac systems ● EN 60439 - Gear assemblies and control equipment for low voltage (LV switchboards), 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 50470-3 - Electricity metering equipment (ac) - Part 3: Particular requirements - Static meters for active energy (class indexes A, B and C) ● EN 6099-1 - Arresters - Part 1: unloaders nonlinear resistors with spark gaps for ac systems ● EN 60439 - Gear assemblies and control equipment for low voltage (LV switchboards),

	<p>low voltage (LV switchboards), series</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN50438 - Requirements for the connection of micro-generators in parallel with the public supply systems in low voltage 	<p>series</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN50438 - Requirements for the connection of micro-generators in parallel with the public supply systems in low voltage 	<p>Requirements for the connection of micro-generators in parallel with the public supply systems in low voltage</p>	<p>series</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN50438 - Requirements for the connection of micro-generators in parallel with the public supply systems in low voltage 	<p>series</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN50438 - Requirements for the connection of micro-generators in parallel with the public supply systems in low voltage
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61724 - Photovoltaic system performance monitoring, guidelines for measurement, data exchange and analysis ● IEC 62109-1 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems- Part 1: General requirements ● IEC 62109-2 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61724 - Photovoltaic system performance monitoring, guidelines for measurement, data exchange and analysis ● IEC 62109-1 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems- Part 1: General requirements ● IEC 62109-2 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems- Part 2: Particular 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61724 - Photovoltaic system performance monitoring, guidelines for measurement, data exchange and analysis ● IEC 62109-1 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems- Part 1: General requirements ● IEC 62109-2 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems- Part 2: Particular requirements for inverters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61724 - Photovoltaic system performance monitoring, guidelines for measurement, data exchange and analysis ● IEC 62109-1 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems- Part 1: General requirements ● IEC 62109-2 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems- Part 2: Particular 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61724 - Photovoltaic system performance monitoring, guidelines for measurement, data exchange and analysis ● IEC 62109-1 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems- Part 1: General requirements ● IEC 62109-2 - Safety of power converters for use in photovoltaic power systems- Part 2: Particular

	systems- Part 2: Particular requirements for inverters	requirements for inverters		requirements for inverters	requirements for inverters
	<p><u>Additional electrical Standards:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-6-1 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-1: Generic standards – Immunity for residential, commercial and light-industrial environments ● IEC 61000-6-2 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-2: Generic standards – Immunity for industrial environments ● IEC 61000-6-3 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-3: General standards – 	<p><u>Additional electrical Standards:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-6-1 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-1: Generic standards – Immunity for residential, commercial and light-industrial environments ● IEC 61000-6-2 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-2: Generic standards – Immunity for industrial environments ● IEC 61000-6-3 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-3: General standards – Emission standard for residential, commercial and 	<p><u>Additional electrical Standards:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-6-1 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-1: Generic standards – Immunity for residential, commercial and light-industrial environments ● IEC 61000-6-2 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-2: Generic standards – Immunity for industrial environments ● IEC 61000-6-3 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-3: General standards – Emission standard for residential, commercial and light-industrial environments ● IEC 61000-6-4 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-4: Generic 	<p><u>Additional electrical Standards:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-6-1 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-1: Generic standards – Immunity for residential, commercial and light-industrial environments ● IEC 61000-6-2 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-2: Generic standards – Immunity for industrial environments ● IEC 61000-6-3 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-3: General standards – Emission standard for residential, commercial and 	<p><u>Additional electrical Standards:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-6-1 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-1: Generic standards – Immunity for residential, commercial and light-industrial environments ● IEC 61000-6-2 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-2: Generic standards – Immunity for industrial environments ● IEC 61000-6-3 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-3: General standards – Emission standard for residential, commercial and

	<p>Emission standard for residential, commercial and light-industrial environments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-6-4 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-4: Generic standards – Emission standard for industrial environments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-2 + A1 + A2 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-2: Limits – Limits for harmonic current emissions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-3 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-11: Limits – Limitation of voltage changes, voltage fluctuations</p>	<p>light- industrial environments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-6-4 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-4: Generic standards – Emission standard for industrial environments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-2 + A1 + A2 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-2: Limits – Limits for harmonic current emissions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-3 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-11: Limits – Limitation of voltage changes, voltage fluctuations and flicker in public low-voltage supply systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-12 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-12: Limits – Limits for</p>	<p>standards – Emission standard for industrial environments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-2 + A1 + A2 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-2: Limits – Limits for harmonic current emissions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-3 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-11: Limits – Limitation of voltage changes, voltage fluctuations and flicker in public low-voltage supply systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-12 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-12: Limits – Limits for harmonic currents produced by equipment connected to public low-voltage systems with input current</p>	<p>light- industrial environments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-6-4 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-4: Generic standards – Emission standard for industrial environments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-2 + A1 + A2 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-2: Limits – Limits for harmonic current emissions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-3 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-11: Limits – Limitation of voltage changes, voltage fluctuations and flicker in public low-voltage supply systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-12 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-12: Limits – Limits for</p>	<p>light- industrial environments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-6-4 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 6-4: Generic standards – Emission standard for industrial environments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-2 + A1 + A2 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-2: Limits – Limits for harmonic current emissions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-3 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-11: Limits – Limitation of voltage changes, voltage fluctuations and flicker in public low-voltage supply systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-12 - <p>Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-12: Limits – Limits for</p>
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		<p>and flicker in public low-voltage supply systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IEC 61000-3-12 - Electromagnetic compatibility – Part 3-12: Limits – Limits for harmonic currents produced by equipment connected to public low-voltage systems with input current 	<p>harmonic currents produced by equipment connected to public low-voltage systems with input current</p>		<p>harmonic currents produced by equipment connected to public low-voltage systems with input current</p>	<p>harmonic currents produced by equipment connected to public low-voltage systems with input current</p>
	Lightning protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 61643 - Low-voltage surge protective devices – Part 11: Surge protective devices connected to low-voltage power systems: Requirements and test methods ● EN 62305-1- Lightning protection - Part 1: General principles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 61643 - Low-voltage surge protective devices – Part 11: Surge protective devices connected to low-voltage power systems: Requirements and test methods ● EN 62305-1- Lightning protection - Part 1: General principles ● EN 62305-2- Lightning protection - Part 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 61643 - Low-voltage surge protective devices – Part 11: Surge protective devices connected to low-voltage power systems: Requirements and test methods ● EN 62305-1- Lightning protection - Part 1: General principles ● EN 62305-2- Lightning protection - Part 2: Risk-management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 61643 - Low-voltage surge protective devices – Part 11: Surge protective devices connected to low-voltage power systems: Requirements and test methods ● EN 62305-1- Lightning protection - Part 1: General principles ● EN 62305-2- Lightning protection - Part 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 61643 - Low-voltage surge protective devices – Part 11: Surge protective devices connected to low-voltage power systems: Requirements and test methods ● EN 62305-1- Lightning protection - Part 1: General principles ● EN 62305-2- Lightning protection - Part

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 62305-2- Lightning protection - Part 2: Risk-management ● EN 62305-3 - Lightning protection - Part 3: Physical damage to structures and life hazard ● EN 62305-4- Lightning protection - Part 4: Electrical and electronic systems within structures 	<p>2: Risk-management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 62305-3 - Lightning protection - Part 3: Physical damage to structures and life hazard ● EN 62305-4- Lightning protection - Part 4: Electrical and electronic systems within structures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 62305-3 - Lightning protection - Part 3: Physical damage to structures and life hazard ● EN 62305-4- Lightning protection - Part 4: Electrical and electronic systems within structures 	<p>2: Risk-management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 62305-3 - Lightning protection - Part 3: Physical damage to structures and life hazard ● EN 62305-4- Lightning protection - Part 4: Electrical and electronic systems within structures 	<p>2: Risk-management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 62305-3 - Lightning protection - Part 3: Physical damage to structures and life hazard ● EN 62305-4- Lightning protection - Part 4: Electrical and electronic systems within structures
safety in case of fire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1991 -1-2 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-2: Stress and strain under fire ● EN 13501-1 - Fire classification of construction products and building 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1991 -1-2 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-2: Stress and strain under fire ● EN 13501-1 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 1: Classification using data from 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1991 -1-2 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-2: Stress and strain under fire ● prEN 1364-1 - Fire resistance tests for non-loadbearing elements - Part 1: Test procedures, walls ● EN 1365-1 - Fire resistance tests for loadbearing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1991 -1-2 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-2: Stress and strain under fire ● EN 13501-1 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 1: Classification using data from 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1991 -1-2 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-2: Stress and strain under fire ● EN 13501-1 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 1: Classification using data from

	<p>elements - Part 1: Classification using data from reaction to fire tests</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13501-2 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 2: Classification using data from fire resistance tests, excluding ventilation services ● EN 13501-3 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 3: Classification using data from fire resistance tests on products and elements used in building service 	<p>reaction to fire tests</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13501-2 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 2: Classification using data from fire resistance tests, excluding ventilation services ● EN 13501-3 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 3: Classification using data from fire resistance tests on products and elements used in building service installations: fire resisting ducts and fire dampers ● EN 13501-5 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 	<p>elements - Part 1: Walls</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13501-1 - 1 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 1: Classification using data from reaction to fire tests ● EN 13501-2 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 2: Classification using data from fire resistance tests, excluding ventilation services ● EN 13501-3 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 3: Classification using data from fire resistance tests on products and elements used in building service installations: fire resisting ducts and fire dampers ● EN 1363-1 - Fire 	<p>reaction to fire tests</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13501-2- Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 2: Classification using data from fire resistance tests, excluding ventilation services ● EN 13501-3 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 3: Classification using data from fire resistance tests on products and elements used in building service installations: fire resisting ducts and fire dampers ● EN 14351-1 - Manufacturer to declare the fire rating. Further requirements depend on application and 	<p>reaction to fire tests</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13501-2 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 2: Classification using data from fire resistance tests, excluding ventilation services ● EN 13501-3 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 3: Classification using data from fire resistance tests on products and elements used in building service installations: fire resisting ducts and fire dampers ● EN 14351-1 - Manufacturer to declare the fire rating. Further requirements depend on
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	<p>installations: fire resisting ducts and fire dampers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13501-5 - Fire classification of construction products and building elements - Part 5: Classification using data from external fire exposure to roofs tests National requirements may demand Broof (t1),(t2),(t3)or(t4) ● EN 1363-1 - Fire resistance tests for determination of fire resistance of several elements of construction- General requirements ● EN 1363-2 - Fire resistance tests - Part 2: Alternative and additional procedures 	<p>5: Classification using data from external fire exposure to roofs tests</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1363-1 - Fire resistance tests for determination of fire resistance of several elements of construction- General requirements ● EN 1363-2 - Fire resistance tests - Part 2: Alternative and additional procedures ● EN 1364-2 - Fire resistance tests for non-loadbearing elements - Part 2: Ceilings ● prEN 1365-2 - Fire resistance tests for loadbearing elements - Part 2: Floors and roofs 	<p>resistance tests for determination of fire resistance of several elements of construction - General requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1363-2 - Fire resistance tests - Part 2: Alternative and additional procedures 	<p>country.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prEN 1364-1 - Fire resistance tests for non-loadbearing elements - Part 1: Test procedures, walls ● EN 1365-1- Fire resistance tests for loadbearing elements - Part 1: Walls ● EN 1363-1 - Fire resistance tests for determination of fire resistance of several elements of construction - General requirements ● EN 1363-2 - Fire resistance tests - Part 2: Alternative and additional procedures 	<p>application and country</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prEN 1364-3 - Fire resistance tests for non-loadbearing elements - Part 3: Curtain walling - Full configuration (complete assembly) ● prEN 1364-4 - Fire resistance tests for non-loadbearing elements - Part 4: Curtain walling - part configuration ● EN 1365-1- Fire resistance tests for loadbearing elements - Part 1: Walls
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1364-2 - Fire resistance tests for non-loadbearing elements - Part 2: Ceilings 				
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prEN 1365-2 - Fire resistance tests for loadbearing elements - Part 2: Floors and roofs ● EN 357 - Fire resistant glazed elements with transparent or translucent glass products: Classification of fire resistance ● EN 15998 - Glass in building – Safety in case of fire, fire resistance: Glass testing methodology for the purpose of classification ● EN ISO 13943 - Fire resistance: Vocabulary, terminology ● DIN CEN/TS 1187 - Testing methods for external fire exposure to roofs ● EN 1182 - Reaction to fire tests for products - Non-combustibility test ● EN 13823 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 357 - Fire resistant glazed elements with transparent or translucent glass products: Classification of fire resistance ● EN 15998 - Glass in building – Safety in case of fire, fire resistance: Glass testing methodology for the purpose of classification ● EN ISO 13943 - Fire resistance: Vocabulary, terminology ● EN 1182 - Reaction to fire tests for products - Non-combustibility test ● EN 13823 - Reaction to fire tests for building products - Building products excluding floorings exposed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 357 - Fire resistant glazed elements with transparent or translucent glass products: Classification of fire resistance ● EN 15998 - Glass in building – Safety in case of fire, fire resistance: Glass testing methodology for the purpose of classification ● EN ISO 13943 - Fire resistance: Vocabulary, terminology ● EN 1182 - Reaction to fire tests for products - Non-combustibility test ● EN 13823 - Reaction to fire tests for building products - Building products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 357 - Fire resistant glazed elements with transparent or translucent glass products: Classification of fire resistance ● EN 15998 - Glass in building – Safety in case of fire, fire resistance: Glass testing methodology for the purpose of classification ● EN ISO 13943 - Fire resistance: Vocabulary, terminology ● EN 1182 - Reaction to fire tests for products - Non-combustibility test ● EN 13823 - Reaction to fire tests for building products - Building products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1363-1 - Fire resistance tests for determination of fire resistance of several elements of construction - General requirements ● EN 1363-2 - Fire resistance tests - Part 2: Alternative and additional procedures ● EN 357 - Fire resistant glazed elements with transparent or translucent glass products: Classification of fire resistance ● EN 15998 - Glass in building – Safety in case of fire, fire resistance: Glass testing methodology for the purpose of classification

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN CEN/TS 1187 - Testing methods for external fire exposure to roofs ● EN 1182 - Reaction to fire tests for products - Non-combustibility test ● EN 13823 - Reaction to fire tests for building products - Building products excluding floorings exposed to the thermal attack by a single burning item 	Reaction to fire tests for building products - Building products excluding floorings exposed to the thermal attack by a single burning item	to the thermal attack by a single burning item	excluding floorings exposed to the thermal attack by a single burning item	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 13943 - Fire resistance: Vocabulary, terminology ● EN 1182 - Reaction to fire tests for products - Non-combustibility test ● EN 13823 - Reaction to fire tests for building products - Building products excluding floorings exposed to the thermal attack by a single burning item
					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prEN 1364-3, 006-12 Fire resistance proof of non-supporting components – Part 3: curtain wall; German version EN 1364-3:2006 ● prEN 1364-4, 2007-06 Fire resistance proof of non-supporting

						components – Part 3: curtain wall; German version EN 1364-4:2007
	safety in use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13022 only applicable for BIPV modules or insulating glass units to be bonded adhesively which are sold separately from the framework and installed under the responsibility of the designer and assembler. National regulations may define restrictions or additional requirements ● ETAG 002 applicable for structural sealant glazing systems put on the market as a 'kit' of components; specified by European Technical Approval or 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13022 only applicable for BIPV modules or insulating glass units to be bonded adhesively which are sold separately from the framework and installed under the responsibility of the designer and assembler. National regulations may define restrictions or additional requirements ● ETAG 002 applicable for structural sealant glazing systems put on the market as a 'kit' of components; specified by European Technical Approval or National Approval. ● prEN ISO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13022 ● ETAG 002 in case of structural sealant glazing systems <p>Structural sealant glazing systems or kits comprising PV modules are in the first consideration a matter of Technical Approvals which set out the requirements for the complete product to be fulfilled by the manufacturer. In the second consideration, PV modules as glass products to be sold separately and installed into or onto a framework or into or onto the building using a structural glazing technique are specified in EN 13022. Meeting the requirements of this standard,</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13022 ● ETAG 002 in case of structural sealant glazing systems <p>Structural sealant glazing systems or kits comprising PV modules are in the first consideration a matter of Technical Approvals which set out the requirements for the complete product to be fulfilled by the manufacturer. In the second consideration, PV modules as glass products to be sold separately and installed into or onto a framework or into or onto the building using a structural glazing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13022 ● ETAG 002 in case of structural sealant glazing systems <p>Structural sealant glazing systems or kits comprising PV modules are in the first consideration a matter of Technical Approvals which set out the requirements for the complete product to be fulfilled by the manufacturer. In the second consideration, PV modules as glass products to be sold separately and installed into or onto a framework or into or onto the building using a structural glazing</p>

	<p>National Approval.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN ISO 14439 <p>Applicable if contact of glass and frame can not be excluded.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 12600 <p>For laminated safety glass only and if national regulations require the classification of pendulum body impact resistance: required for CE marking of laminated safety glass</p>	<p>14439</p> <p>Applicable if contact of glass and frame can not be excluded.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 12600 <p>For laminated safety glass only and if national regulations require the classification of pendulum body impact resistance: required for CE marking of laminated safety glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 14351-1 <p>Apply conditions as defined in C.1</p>	<p>they are suitable for use in SSGS as defined in ETAG 002.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • when classification as laminated SAFETY glass is required: EN12600 and EN12543 apply. <p>For laminated safety glass only and if national regulations require the classification of pendulum body impact resistance: required for CE marking of laminated safety glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN ISO 14439 	<p>technique are specified in EN 13022. Meeting the requirements of this standard, they are suitable for use in SSGS as defined in ETAG 002.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • when classification as laminated SAFETY glass is required: EN12600 and EN12543 apply. <p>For laminated safety glass only and if national regulations require the classification of pendulum body impact resistance: required for CE marking of laminated safety glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN ISO 14439 	<p>technique are specified in EN 13022. Meeting the requirements of this standard, they are suitable for use in SSGS as defined in ETAG 002.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • when classification as laminated SAFETY glass is required: EN12600 <p>For laminated safety glass only and if national regulations require the classification of pendulum body impact resistance: required for CE marking of laminated safety glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN ISO 14439 • EN 12519 - Curtain wall: Terminology: doors, windows, assemblies
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1991-1-1 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1991-1-1 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1991-1-1 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1991-1-1 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1991-1-1 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and

		<p>concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-1: Dead load and actual load</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1991-1-6 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-6:Stresses and strains during construction 	<p>rules of measurement - Part 1-1: Dead load and actual load</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1991-1-6 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-6:Stresses and strains during construction 	<p>of measurement - Part 1-1: Dead load and actual load</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1991-1-6 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-6:Stresses and strains during construction ● ETAG 004 - External Thermal Insulation Composite System with rendering for the use as external insulation of building walls ● ETAG 014 - Plastic Anchors for fixing of external thermal insulation composite systems with rendering 	<p>rules of measurement - Part 1-1: Dead load and actual load</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1991-1-6 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-6:Stresses and strains during construction 	<p>rules of measurement - Part 1-1: Dead load and actual load</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1991-1-6 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-6:Stresses and strains during construction
						<p><u>Constructive requirements for ventilated façades:</u> <u>Stability of the cladding of a ventilated façade:</u></p>

						<p>Impact loads and dynamic stress on cladding of a ventilated façade:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14019:2004 Protection against shock can be fixed up to a height of 2,8 m. <p>DIN EN 14019, 2004-09</p> <p>Curtain walls – impact strength – performance requirements; German version EN 14019:2004</p>
slate, shingles and roofing tiles	<p><u>Slate as building material</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FprEN 12326-1 - Slate and stone for discontinuous roofing and external cladding – Part 1: Specifications for slate and carbonate slate ● EN 12326-2 - Slate and stone for 	<p><u>Slate as building material</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FprEN 12326-1 - Slate and stone for discontinuous roofing and external cladding – Part 1: Specifications for slate and carbonate slate ● EN 12326-2 - Slate and stone for discontinuous roofing and external 	<p><u>Slate as building material</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FprEN 12326-1 - Slate and stone for discontinuous roofing and external cladding – Part 1: Specifications for slate and carbonate slate ● EN 12326-2 - Slate and stone for discontinuous roofing and external cladding – Part 2: Methods of test for slate 	<p><u>Slate as building material</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FprEN 12326-1 - Slate and stone for discontinuous roofing and external cladding – Part 1: Specifications for slate and carbonate slate ● EN 12326-2 - Slate and stone for discontinuous roofing and external 	<p><u>Slate as building material</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FprEN 12326-1 - Slate and stone for discontinuous roofing and external cladding – Part 1: Specifications for slate and carbonate slate ● EN 12326-2 - Slate and stone for discontinuous roofing and external 	

	<p>discontinuous roofing and external cladding – Part 2: Methods of test for slate and carbonate slate</p> <p><u>Bitumen shingles</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 544 - Bitumen shingles with mineral and/or synthetic reinforcement s: Product specification and test methods 	<p>cladding – Part 2: Methods of test for slate and carbonate slate</p> <p><u>Bitumen shingles</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 544 - Bitumen shingles with mineral and/or synthetic reinforcements: Product specification and test methods 	<p>and carbonate slate</p> <p><u>Bitumen shingles</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 544 - Bitumen shingles with mineral and/or synthetic reinforcements: Product specification and test methods 	<p>cladding – Part 2: Methods of test for slate and carbonate slate</p> <p><u>Bitumen shingles</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 544 - Bitumen shingles with mineral and/or synthetic reinforcements: Product specification and test methods 	<p>cladding – Part 2: Methods of test for slate and carbonate slate</p>
	<p>Roofing tiles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1024 - Roofing tiles: Determination of geometric characteristics ● EN 1304 - Roofing tiles: Product definitions and specifications 	<p>Roofing tiles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1024 - Roofing tiles: Determination of geometric characteristics ● EN 1304 - Roofing tiles: Product definitions and specifications 			
water tightness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN V 20000-201 - Waterproofness: Adaption standard for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 539-1 - Roofing tiles - Determination of physical characteristics - Part 1: 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN EN 12154, 2000-06 - Curtain wall – air permeability – performance requirements

	<p>flexible sheets for waterproofing according to European standards for the use as waterproofing of roofs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 539-1 - Roofing tiles - Determination of physical characteristics - Part 1: Impermeability test 	<p>Impermeability test</p>			<p>and categorization; German version EN 12154:1999</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN EN 12155, 2000-10 - Curtain wall – leak-proof in case of driving rain – laboratory test under static pressure; <p>German version EN 12155:2000</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN EN 13050, 2011-09 - Curtain wall – leak-proof in case of driving rain – laboratory test with changing barometric pressure and sprinkling with water; <p>German version prEN 13050:2006</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN EN 13051, 2001-11 - Curtain wall – leak-proof in case of driving rain – test in place; <p>German version EN 13051:2001</p>
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						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN EN 12152, 2002-08 Curtain wall – air permeability – performance requirements and categorization; German version EN 12152:2002 • DIN EN 12153, 2000-09 Curtain wall – air permeability – test procedure; German version EN 12153:2000
	wind resistance and airtightness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1990/1991 1-4 Joints of the cladding max. 20 mm Arrangement of a windstop Separation into pressure zones Obstruction of strong airstreams on the edges of the building and in areas with variable wind-pressures Requirements: • Every pressure zone contains 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1990/1991 1-4 Joints of the cladding max. 20 mm Arrangement of a windstop Separation into pressure zones Obstruction of strong airstreams on the edges of the building and in areas with variable wind-pressures Requirements: • Every pressure zone contains adequate sized ventiducts (according to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1990/1991 1-4 Joints of the cladding max. 20 mm Arrangement of a windstop Separation into pressure zones Obstruction of strong airstreams on the edges of the building and in areas with variable wind-pressures Requirements: • Every pressure zone contains adequate sized ventiducts (according to the volume) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1990/1991 1-4 Joints of the cladding max. 20 mm Arrangement of a windstop Separation into pressure zones Obstruction of strong airstreams on the edges of the building and in areas with variable wind-pressures Requirements: • Every pressure zone contains adequate sized ventiducts (according to 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1991-1-4 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-4: Wind loads • EN 1990/1991 1-4 Joints of the cladding max. 20 mm Arrangement of a windstop Separation into pressure zones Obstruction of strong airstreams on the edges of the building and in

	<p>adequate sized ventiducts (according to the volume)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Division of the pressure zone: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Horizontal on floor-level Vertical maximal every 6 meter Vertical every 1.5 meter in the edges Vertical 300 mm from the edges of the building • Partially pressure stops are reasonable to moderate the pressure balance • EN 14437 - Determination of the uplift resistance of installed clay or concrete tiles for roofing - Roof system test method 	<p>the volume)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Division of the pressure zone: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Horizontal on floor-level Vertical maximal every 6 meter Vertical every 1.5 meter in the edges Vertical 300 mm from the edges of the building • Partially pressure stops are reasonable to moderate the pressure balance • EN 14437 - Determination of the uplift resistance of installed clay or concrete tiles for roofing - Roof system test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Division of the pressure zone: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Horizontal on floor-level Vertical maximal every 6 meter Vertical every 1.5 meter in the edges Vertical 300 mm from the edges of the building • Partially pressure stops are reasonable to moderate the pressure balance 	<p>the volume)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Division of the pressure zone: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Horizontal on floor-level Vertical maximal every 6 meter Vertical every 1.5 meter in the edges Vertical 300 mm from the edges of the building • Partially pressure stops are reasonable to moderate the pressure balance 	<p>areas with variable wind-pressures</p> <p>Requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Every pressure zone contains adequate sized ventiducts (according to the volume) • Division of the pressure zone: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Horizontal on floor-level Vertical maximal every 6 meter Vertical every 1.5 meter in the edges Vertical 300 mm from the edges of the building • Partially pressure stops are reasonable to moderate the pressure balance • prEN 12211:2013 - Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method; German version
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 12211:2013 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 12211:2013 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 12211:2013 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 12211:2013 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN EN 12179, 2000-09 -

		Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method; German version	Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method; German version	Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method; German version	Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method; German version	Curtain wall – resistance to wind load – testing procedure; German version EN 12179:2000 • DIN EN 13116, 2001-11 - Curtain wall – resistance to wind load – performance requirements; German version EN 13116:2001 • DIN EN 12152 - Curtain wall - Air permeability: Performance and classification • DIN EN 12513 - Curtain wall - Air permeability: Test methods
	resistance against snow and ice loads	• EN 1991-1-3 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-3: Snow loads - Snow shape coefficient categorization	• EN 1991-1-3 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-3: Snow loads - Snow shape coefficient categorization into i) flat and	• EN 1991-1-3 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-3: Snow loads	• EN 1991-1-3 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-3: Snow loads	• EN 1991-1-3 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-3: Snow loads: 0,1 kN/m ²

		into i) flat and mono-pitch roofs, ii) duo-pitch roofs ● EN 539-2 - Roofing tiles - Determination of physical characteristics - Part 2: Test for frost resistance	mono-pitch roofs, ii) duo-pitch roofs ● EN 539-2 - Roofing tiles - Determination of physical characteristics- Part 2: Test for frost resistance			
	handling of deformation caused by temperature	● EN 1991-1-5 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-5: Stresses and strains of temperature changes	● EN 1991-1-5 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-5: Stresses and strains of temperature changes	● EN 1991-1-5 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-5: Stresses and strains of temperature changes	● EN 1991-1-5 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-5: Stresses and strains of temperature changes	● EN 1991-1-5 - Arithmetical proof of structural safety - concept and rules of measurement - Part 1-5: Stresses and strains of temperature changes <u>Deformation of a ventilated façade:</u>
	Cladding	As a rule of thumb in order enough ventilation for the PV module to be provided, the cladding/substructure must provide a gap of around 200 mm between the modules	As a rule of thumb in order enough ventilation for the PV module to be provided, the cladding/substructure must provide a gap of around 200 mm between the	● DIN EN 13162:2013-03 - Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made mineral wool (MW) products ● DIN EN 13163:2013-03 - Thermal	● DIN EN 13162:2013-03 - Thermal insulation products for buildings - Factory made mineral wool (MW) products ● DIN EN 13163:2013-03 - Thermal	<u>Structural - physical requirements of the ventilation gaps of ventilated façades:</u> Ventilation is necessary to reduce humidity, deposition, conduction of

		and the roof (???)	modules and the roof (???)	insulation products for buildings - Factory made expanded polystyrene (EPS) products ● DIN EN 15824:2009-10 - Specifications for external renders and internal plasters based on organic binders	insulation products for buildings - Factory made expanded polystyrene (EPS) products ● DIN EN 15824:2009-10 - Specifications for external renders and internal plasters based on organic binders	condensation water and for other aspects. Distance: at least 20 mm from the exterior wall Distance can maximal be reduced to 5 mm (roughness of the wall) Free cross section of the ventilation: at least 200 cm ² /m Breather hole: at least 50 cm ² /1 m length of wall
G l a s s	Terminology, physical properties, ...	● EN 12898 - Determination of the emissivity of glass ● EN 61345 UV test on photovoltaic (PV) modules - Defines a test which determines the resistance of the module when exposed to ultra-violet (UV) radiation	● EN 12898 - Determination of the emissivity of glass ● EN 61345 UV test on photovoltaic (PV) modules - Defines a test which determines the resistance of the module when exposed to ultra-violet (UV) radiation	● EN 12898 - Determination of the emissivity of glass ● EN 61345 UV test on photovoltaic (PV) modules - Defines a test which determines the resistance of the module when exposed to ultra-violet (UV) radiation	● EN 12898 - Determination of the emissivity of glass ● EN 61345 UV test on photovoltaic (PV) modules - Defines a test which determines the resistance of the module when exposed to ultra-violet (UV) radiation	● EN 12898 - Determination of the emissivity of glass ● EN 61345 UV test on photovoltaic (PV) modules - Defines a test which determines the resistance of the module when exposed to ultra-violet (UV) radiation
		basic products of <u>Basic soda-lime-silicate glass products:</u>	<u>Basic soda-lime-silicate glass products:</u>	<u>Basic soda-lime-silicate glass products:</u>	<u>Basic soda-lime-silicate glass products:</u>	<u>Basic soda-lime-silicate glass products:</u>

	<p>lime silicate glass – Part 6: Wired patterned glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 572-7 - Basic products out of soda-lime silicate glass – Part 7: Wired or unwired channel shaped glass ● EN 572-8 - Basic products out of soda-lime silicate glass – Part 8: Supplied and final cut sizes ● EN 572-9 - Basic products out of soda-lime silicate glass – Part 9: Evaluation of conformity/ product code of basic soda lime silicate glass, float glass, polished wired glass, drawn sheet glass, patterned glass, wired patterned glass and wired or 	<p>Basic products out of soda-lime silicate glass – Part 7: Wired or unwired channel shaped glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 572-8 - Basic products out of soda-lime silicate glass – Part 8: Supplied and final cut sizes ● EN 572-9 - Basic products out of soda-lime silicate glass – Part 9: Evaluation of conformity/ product code of basic soda lime silicate glass, float glass, polished wired glass, drawn sheet glass, patterned glass, wired patterned glass and wired or unwired channel shaped glass 	<p>channel shaped glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 572-8 - Basic products out of soda-lime silicate glass – Part 8: Supplied and final cut sizes ● EN 572-9 - Basic products out of soda-lime silicate glass – Part 9: Evaluation of conformity/ product code of basic soda lime silicate glass, float glass, polished wired glass, drawn sheet glass, patterned glass, wired patterned glass and wired or unwired channel shaped glass 	<p>Basic products out of soda-lime silicate glass – Part 7: Wired or unwired channel shaped glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 572-8 - Basic products out of soda-lime silicate glass – Part 8: Supplied and final cut sizes ● EN 572-9 - Basic products out of soda-lime silicate glass – Part 9: Evaluation of conformity/ product code of basic soda lime silicate glass, float glass, polished wired glass, drawn sheet glass, patterned glass, wired patterned glass and wired or unwired channel shaped glass 	<p>Basic products out of soda-lime silicate glass – Part 7: Wired or unwired channel shaped glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 572-8 - Basic products out of soda-lime silicate glass – Part 8: Supplied and final cut sizes ● EN 572-9 - Basic products out of soda-lime silicate glass – Part 9: Evaluation of conformity/ product code of basic soda lime silicate glass, float glass, polished wired glass, drawn sheet glass, patterned glass, wired patterned glass and wired or unwired channel shaped glass
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		unwired channel shaped glass				
		<u>Basic borosilicate glass products:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1748-1-1 - Special basic products - Borosilicate glasses - Part 1-1: Definitions and general physical and mechanical properties ● EN 1748-1-2 - Special basic products - Borosilicate glasses - Part 1-2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard <u>Basic alkaline-earth-silicate glass products:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14178-1 - Basic alkaline earth silicate glass products - Part 1: Float glass ● EN 14178-2 - Basic alkaline earth silicate 	<u>Basic borosilicate glass products:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1748-1-1 - Special basic products - Borosilicate glasses - Part 1-1: Definitions and general physical and mechanical properties ● EN 1748-1-2 - Special basic products - Borosilicate glasses - Part 1-2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard <u>Basic alkaline-earth-silicate glass products:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14178-1 - Basic alkaline earth silicate glass products - Part 1: Float glass ● EN 14178-2 - Basic alkaline earth silicate glass products - 	<u>Basic borosilicate glass products:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1748-1-1 - Special basic products - Borosilicate glasses - Part 1-1: Definitions and general physical and mechanical properties ● EN 1748-1-2 - Special basic products - Borosilicate glasses - Part 1-2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard <u>Basic alkaline-earth-silicate glass products:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14178-1 - Basic alkaline earth silicate glass products - Part 1: Float glass ● EN 14178-2 - Basic alkaline earth silicate Product standard 	<u>Basic borosilicate glass products:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1748-1-1 - Special basic products - Borosilicate glasses - Part 1-1: Definitions and general physical and mechanical properties ● EN 1748-1-2 - Special basic products - Borosilicate glasses - Part 1-2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard <u>Basic alkaline-earth-silicate glass products:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14178-1 - Basic alkaline earth silicate glass products - Part 1: Float glass ● EN 14178-2 - Basic alkaline earth silicate glass products - 	<u>Basic borosilicate glass products:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1748-1-1 - Special basic products - Borosilicate glasses - Part 1-1: Definitions and general physical and mechanical properties ● EN 1748-1-2 - Special basic products - Borosilicate glasses - Part 1-2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard <u>Basic alkaline-earth-silicate glass products:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14178-1 - Basic alkaline earth silicate glass products - Part 1: Float glass ● EN 14178-2 - Basic alkaline earth silicate glass products -

	<p>glass products - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard</p> <p><u>Basic alumino silicate glass products:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●prEN 15681-1 - Basic alumino silicate glass products - Part 1: Definitions and general physical and mechanical properties ●prEN 15681-2 - Basic alumino silicate glass products - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/Product standard 	<p>Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard</p> <p><u>Basic alumino silicate glass products:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●prEN 15681-1 - Basic alumino silicate glass products - Part 1: Definitions and general physical and mechanical properties ●prEN 15681-2 - Basic alumino silicate glass products - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/Product standard 	<p><u>Basic alumino silicate glass products:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●prEN 15681-1 - Basic alumino silicate glass products - Part 1: Definitions and general physical and mechanical properties ●prEN 15681-2 - Basic alumino silicate glass products - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/Product standard 	<p>Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard</p> <p><u>Basic alumino silicate glass products:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●prEN 15681-1 - Basic alumino silicate glass products - Part 1: Definitions and general physical and mechanical properties ●prEN 15681-2 - Basic alumino silicate glass products - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/Product standard 	<p>Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard</p> <p><u>Basic alumino silicate glass products:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●prEN 15681-1 - Basic alumino silicate glass products - Part 1: Definitions and general physical and mechanical properties ●prEN 15681-2 - Basic alumino silicate glass products - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/Product standard
types of glazing	<p><u>laminated glass, laminated safety glass:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14449 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass: 	<p><u>laminated glass, laminated safety glass:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14449 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass: Evaluation of conformity/ 	<p><u>laminated glass, laminated safety glass:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14449 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass: Evaluation of conformity/ 	<p><u>laminated glass, laminated safety glass:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14449 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass: Evaluation of conformity/ 	<p><u>laminated glass, laminated safety glass:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14449 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass: Evaluation of conformity/

	<p>Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 12543-1 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 1: Definitions and description of component parts ● EN ISO 12543-2 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 2: Laminated safety glass ● EN ISO 12543-3 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 3: Laminated glass ● EN ISO 12543-4 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - 	<p>Product standard</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 12543-1 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 1: Definitions and description of component parts ● EN ISO 12543-2 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 2: Laminated safety glass ● EN ISO 12543-3 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 3: Laminated glass ● EN ISO 12543-4 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 4: Laminated glass ● EN ISO 12543-5 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 5: Methods 	<p>Product standard</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 12543-1 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 1: Definitions and description of component parts ● EN ISO 12543-2 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 2: Laminated safety glass ● EN ISO 12543-3 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 3: Laminated glass ● EN ISO 12543-4 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 4: Laminated glass ● EN ISO 12543-5 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 5: Methods to test the durability ● EN ISO 12543-6 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 6: Dimensions and tolerances 	<p>Product standard</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 12543-1 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 1: Definitions and description of component parts ● EN ISO 12543-2 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 2: Laminated safety glass ● EN ISO 12543-3 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 3: Laminated glass ● EN ISO 12543-4 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 4: Laminated glass ● EN ISO 12543-5 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 5: Methods 	<p>Product standard</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 12543-1 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 1: Definitions and description of component parts ● EN ISO 12543-2 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 2: Laminated safety glass ● EN ISO 12543-3 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 3: Laminated glass ● EN ISO 12543-4 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 4: Laminated glass ● EN ISO 12543-5 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Part 5: Methods
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	<p>Part 4: Laminated glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 12543-5 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - <p>Part 5: Methods to test the durability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 12543-6 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - <p>Part 6: Dimensions and tolerances</p>	<p>to test the durability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 12543-6 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - <p>Part 6: Dimensions and tolerances</p>		<p>to test the durability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 12543-6 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - <p>Part 6: Dimensions and tolerances</p>	<p>to test the durability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 12543-6 - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - <p>Part 6: Dimensions and tolerances</p>
	<p><u>coated glass:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096 - 1 - Coated glass - <p>Part 1: Definition and classification</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096-2 - Coated glass - <p>Part 2: Requirements and test methods for the durability under abrasion for class A and B coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096-3 - 	<p><u>coated glass:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096 - 1 - Coated glass - <p>Part 1: Definition and classification</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096-2 - Coated glass - <p>Part 2: Requirements and test methods for the durability under abrasion for class A and B coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096-3 - Coated glass - 	<p><u>coated glass:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096 - 1 - Coated glass - <p>Part 1: Definition and classification</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096-2 - Coated glass - <p>Part 2: Requirements and test methods for the durability under abrasion for class A and B coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096-3 - Coated glass - <p>Part 3: Requirements</p>	<p><u>coated glass:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096 - 1 - Coated glass - <p>Part 1: Definition and classification</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096-2 - Coated glass - <p>Part 2: Requirements and test methods for the durability under abrasion for class A and B coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096-3 - Coated glass - 	<p><u>coated glass:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096 - 1 - Coated glass - <p>Part 1: Definition and classification</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096-2 - Coated glass - <p>Part 2: Requirements and test methods for the durability under abrasion for class A and B coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1096-3 - Coated glass -

	<p>Coated glass - Part 3: Requirements and test methods for the durability under radiation for class C and D coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prEN 1096-4 - Coated glass - Part 4: Evaluation of conformity/ product code ● prEN 1096-5 - Coated glass - Part 5: Test method and classification for the self-cleaning performances of coated glass surfaces 	<p>Part 3: Requirements and test methods for the durability under radiation for class C and D coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prEN 1096-4 - Coated glass - Part 4: Evaluation of conformity/ product code ● prEN 1096-5 - Coated glass - Part 5: Test method and classification for the self-cleaning performances of coated glass surfaces 	<p>and test methods for the durability under radiation for class C and D coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prEN 1096-4 - Coated glass - Part 4: Evaluation of conformity/ product code ● prEN 1096-5 - Coated glass - Part 5: Test method and classification for the self-cleaning performances of coated glass surfaces 	<p>Part 3: Requirements and test methods for the durability under radiation for class C and D coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prEN 1096-4 - Coated glass - Part 4: Evaluation of conformity/ product code ● prEN 1096-5 - Coated glass - Part 5: Test method and classification for the self-cleaning performances of coated glass surfaces 	<p>Part 3: Requirements and test methods for the durability under radiation for class C and D coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prEN 1096-4 - Coated glass - Part 4: Evaluation of conformity/ product code ● prEN 1096-5 - Coated glass - Part 5: Test method and classification for the self-cleaning performances of coated glass surfaces
	<p><u>Insulating glass units:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-1 - Insulating lass units - Part 1: Generalities, dimensional tolerances and rules for the description of the system ● EN 1279-2 - Insulating lass units - Part 2: 	<p><u>Insulating glass units:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-1 - Insulating lass units - Part 1: Generalities, dimensional tolerances and rules for the description of the system ● EN 1279-2 - Insulating lass units - Part 2: 	<p><u>Insulating glass units:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-1 - Insulating lass units - Part 1: Generalities, dimensional tolerances and rules for the description of the system ● EN 1279-2 - Insulating lass units - Part 2: 	<p><u>Insulating glass units:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-1 - Insulating lass units - Part 1: Generalities, dimensional tolerances and rules for the description of the system ● EN 1279-2 - Insulating lass units - Part 2: 	<p><u>Insulating glass units:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-1 - Insulating lass units - Part 1: Generalities, dimensional tolerances and rules for the description of the system ● EN 1279-2 - Insulating lass units - Part 2:

	<p>Long term test method and requirements for moisture penetration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-3 <p>Insulating lass units - Part 3: Long term test method and requirements for gas leakage rate and for gas concentration tolerances</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-4 - Insulating glass units - Part 4: Methods of test for the physical attributes of edge seals ● EN 1279-5 - Insulating glass units - Part 5: Evaluation of conformity ● EN 1279-6 - Insulating glass units - Part 6: Factory production control and periodic test 	<p>Long term test method and requirements for moisture penetration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-3 <p>Insulating lass units - Part 3: Long term test method and requirements for gas leakage rate and for gas concentration tolerances</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-4 - Insulating glass units - Part 4: Methods of test for the physical attributes of edge seals ● EN 1279-5 - Insulating glass units - Part 5: Evaluation of conformity ● EN 1279-6 - Insulating glass units - Part 6: Factory production control and periodic test 	<p>Long term test method and requirements for moisture penetration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-3 <p>Insulating lass units - Part 3: Long term test method and requirements for gas leakage rate and for gas concentration tolerances</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-4 - Insulating glass units - Part 4: Methods of test for the physical attributes of edge seals ● EN 1279-5 - Insulating glass units - Part 5: Evaluation of conformity ● EN 1279-6 - Insulating glass units - Part 6: Factory production control and periodic test 	<p>Long term test method and requirements for moisture penetration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-3 <p>Insulating lass units - Part 3: Long term test method and requirements for gas leakage rate and for gas concentration tolerances</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-4 - Insulating glass units - Part 4: Methods of test for the physical attributes of edge seals ● EN 1279-5 - Insulating glass units - Part 5: Evaluation of conformity ● EN 1279-6 - Insulating glass units - Part 6: Factory production control and periodic test 	<p>Long term test method and requirements for moisture penetration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-3 <p>Insulating lass units - Part 3: Long term test method and requirements for gas leakage rate and for gas concentration tolerances</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1279-4 - Insulating glass units - Part 4: Methods of test for the physical attributes of edge seals ● EN 1279-5 - Insulating glass units - Part 5: Evaluation of conformity ● EN 1279-6 - Insulating glass units - Part 6: Factory production control and periodic test
	<u>strengthened glass:</u>				

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1863-1 - Heat-strengthened soda-lime glass – Part 1: Definition and specification ● EN 1863-2 - Heat-strengthened soda-lime glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard ● prEN 12150-1 - Thermally pre-stressed soda-lime tempered safety glass – Part 1: Definition and specification ● EN 12150-2 - Thermally pre-stressed soda-lime tempered safety glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard ● EN 12337-1 - Chemically strengthened 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1863-1 - Heat-strengthened soda-lime glass – Part 1: Definition and specification ● EN 1863-2 - Heat-strengthened soda-lime glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard ● prEN 12150-1 - Thermally pre-stressed soda-lime tempered safety glass – Part 1: Definition and specification ● EN 12150-2 - Thermally pre-stressed soda-lime tempered safety glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard ● EN 12337-1 - Chemically strengthened soda lime 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1863-1 - Heat-strengthened soda-lime glass – Part 1: Definition and specification ● EN 1863-2 - Heat-strengthened soda-lime glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard ● prEN 12150-1 - Thermally pre-stressed soda-lime tempered safety glass – Part 1: Definition and specification ● EN 12150-2 - Thermally pre-stressed soda-lime tempered safety glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard ● EN 12337-1 - Chemically strengthened soda lime silicate glass - Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 12337-2 - Chemically strengthened 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1863-1 - Heat-strengthened soda-lime glass – Part 1: Definition and specification ● EN 1863-2 - Heat-strengthened soda-lime glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard ● prEN 12150-1 - Thermally pre-stressed soda-lime tempered safety glass – Part 1: Definition and specification ● EN 12150-2 - Thermally pre-stressed soda-lime tempered safety glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard ● EN 12337-1 - Chemically strengthened soda lime 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1863-1 - Heat-strengthened soda-lime glass – Part 1: Definition and specification ● EN 1863-2 - Heat-strengthened soda-lime glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard ● prEN 12150-1 - Thermally pre-stressed soda-lime tempered safety glass – Part 1: Definition and specification ● EN 12150-2 - Thermally pre-stressed soda-lime tempered safety glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard ● EN 12337-1 - Chemically strengthened soda lime
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	<p>soda lime silicate glass - Part 1: Definition and description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 12337-2 - Chemically strengthened soda lime silicate glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard ● EN 13024-1 - Thermally toughened borosilicate safety glass – Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 13024-2 - Thermally toughened borosilicate safety glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard 	<p>silicate glass - Part 1: Definition and description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 12337-2 - Chemically strengthened soda lime silicate glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard ● EN 13024-1 - Thermally toughened borosilicate safety glass – Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 13024-2 - Thermally toughened borosilicate safety glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard 	<p>soda lime silicate glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13024-1 - Thermally toughened borosilicate safety glass – Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 13024-2 - Thermally toughened borosilicate safety glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard 	<p>silicate glass - Part 1: Definition and description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 12337-2 - Chemically strengthened soda lime silicate glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard ● EN 13024-1 - Thermally toughened borosilicate safety glass – Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 13024-2 - Thermally toughened borosilicate safety glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard 	<p>silicate glass - Part 1: Definition and description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 12337-2 - Chemically strengthened soda lime silicate glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ product standard ● EN 13024-1 - Thermally toughened borosilicate safety glass – Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 13024-2 - Thermally toughened borosilicate safety glass – Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14179-1 - Heat soaked thermally toughened soda lime silicate safety glass - Part 1: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14179-1 - Heat soaked thermally toughened soda lime silicate safety glass - Part 1: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14179-1 - Heat soaked thermally toughened soda lime silicate safety glass - Part 1: Definition and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14179-1 - Heat soaked thermally toughened soda lime silicate safety glass - Part 1: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14179-1 - Heat soaked thermally toughened soda lime silicate safety glass - Part 1:

	<p>Definition and description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14179-2 - Heat soaked thermally toughened soda lime silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard ● EN 14321-1 - Thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 14321-2 - Thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard ● EN 15683-1 - Thermally toughened soda lime silicate channel shaped safety glass - Part 1: 	<p>Definition and description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14179-2 - Heat soaked thermally toughened soda lime silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard ● EN 14321-1 - Thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 14321-2 - Thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard ● EN 15683-1 - Thermally toughened soda lime silicate channel shaped safety glass - Part 1: Definition and 	<p>description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14179-2 - Heat soaked thermally toughened soda lime silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard ● EN 14321-1 - Thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 14321-2 - Thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard ● EN 15683-1 - Thermally toughened soda lime silicate channel shaped safety glass - Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 15682-1 - Heat soaked thermally 	<p>Definition and description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14179-2 - Heat soaked thermally toughened soda lime silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard ● EN 14321-1 - Thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 14321-2 - Thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard ● EN 15683-1 - Thermally toughened soda lime silicate channel shaped safety glass - Part 1: Definition and 	<p>Definition and description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 14179-2 - Heat soaked thermally toughened soda lime silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard ● EN 14321-1 - Thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 14321-2 - Thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/ Product standard ● EN 15683-1 - Thermally toughened soda lime silicate channel shaped safety glass - Part 1: Definition and
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	<p>Definition and description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 15682-1 - Heat soaked thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 15682-2 - Heat soaked thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/Product standard 	<p>description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 15682-1 - Heat soaked thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 15682-2 - Heat soaked thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/Product standard 	<p>toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 1: Definition and description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 15682-2 - Heat soaked thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/Product standard 	<p>description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 15682-1 - Heat soaked thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 15682-2 - Heat soaked thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/Product standard 	<p>description</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 15682-1 - Heat soaked thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 1: Definition and description ● EN 15682-2 - Heat soaked thermally toughened alkaline earth silicate safety glass - Part 2: Evaluation of conformity/Product standard
	<p><u>structural sealant glazing:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FprEN 13022-1 - Structural sealant glazing - Part 1: Glass products for structural sealant glazing systems – supported and unsupported monolithic and multiple glazing 	<p><u>structural sealant glazing:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FprEN 13022-1 - Structural sealant glazing - Part 1: Glass products for structural sealant glazing systems – supported and unsupported monolithic and multiple glazing ● FprEN 13022-2 - Structural sealant glazing - 	<p><u>structural sealant glazing:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FprEN 13022-1 - Structural sealant glazing - Part 1: Glass products for structural sealant glazing systems – supported and unsupported monolithic and multiple glazing ● FprEN 13022-2 - Structural sealant glazing - Part 2: Assembly 	<p><u>structural sealant glazing:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FprEN 13022-1 - Structural sealant glazing - Part 1: Glass products for structural sealant glazing systems – supported and unsupported monolithic and multiple glazing ● FprEN 13022-2 - Structural sealant glazing - 	<p><u>structural sealant glazing:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FprEN 13022-1 - Structural sealant glazing - Part 1: Glass products for structural sealant glazing systems – supported and unsupported monolithic and multiple glazing ● FprEN 13022-2 - Structural sealant glazing -

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FprEN 13022-2 - Structural sealant glazing - Part 2: Assembly rules ● ETAG-002: Guideline for european technical approval of Structural Sealant Glazing 	<p>Part 2: Assembly rules</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ETAG-002: Guideline for european technical approval of Structural Sealant Glazing 	<p>rules</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ETAG-002: Guideline for european technical approval of Structural Sealant Glazing 	<p>Part 2: Assembly rules</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ETAG-002: Guideline for european technical approval of Structural Sealant Glazing 	<p>Part 2: Assembly rules</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ETAG-002: Guideline for european technical approval of Structural Sealant Glazing
	Sealing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 9142 - Adhesive: Guidelines for the selection of artificial-ageing conditions for the test of adhesive bonds ● EN ISO 11600 - Building construction - Jointing products - Classification and requirements for sealants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 9142 - Adhesive: Guidelines for the selection of artificial-ageing conditions for the test of adhesive bonds ● EN ISO 11600 - Building construction - Jointing products - Classification and requirements for sealants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 9142 - Adhesive: Guidelines for the selection of artificial-ageing conditions for the test of adhesive bonds ● EN ISO 11600 - Building construction - Jointing products - Classification and requirements for sealants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 9142 - Adhesive: Guidelines for the selection of artificial-ageing conditions for the test of adhesive bonds ● EN ISO 11600 - Building construction - Jointing products - Classification and requirements for sealants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 9142 - Adhesive: Guidelines for the selection of artificial-ageing conditions for the test of adhesive bonds ● EN ISO 11600 - Building construction - Jointing products - Classification and requirements for sealants
	General technical rules for usage					

	of glazing					
		<p>According to glass drill holes and recesses: Glass drill holes and recesses shall be continuous and shall only be produced in glass which is subsequently thermally toughened or heat strengthened. Note: In the case of laminated glass and laminated safety glass, the term ‘continuous’ refers to the individual monolithic pane. The remaining width of glass between drill holes or recesses and adjacent drill holes or recesses shall be 80 mm as a</p>	<p>According to glass drill holes and recesses: Glass drill holes and recesses shall be continuous and shall only be produced in glass which is subsequently thermally toughened or heat strengthened. Note: In the case of laminated glass and laminated safety glass, the term ‘continuous’ refers to the individual monolithic pane. The remaining width of glass between drill holes or recesses and adjacent drill holes or recesses shall be 80 mm as a minimum. In the case of the remaining</p>	<p>According to glass drill holes and recesses: Glass drill holes and recesses shall be continuous and shall only be produced in glass which is subsequently thermally toughened or heat strengthened. Note: In the case of laminated glass and laminated safety glass, the term ‘continuous’ refers to the individual monolithic pane. The remaining width of glass between drill holes or recesses and adjacent drill holes or recesses shall be 80 mm as a minimum. In the case of the remaining width of glass between the edges of the drill</p>	<p>According to glass drill holes and recesses: Glass drill holes and recesses shall be continuous and shall only be produced in glass which is subsequently thermally toughened or heat strengthened. Note: In the case of laminated glass and laminated safety glass, the term ‘continuous’ refers to the individual monolithic pane. The remaining width of glass between drill holes or recesses and adjacent drill holes or recesses shall be 80 mm as a minimum. In the case of the remaining</p>	<p>According to glass drill holes and recesses: Glass drill holes and recesses shall be continuous and shall only be produced in glass which is subsequently thermally toughened or heat strengthened. Note: In the case of laminated glass and laminated safety glass, the term ‘continuous’ refers to the individual monolithic pane. The remaining width of glass between drill holes or recesses and adjacent drill holes or recesses shall be 80 mm as a minimum. In the case of the remaining</p>

		<p>minimum.</p> <p>In the case of the remaining width of glass between the edges of the drill holes or between the edges of the drill holes and the edges of the glass being less than 80 mm, the design value of the load-bearing resistance of the respective base glass shall be taken as a basis for design at the edge of the drill hole.</p>	<p>width of glass between the edges of the drill holes or between the edges of the drill holes and the edges of the glass being less than 80 mm, the design value of the load-bearing resistance of the respective base glass shall be taken as a basis for design at the edge of the drill hole.</p>	<p>holes and the edges of the glass being less than 80 mm, the design value of the load-bearing resistance of the respective base glass shall be taken as a basis for design at the edge of the drill hole.</p>	<p>width of glass between the edges of the drill holes or between the edges of the drill holes and the edges of the glass being less than 80 mm, the design value of the load-bearing resistance of the respective base glass shall be taken as a basis for design at the edge of the drill hole.</p>	<p>width of glass between the edges of the drill holes or between the edges of the drill holes and the edges of the glass being less than 80 mm, the design value of the load-bearing resistance of the respective base glass shall be taken as a basis for design at the edge of the drill hole.</p>
	<p>mechanical resistance and stability</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● C.1 Depending on application and national requirements ● Annex A: Methods for determining the uplift resistance of BIPV roof elements and their snow-load-bearing capability -Requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● C.1 Depending on application and national requirements ● EN 538 - Roofing tiles: Flexural strength test ● EN 380 - Timber structures - Test methods - General 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 380 - Timber structures - Test methods - General principles for static load testing ● EN 1993 - Eurocode 3: Design of steel 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13116 PV is tested as part of the entire façade ● EN 12179 PV is tested as part of the entire façade ● EN/IEC 61215 (the tests take into account variable climatic conditions but national climatic load requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN/IEC 61215 (the tests take into account variable climatic conditions but national climatic load requirements might be higher than the IEC standard loads) Additional national standards may apply, such as in Germany, DIN

	<p>are set by the Eurocode 1 for wind and snows</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 538 - Roofing tiles: Flexural strength test ● EN 380 - Timber structures - Test methods - General principles for static load testing ● EN 1993 - Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings ● EN 1999 - Eurocode 9: Design of aluminium structures - Part 1-1: General structural rules 	<p>principles for static load testing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1993 - Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings ● EN 1999 - Eurocode 9: Design of aluminium structures - Part 1-1: General structural rules 	<p>structures - Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 1999 - Eurocode 9: Design of aluminium structures - Part 1-1: General structural rules 	<p>might be higher than the IEC standard loads) Additional national standards may apply, such as in Germany, DIN 18516 and DIN 18008</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 380 - Timber structures - Test methods - General principles for static load testing ● EN 1993 - Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings ● EN 1999 - Eurocode 9: Design of aluminium structures - Part 1-1: General structural rules 	<p>18516 and DIN 18008</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 380 - Timber structures - Test methods - General principles for static load testing ● EN 1993 - Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings ● EN 1999 - Eurocode 9: Design of aluminium structures - Part 1-1: General structural rules

	<p><u>Glass in building</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 1288-1 - Determination of the beding strength of glass - Part 1: Basic information ● EN ISO 1288-2 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 2: Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with large test surface areas ● EN ISO 1288-3 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 3: Test with specimen supported at two points (four point bending) ● EN ISO 1288-4 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 4: Testing of channel 	<p><u>Glass in building</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 1288-1 - Determination of the beding strength of glass - Part 1: Basic information ● EN ISO 1288-2 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 2: Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with large test surface areas ● EN ISO 1288-3 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 3: Test with specimen supported at two points (four point bending) ● EN ISO 1288-4 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 4: Testing of channel shaped glass ● EN ISO 1288-5 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 5: Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with 	<p><u>Glass in building</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 1288-1 - Determination of the beding strength of glass - Part 1: Basic information ● EN ISO 1288-2 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 2: Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with large test surface areas ● EN ISO 1288-3 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 3: Test with specimen supported at two points (four point bending) ● EN ISO 1288-4 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 4: Testing of channel shaped glass ● EN ISO 1288-5 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 5: Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with small test surface areas 	<p><u>Glass in building</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 1288-1 - Determination of the beding strength of glass - Part 1: Basic information ● EN ISO 1288-2 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 2: Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with large test surface areas ● EN ISO 1288-3 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 3: Test with specimen supported at two points (four point bending) ● EN ISO 1288-4 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 4: Testing of channel shaped glass ● EN ISO 1288-5 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 5: Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with 	<p><u>Glass in building</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 1288-1 - Determination of the beding strength of glass - Part 1: Basic information ● EN ISO 1288-2 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 2: Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with large test surface areas ● EN ISO 1288-3 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 3: Test with specimen supported at two points (four point bending) ● EN ISO 1288-4 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 4: Testing of channel shaped glass ● EN ISO 1288-5 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 5: Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with
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	<p>shaped glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 1288-5 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 5: Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with small test surface areas ● EN 12600 - Pendulum impact test: Method of testing and classification of flat glass ● EN 12603 - Determination of bending strength of glass: Procedure for goodness of fit and confidence intervals for data of Weibull-distribution ● EN 356 - Safety glazing - Testing and classification of resistance against manual attack ● EN 1063 - Glass in building - Security glazing - Testing and classification of resistance against bullet attack; German version ● prEN 16612 - Glass in building - Determination of the load 	<p>small test surface areas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 12600 - Pendulum impact test: Method of testing and classification of flat glass ● EN 12603 - Determination of bending strength of glass: Procedure for goodness of fit and confidence intervals for data of Weibull-distribution ● EN 356 - Safety glazing - Testing and classification of resistance against manual attack ● EN 1063 - Glass in building - Security glazing - Testing and classification of resistance against bullet attack; German version ● prEN 16612 - Glass in building - Determination of the load 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 12600 - Pendulum impact test: Method of testing and classification of flat glass ● EN 12603 - Determination of bending strength of glass: Procedure for goodness of fit and confidence intervals for data of Weibull-distribution ● EN 356 - Safety glazing - Testing and classification of resistance against manual attack ● EN 1063 - Glass in building - Security glazing - Testing and classification of resistance against bullet attack; German version ● prEN 16612 - Glass in building - Determination of the load ● prEN 16613 - Glass in building - Laminated glass 	<p>small test surface areas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 12600 - Pendulum impact test: Method of testing and classification of flat glass ● EN 12603 - Determination of bending strength of glass: Procedure for goodness of fit and confidence intervals for data of Weibull-distribution ● EN 356 - Safety glazing - Testing and classification of resistance against manual attack ● EN 1063 - Glass in building - Security glazing - Testing and classification of resistance against bullet attack; German version ● prEN 16612 - Glass in building - Determination of the load 	<p>small test surface areas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 12600 - Pendulum impact test: Method of testing and classification of flat glass ● EN 12603 - Determination of bending strength of glass: Procedure for goodness of fit and confidence intervals for data of Weibull-distribution ● EN 356 - Safety glazing - Testing and classification of resistance against manual attack ● EN 1063 - Glass in building - Security glazing - Testing and classification of resistance against bullet attack; German version ● prEN 16612 - Glass in building - Determination of the load
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		<p>building - Security glazing - Testing and classification of resistance against bullet attack; German version</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prEN 16612 - Glass in building - Determination of the load resistance of glass panes by calculation and testing ● prEN 16613 - Glass in building - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Determination of interlayer mechanical properties 	<p>resistance of glass panes by calculation and testing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prEN 16613 - Glass in building - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Determination of interlayer mechanical properties 	<p>and laminated safety glass - Determination of interlayer mechanical properties</p>	<p>resistance of glass panes by calculation and testing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prEN 16613 - Glass in building - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Determination of interlayer mechanical properties 	<p>resistance of glass panes by calculation and testing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● prEN 16613 - Glass in building - Laminated glass and laminated safety glass - Determination of interlayer mechanical properties
seismic actions and rules for buildings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ENV 1998-1-1 - Design of structures for seismic resistance (Eurocode 8) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ENV 1998-1-1 - Design of structures for seismic resistance (Eurocode 8) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ENV 1998-1-1 - Design of structures for seismic resistance (Eurocode 8) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ENV 1998-1-1 - Design of structures for seismic resistance (Eurocode 8) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ENV 1998-1-1 - Design of structures for seismic resistance (Eurocode 8) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ENV 1998-1-1 - Design of structures for seismic resistance (Eurocode 8)
Hygiene/toxicity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Annex B, rain penetration 	Transition from the Construction	Transition from the Construction Products	Transition from the Construction	Transition from the Construction	Transition from the Construction

	test Characterization of resistance to wind-driven rain ● EN 61701 - Salt mist corrosion testing of photovoltaic (PV) modules	Products Directive (CPD) to the Construction Products Regulation (CPR): http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/sectors/construction/legislation/transition/index_en.htm Definitely, the data required by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials and optionally LCIA= Life Cycle Impact Assessment. ● EN 61701 - Salt mist corrosion testing of photovoltaic (PV) modules	Directive (CPD) to the Construction Products Regulation (CPR): http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/sectors/construction/legislation/transition/index_en.htm Definitely, the data required by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials and optionally LCIA= Life Cycle Impact Assessment. ● EN 61701 - Salt mist corrosion testing of photovoltaic (PV) modules	Products Directive (CPD) to the Construction Products Regulation (CPR): http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/sectors/construction/legislation/transition/index_en.htm Definitely, the data required by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials and optionally LCIA= Life Cycle Impact Assessment. ● EN 61701 - Salt mist corrosion testing of photovoltaic (PV) modules	Products Directive (CPD) to the Construction Products Regulation (CPR): http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/sectors/construction/legislation/transition/index_en.htm ● EN 61701 - Salt mist corrosion testing of photovoltaic (PV) modules
replac emen t strate gy /	The roof manufacturer is obliged to provide a strategy for	The roof manufacturer is obliged to provide a strategy for the	The façade manufacturer is obliged to provide a strategy for the possible	The façade manufacturer is obliged to provide a strategy for the	The façade manufacturer is obliged to provide a strategy for the

<p>maintenanc e (other wise applic ation is not 'safe')</p>	<p>the possible replacement of solar panels. The manufacturer of the laminated PV- glass panels is obliged to provide a strategy for the replacement with aesthetically equivalent PV- panels. The corresponding criteria are to be defined upfront. --> checklist to be developed in ConstructPV</p>	<p>possible replacement of solar panels. The manufacturer of the laminated PV-glass panels is obliged to provide a strategy for the replacement with aesthetically equivalent PV- panels. The corresponding criteria are to be defined upfront. --> checklist to be developed in ConstructPV</p>	<p>replacement of solar panels. The manufactuerer of the laminated PV- glass panels is obliged to provide a strategy for the replacement with aesthetically equivalent PV- panels. The corresponding criteria are to be defined upfront. - -> checklist to be developed in ConstructPV</p>	<p>possible replacement of solar panels. The manufactuerer of the laminated PV-glass panels is obliged to provide a strategy for the replacement with aesthetically equivalent PV- panels. The corresponding criteria are to be defined upfront. --> checklist to be developed in ConstructPV</p>	<p>possible replacement of solar panels. The manufactuerer of the laminated PV-glass panels is obliged to provide a strategy for the replacement with aesthetically equivalent PV- panels. The corresponding criteria are to be defined upfront. --> checklist to be developed in ConstructPV</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Recycleability of (ventilated) roofs:</u> One crucial factor for sustainability is the recyclability of structural components and building materials. Ventilated roofs are able to fractionate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Recycleability of (ventilated) roofs:</u> One crucial factor for sustainability is the recyclability of structural components and building materials. Ventilated roofs are able to fractionate the components into individual 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Recycleability of façades:</u> One crucial factor for sustainability is the recyclability of structural components and building materials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Recycleability of façades:</u> One crucial factor for sustainability is the recyclability of structural components and building materials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Recycleability of (ventilated) façades:</u> One crucial factor for sustainability is the recyclability of structural components and building materials. Ventilated façades are able to fractionate the components into individual

		the components into individual elements and they are able to recycle each element to the recovered substance cycle.	elements and they are able to recycle each element to the recovered substance cycle.			elements and they are able to recycle each element to the recovered substance cycle.
f u n c t i o n / p e r f o r m a n c e	noise protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 12758 In case specific properties are required, pv panels shall have identical or better properties than the glass types conventional being used ● EN 20140-2 - Acoustics; measurement of sound insulation in buildings and of building elements - Part 2:determination, verification and application of precision data ● EN ISO 140-18 - Acoustics - Measurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 12758 In case specific properties are required, pv panels shall have identical or better properties than the glass types conventional being used ● EN 20140-2 - Acoustics; measurement of sound insulation in buildings and of building elements - Part 2:determination , verification and application of precision data ● EN ISO 140-18 - Acoustics - Measurement of sound insulation in buildings and of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 12758 In case specific properties are required, pv panels shall have identical or better properties than the glass types conventional being used ● EN 20140-2 - Acoustics; measurement of sound insulation in buildings and of building elements - Part 2:determination, verification and application of precision data ● EN ISO 140-18 - Acoustics - Measurement of sound insulation in buildings and of building elements - Part 18: Laboratory measurement of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 12758 In case specific properties are required, pv panels shall have identical or better properties than the glass types conventional being used ● EN 20140-2 - Acoustics; measurement of sound insulation in buildings and of building elements - Part 2:determination , verification and application of precision data ● EN ISO 140-18 - Acoustics - Measurement of sound insulation in buildings and of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 12758 In case specific properties are required, pv panels shall have identical or better properties than the glass types conventional being used ● EN 20140-2 - Acoustics; measurement of sound insulation in buildings and of building elements - Part 2:determination , verification and application of precision data ● EN ISO 140-18 - Acoustics - Measurement of sound insulation in buildings and of

		of sound insulation in buildings and of building elements - Part 18: Laboratory measurement of sound generated by rainfall on building elements	building elements - Part 18: Laboratory measurement of sound generated by rainfall on building elements	sound generated by rainfall on building elements	building elements - Part 18: Laboratory measurement of sound generated by rainfall on building elements	building elements - Part 18: Laboratory measurement of sound generated by rainfall on building elements
	insulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN EN 13162 Layer of insulation according 4108-10 Closed and free of cavities mounting Mineral insulation according DIN EN 13162 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •DIN EN 13162 Layer of insulation according 4108-10 Closed and free of cavities mounting Mineral insulation according DIN EN 13162 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •DIN EN 13162 Layer of insulation according 4108-10 Closed and free of cavities mounting Mineral insulation according DIN EN 13162 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •DIN EN 13162 Layer of insulation according 4108-10 Closed and free of cavities mounting Mineral insulation according DIN EN 13162 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •DIN EN 13162 Layer of insulation according 4108-10 Closed and free of cavities mounting Mineral insulation according DIN EN 13162
	Energy economy and heat retention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 410 Calculation of light and solar energy characteristics . - Applicable only if underlying layer is transparent. • C.2 Calculation of light and solar energy characteristics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 410 Calculation of light and solar energy characteristics. - Applicable only if underlying layer is transparent. • C.2 Calculation of light and solar energy characteristics. -Applicable only 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 410 Calculation of light and solar energy characteristics. - Applicable only if underlying layer is transparent. • C.2 Calculation of light and solar energy characteristics. - Applicable only if underlying layer is transparent. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 410 Calculation of light and solar energy characteristics. - Applicable only if underlying layer is transparent. • C.2 Calculation of light and solar energy characteristics. -Applicable only 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • light and solar energy characteristics might be required (e.g. light transmittance of PV-blinds and shutters or solar reflectance because of façade surface temperature or urban heat island effect)

	<p>-Applicable only if underlying layer is transparent.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 6946 Calculation of thermal characteristics of roof construction. ● EN 673 - Uncoated glass, coated glass, multiple glazing, non-transparent materials in far infrared: Determination of thermal transmittance (U-value) - Calculation method ● EN 674 - Multiple sealed glazing: Determination of thermal transmittance (U value) - Guarded hot plate method ● EN 675 - Multiple sealed glazing: Determination of thermal transmittance (U value) - 	<p>if underlying layer is transparent.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 6946 Calculation of thermal characteristics of roof construction ● Thermal characteristics (U-value). Calculation method (EN13947). ● Provision for application in warm climates in case of rear ventilated façades/structures, probability of overheating phenomenon ● EN 673 - Uncoated glass, coated glass, multiple glazing, non-transparent materials in far infrared: Determination of thermal transmittance (U-value) - Calculation method ● EN 674 - Multiple sealed glazing: Determination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Thermal characteristics (U-value). Calculation method (EN 13947). ● EN 673 - Uncoated glass, coated glass, multiple glazing, non-transparent materials in far infrared: Determination of thermal transmittance (U-value) - Calculation method ● EN 674 - Multiple sealed glazing: Determination of thermal transmittance (U value) - Guarded hot plate method ● EN 675 - Multiple sealed glazing: Determination of thermal transmittance (U value) - Guarded hot plate method 	<p>if underlying layer is transparent.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Thermal characteristics (U-value). Calculation method (EN 13947). ● EN 673 - Uncoated glass, coated glass, multiple glazing, non-transparent materials in far infrared: Determination of thermal transmittance (U-value) - Calculation method ● EN 674 - Multiple sealed glazing: Determination of thermal transmittance (U value) - Guarded hot plate method ● EN 675 - Multiple sealed glazing: Determination of thermal transmittance (U value) - Guarded hot plate method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 12631 - Thermal performance of curtain walling: Calculation of thermal transmittance ● EN 410 Calculation of light and solar energy characteristics. <p>- Applicable only if underlying layer is transparent.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● C.2 Calculation of light and solar energy characteristics. <p>-Applicable only if underlying layer is transparent.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 673 - Uncoated glass, coated glass, multiple glazing, non-transparent materials in far infrared: Determination of thermal transmittance (U-value) - Calculation method ● EN 674 - Multiple sealed glazing:
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	<p>Guarded hot plate method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thermal characteristics (U-value). Calculation method (EN13947) // or measurements (EN673,EN674 ,EN675) •Provision for application in warm climates in case of rear ventilated façades/structures, probability of overheating phenomenon 	<p>of thermal transmittance (U value) - Guarded hot plate method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 675 - Multiple sealed glazing: Determination of thermal transmittance (U value) - Guarded hot plate method 			<p>Determination of thermal transmittance (U value) - Guarded hot plate method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 675 - Multiple sealed glazing: Determination of thermal transmittance (U value) - Guarded hot plate method • Thermal characteristics (U-value). Calculation method (EN13947) // or measurements (EN673,EN674,E N675) •Provision for application in warm climates in case of rear ventilated façades/structures, probability of overheating phenomenon
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 12114 - Thermal performances of buildings - Air permeability of building components and building 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 12114 - Thermal performances of buildings - Air permeability of building components and building 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 12114 - Thermal performances of buildings - Air permeability of building components and building 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 12114 - Thermal performances of buildings - Air permeability of building components and building 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 12114 - Thermal performances of buildings - Air permeability of building components and building

	<p>elements: Laboratory test method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13829 - Thermal performance of buildings - Determination of air permeability of buildings - Fan pressurization method ● EN ISO 14438 - Determination of energy balance value- calculation method ● EN ISO 7345 - Thermal insulation: Physical quantities and definitions ● EN ISO 10211 - Thermal bridges in building construction - Heat flows and surface temperatures: Detailed calculations ● EN ISO 12572 - Hygrothermal performance of building materials and products: Determination of water vapour 	<p>elements: Laboratory test method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13829 - Thermal performance of buildings - Determination of air permeability of buildings - Fan pressurization method ● EN ISO 14438 - Determination of energy balance value- calculation method ● EN ISO 7345 - Thermal insulation: Physical quantities and definitions ● EN ISO 10211 - Thermal bridges in building construction - Heat flows and surface temperatures: Detailed calculations ● EN ISO 12572 - Hygrothermal performance of building materials and products: 	<p>elements: Laboratory test method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13829 - Thermal performance of buildings - Determination of air permeability of buildings - Fan pressurization method ● EN ISO 14438 - Determination of energy balance value- calculation method ● EN ISO 7345 - Thermal insulation: Physical quantities and definitions ● EN ISO 10211 - Thermal bridges in building construction - Heat flows and surface temperatures: Detailed calculations ● EN ISO 12572 - Hygrothermal performance of building materials and products: Determination of water vapour transmission properties 	<p>elements: Laboratory test method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13829 - Thermal performance of buildings - Determination of air permeability of buildings - Fan pressurization method ● EN ISO 14438 - Determination of energy balance value- calculation method ● EN ISO 7345 - Thermal insulation: Physical quantities and definitions ● EN ISO 10211 - Thermal bridges in building construction - Heat flows and surface temperatures: Detailed calculations ● EN ISO 12572 - Hygrothermal performance of building materials and products: 	<p>elements: Laboratory test method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN 13829 - Thermal performance of buildings - Determination of air permeability of buildings - Fan pressurization method ● EN ISO 14438 - Determination of energy balance value- calculation method ● EN ISO 7345 - Thermal insulation: Physical quantities and definitions ● EN ISO 10211 - Thermal bridges in building construction - Heat flows and surface temperatures: Detailed calculations ● EN ISO 12572 - Hygrothermal performance of building materials and products:
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		transmission properties	Determination of water vapour transmission properties		Determination of water vapour transmission properties	Determination of water vapour transmission properties Coefficient of heat: ● DIN EN 13947, edition: 2007-07 Thermotechnical behavior of curtain walls – calculation of the thermal transmission coefficient; German version EN 13947:2006 corrected document (previous document DIN EN 13947:2007-03)
tolerance in visual appearance (especially color uniformity under different viewing angles and irradiation conditions)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● difficult but practically important. In case the pv panel is defined as laminated glass EN 12543-6 applies. In case of big projects it is strongly recommended to include a visual mock-up 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● difficult but practically important. In case the pv panel is defined as laminated glass EN 12543-6 applies. In case of big projects it is strongly recommended to include a visual mock-up as contractually binding basis for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● difficult but practically important. In case the pv panel is defined as laminated glass EN 12543-6 applies. In case of big projects it is strongly recommended to include a visual mock-up as contractually binding basis for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● difficult but practically important. In case the pv panel is defined as laminated glass EN 12543-6 applies. In case of big projects it is strongly recommended to include a visual mock-up as contractually binding basis for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● difficult but practically important. In case the pv panel is defined as laminated glass EN 12543-6 applies. In case of big projects it is strongly recommended to include a visual mock-up as contractually binding basis for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● difficult but practically important. In case the pv panel is defined as laminated glass EN 12543-6 applies. In case of big projects it is strongly recommended to include a visual mock-up as contractually binding basis for

	ions. Also important for subsequent supply)	as contractually binding basis for all aesthetical aspects (such as cell and glass color, cell arrangement, cell shape, ...)	all aesthetical aspects (such as cell and glass color, cell arrangement, cell shape, ...)	all aesthetical aspects (such as cell and glass color, cell arrangement, cell shape, ...)	all aesthetical aspects (such as cell and glass color, cell arrangement, cell shape, ...)	all aesthetical aspects (such as cell and glass color, cell arrangement, cell shape, ...)
	outside glare	<p>same</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Glare should also be considered for special applications such as airport proximity, urban density areas etc. - Lack of european regulations. Only FAA (Federal Aviation Administration -USA) has established some guidelines 	<p>same</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Glare should also be considered for special applications such as airport proximity, urban density areas etc. - Lack of european regulations. Only FAA (Federal Aviation Administration - USA) has established some guidelines 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● difficult but practically important. D: Preliminary national requirements have been layed down in September 2012 in a very bad and primitive document by the 'Landesumweltämter'. The title is 'Hinweise zur Messung, Beurteilung und Minderung von Lichtimmissionen' and it defines the allowable glare level for any kind of PV system. --> dangerous 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● difficult but practically important. D: Preliminary national requirements have been layed down in September 2012 in a very bad and primitive document by the 'Landesumweltämter'. The title is 'Hinweise zur Messung, Beurteilung und Minderung von Lichtimmissionen' and it defines the allowable glare level for any kind of PV system. --> dangerous
	additional standards	<u>Terminology</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 9488 - Solar energy: 	<u>Terminology</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 9488 - Solar energy: 	<u>Terminology</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 9488 - Solar energy: 	<u>Terminology</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 9488 - Solar energy: 	<u>Terminology</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EN ISO 9488 - Solar energy: <u>Vocabulary,</u>

	(vocabulary etc.)	Vocabulary, terminology	Vocabulary, terminology	Vocabulary, terminology	Vocabulary, terminology	<u>terminology</u> <u>Additional Standards of a ventilated façade:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN EN 13119, 2007-07 Curtain walls - terminology EN 13119:2007 ● DIN EN 949, 1999-05 Windows, Doors, roller shutter, curtain walls – resistance-calculation of doors against shock German version EN 949:1998 ● prEN 13830, 2003-11 Curtain walls – Product standard German version EN 13830:2003
e c o n o m i c r e q	sufficiently big market for industrialization	PV-Modules resumes the function of the outer wall, the cladding wall of a cold façade. The costs for BIPV on coldfaçades	PV-Modules resumes the function of the outer wall, the cladding wall of a cold façade. The costs for BIPV on coldfaçades are	PV-Modules resumes the function of the outer wall, the cladding wall of a cold façade. The costs for BIPV on coldfaçades are the balance	PV-Modules resumes the function of the outer wall, the cladding wall of a cold façade. The costs for BIPV on coldfaçades are	PV-Modules resumes the function of the outer wall, the cladding wall of a cold façade. The costs for BIPV on coldfaçades are

u i r e m e n t s		are the balance between the outer wall and the PV façade. -> Saving costs for cold façade. Important is the Power income.	the balance between the outer wall and the PV façade. -> Saving costs for cold façade. Important is the Power income.	between the outer wall and the PV façade. -> Saving costs for cold façade. Important is the Power income.	the balance between the outer wall and the PV façade. -> Saving costs for cold façade. Important is the Power income.	the balance between the outer wall and the PV façade. -> Saving costs for cold façade. Important is the Power income.
	profitable product	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is needed	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is needed decreased cost of installation	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is needed	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is needed

		needed decreased cost of installation	decreased cost of installation		decreased cost of installation	decreased cost of installation
	low risk product	Modules requirements to be a low risk product: high durability, high current production, cheap in production, temperature stability, quick replaceability	Modules requirements to be a low risk product: high durability, high current production, cheap in production, temperature stability, quick replaceability	Modules requirements to be a low risk product: high durability, high current production, cheap in production, temperature stability, quick replaceability	Modules requirements to be a low risk product: high durability, high current production, cheap in production, temperature stability, quick replaceability	Modules requirements to be a low risk product: high durability, high current production, cheap in production, temperature stability, quick replaceability.
	credit worthy/bankable product	Important: to check the investment horizon, amortisation is often after 5-10 years, break even point, costs of opportunity	Important: to check the investment horizon, amortisation is often after 5-10 years, break even point, costs of opportunity	Important: to check the investment horizon, amortisation is often after 5-10 years, break even point, costs of opportunity	Important: to check the investment horizon, amortisation is often after 5-10 years, break even point, costs of opportunity	Important: to check the investment horizon, amortisation is often after 5-10 years, break even point, costs of opportunity
EPD (e nvironmental p)	EPD	ISO 14025 Definitely, the data required by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of	ISO 14025 Definitely, the data required by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials and	ISO 14025 Definitely, the data required by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials and	ISO 14025 Definitely, the data required by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials and	ISO 14025 Definitely, the data required by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials and

r o d u c t d e c l a r a t i o n)		of materials and optionally LCIA= Life Cycle Impact Assessment.	optionally LCIA= Life Cycle Impact Assessment.	optionally LCIA= Life Cycle Impact Assessment.	optionally LCIA= Life Cycle Impact Assessment.	optionally LCIA= Life Cycle Impact Assessment.
f e a s i b i l i t y	produ cibility	See next worksheet ('Producability')	See next worksheet ('Producability')	See next worksheet ('Producability')	See next worksheet ('Producability')	See next worksheet ('Producability')
	constr uction proce ss confo rmy	possibility to replace/reuse/ recycle individual panels in case of future requirements (example aesthetic changes, renovation, partial damage etc.)	possibility to replace/reuse/ recycle individual panels in case of future requirements (example aesthetic changes, renovation, partial damage etc.)			
s o c	to gain	correspondingly the roof	correspondingly the roof could	requirements on visual aspects. A	requirements on visual	requirements on visual

i a l c r i t e r i a	recognition	could be also a 'recognizable characteristic' for a building	be also a 'recognizable characteristic' for a building	façade is the 'skin' of a building. Buildings are automatically judged visual.	aspects. A façade is the 'skin' of a building. Buildings are automatically judged visual.	aspects. A façade is the 'skin' of a building. Buildings are automatically judged visual.
	compliance with ethic goals	The façade have to fulfill goals in CO2 saving, sustainability and renewability.	The façade have to fulfill goals in CO2 saving, sustainability and renewability.	The façade have to fulfill goals in CO2 saving, sustainability and renewability.	The façade have to fulfill goals in CO2 saving, sustainability and renewability.	The façade have to fulfill goals in CO2 saving, sustainability and renewability.

Table: Productability

The following list summarizes possibilities to design modules for building integration with an estimate on the range of freedom in design parameters and the associated effect on cost. Values are only estimates, since factory line is not yet designed. Cost depends also on lot size.

Parameters that can be changed in an automated production line	Range	Estimate of effect on cost if standard module is 100 %	Comment
Module format			
Module size	Ideal > 1 m ²	Smaller sizes than a chosen standard size: +35% per Wp or area, whichever is greater. Bigger, when deviating from a chosen standard size: +15%	For cost reasons modules should not be smaller than 1 m ² .
	For automated line:		
	Maximum size 2x1m		
	Minimum edge length 0.5m.		
Module shape	Automated line: Only rectangular is possible.	Triangular and with smaller edge length than	At least double cost for manual production.

	Manual line: basically no limits	0.5m needs manual processing	
Cell arrangement			
Length of cell string in a module (one direction)	Automated line: 3 to 12 cells	Double cost for manual production.	Not more than 24 cells may be protected by one bypass diode. Depending on cell type only 20 (e.g. double string of 2x10 cells)
	Manual line: 1 to 12 cells		
Cell spacing within string	2 – 40 mm (presumably)		Most common standard: 3mm
Cell string spacing	Min. 2 mm.		
	Automated line: equal spacing only		
Number of strings in a module	Even number! (2 to 6 strings)	Double cost for odd number of strings	Odd numbers only in manual production.
Resulting cell matrix size	Automated line:	Smaller sizes than a chosen standard size: +35% per Wp or area, whichever is greater. Bigger, when deviating from a chosen standard size: +15%	Generally, bigger matrix sizes are more economical in production, but may be less attractive on buildings. 48 cells (6x8cells) is a good choice for BIPV balancing cost, handling and appearance.
	Maximum 6x12 cells		
	Minimum: 2x3 cells		
	Rectangular arrangement only		
	(second number is # of cells in a string)		
	Manual line: 12x12 cells (presumably)		
Cell matrix shape	Automatic production: only rectangular possible		Interconnection of strings of different length is only possible manually.
Edge spacing	Minimum recommended spacing of current carrying parts from		Alongside string ~20mm

	module edge approx. 20mm		Junction box side ~40mm, counter side ~28mm
Colour			
Varying colour of front glass		Not yet known in mass production of custom size modules.	To be investigated. Small quantity of same size may be a hindrance.
Varying colour of interlayers.	Colour effect mainly between cells and at the module edges.	Not yet known. Presumably low.	To be investigated

Details on cell arrangements that would require manual production and are therefore not suitable for a mass market.	Range	Effect on cost
Arranging strings randomly in a module	Variable distance between strings is possible.	At least double cost
Interconnecting randomly cells in a module string	Only straight strings and presumably evenly spaced cells within one string	

Not possible at all:

- No coloured MWT cells available to date.
- Insulating glazing unit: Shipping to glazing company would be necessary. Unsolved warranty issues. High temperatures affect life time.

5.2 German national standards

	<u>Category A</u> Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	<u>Category B</u> Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	<u>Category C</u> transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module	<u>Category D</u> transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module	<u>Category E</u> cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in

				non-accessible from within the building	accessible from within the building	a glass-glass- module
s a f e t y	electrical safety	<u>PV-standards:</u>	<u>PV-standards:</u>	<u>PV-standards:</u>	<u>PV-standards:</u>	<u>PV-standards:</u>
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ZVDH - Information sheet - solar technology for roof and façade ● DIN VDE 0126-21 - Photovoltaic in building ● VDI 6012-technical guideline 1.1 - Integration of distributed and renewables based energy systems in buildings - Fundamentals - Project planning and execution ● VDI 6012-technical guideline 1.2 - Integration of decentralised and regenerative energy systems in buildings - Fundamentals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ZVDH - Information sheet - solar technology for roof and façade ● DIN VDE 0126-21 - Photovoltaic in building ● VDI 6012-technical guideline 1.1 - Integration of distributed and renewables based energy systems in buildings - Fundamentals - Project planning and execution ● VDI 6012-technical guideline 1.2 - Integration of decentralised and regenerative energy systems in buildings - Fundamentals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ZVDH - Information sheet - solar technology for roof and façade ● DIN VDE 0126-21 - Photovoltaic in building ● VDI 6012-technical guideline 1.1 - Integration of distributed and renewables based energy systems in buildings - Fundamentals - Project planning and execution ● VDI 6012-technical guideline 1.2 - Integration of decentralised and regenerative energy systems in buildings - Fundamentals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ZVDH - Information sheet - solar technology for roof and façade ● DIN VDE 0126-21 - Photovoltaic in building ● VDI 6012-technical guideline 1.1 - Integration of distributed and renewables based energy systems in buildings - Fundamentals - Project planning and execution ● VDI 6012-technical guideline 1.2 - Integration of decentralised and regenerative energy systems in buildings - Fundamentals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ZVDH - Information sheet - solar technology for roof and façade ● DIN VDE 0126-21 - Photovoltaic in building ● VDI 6012-technical guideline 1.1 - Integration of distributed and renewables based energy systems in buildings - Fundamentals - Project planning and execution ● VDI 6012-technical guideline 1.2 - Integration of decentralised and regenerative energy systems in buildings - Fundamentals

	- Fixing of solar modules and solar collectors on buildings	- Fixing of solar modules and solar collectors on buildings	- Fixing of solar modules and solar collectors on buildings	- Fixing of solar modules and solar collectors on buildings	- Fixing of solar modules and solar collectors on buildings
	<u>Additional electrical Standards:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN VDE 0680-1 - Personnel protective equipment, protective devices and apparatus for work on electrically energized systems up to 1 000 V - Part 1 ● DIN VDE 0701-0702 - Inspection after repair, modification of electrical appliances - Periodic inspection on electrical appliances ● DIN 18012 - House service connections facilities ● DIN 18015-1 - Electrical installations in 	<u>Additional electrical Standards:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN VDE 0680-1 - Personnel protective equipment, protective devices and apparatus for work on electrically energized systems up to 1 000 V - Part 1 ● DIN VDE 0701-0702 - Inspection after repair, modification of electrical appliances - Periodic inspection on electrical appliances ● DIN 18012 - House service connections facilities ● DIN 18015-1 - Electrical installations in 	<u>Additional electrical Standards:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN VDE 0680-1 - Personnel protective equipment, protective devices and apparatus for work on electrically energized systems up to 1 000 V - Part 1 ● DIN VDE 0701-0702 - Inspection after repair, modification of electrical appliances - Periodic inspection on electrical appliances ● DIN 18012 - House service connections facilities ● DIN 18015-1 - Electrical installations in 	<u>Additional electrical Standards:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN VDE 0680-1 - Personnel protective equipment, protective devices and apparatus for work on electrically energized systems up to 1 000 V - Part 1 ● DIN VDE 0701-0702 - Inspection after repair, modification of electrical appliances - Periodic inspection on electrical appliances ● DIN 18012 - House service connections facilities ● DIN 18015-1 - Electrical installations in 	<u>Additional electrical Standards:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN VDE 0680-1 - Personnel protective equipment, protective devices and apparatus for work on electrically energized systems up to 1 000 V - Part 1 ● DIN VDE 0701-0702 - Inspection after repair, modification of electrical appliances - Periodic inspection on electrical appliances ● DIN 18012 - House service connections facilities ● DIN 18015-1 - Electrical installations in

	<p>residential buildings – Part 1: Planning principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18015-2 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 2: Nature and extent of minimum equipment ● DIN 18015-3 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 3: Wiring and disposition of electrical equipment ● DIN 18015-4 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 4: Home and building electronic system ● DIN VDE 0126-1-1 - Automatic disconnection device between a generator and 	<p>residential buildings – Part 1: Planning principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18015-2 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 2: Nature and extent of minimum equipment ● DIN 18015-3 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 3: Wiring and disposition of electrical equipment ● DIN 18015-4 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 4: Home and building electronic system ● DIN VDE 0126-1-1 - Automatic disconnection device between a generator and 	<p>residential buildings – Part 1: Planning principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18015-2 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 2: Nature and extent of minimum equipment ● DIN 18015-3 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 3: Wiring and disposition of electrical equipment ● DIN 18015-4 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 4: Home and building electronic system ● DIN VDE 0126-1-1 - Automatic disconnection device between a generator and 	<p>residential buildings – Part 1: Planning principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18015-2 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 2: Nature and extent of minimum equipment ● DIN 18015-3 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 3: Wiring and disposition of electrical equipment ● DIN 18015-4 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 4: Home and building electronic system ● DIN VDE 0126-1-1 - Automatic disconnection device between a generator and 	<p>residential buildings – Part 1: Planning principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18015-2 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 2: Nature and extent of minimum equipment ● DIN 18015-3 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 3: Wiring and disposition of electrical equipment ● DIN 18015-4 - Electrical installations in residential buildings – Part 4: Home and building electronic system ● DIN VDE 0126-1-1 - Automatic disconnection device between a generator and
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		the public low voltage grid	the public low voltage grid	the public low voltage grid	the public low voltage grid	the public low voltage grid
	Lightning protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN VDE V 0185-600 - Protection against lightning - Part 600:Testing of the suitability of coated metallic roofs as a natural components of the lightning protection system ● DIN VDE 0800-2-310 - Application of equipotential bonding and grounding in buildings with information technology equipment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN VDE V 0185-600 - Protection against lightning - Part 600:Testing of the suitability of coated metallic roofs as a natural components of the lightning protection system ● DIN VDE 0800-2-310 - Application of equipotential bonding and grounding in buildings with information technology equipment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN VDE 0800-2-310 - Application of equipotential bonding and grounding in buildings with information technology equipment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN VDE 0800-2-310 - Application of equipotential bonding and grounding in buildings with information technology equipment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN VDE 0800-2-310 - Application of equipotential bonding and grounding in buildings with information technology equipment
	safety in case of fire					
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4102-05 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 5: Fire Barriers. Barriers in Lift 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4102-05 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 5: Fire Barriers. Barriers in Lift 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4102-05 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 5: Fire Barriers. Barriers in Lift 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4102-05 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 5: Fire Barriers. Barriers in Lift 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4102-05 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 5: Fire Barriers. Barriers in Lift

	<p>Wells and glazing resistant against fire, definition, requirements and tests</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4102-07 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 7:Roofing; definitions, requirements and testing ● DIN 4102-09 - Roofing; definitions, requirements and testing: Seals for cable penetrations; concepts, requirements and testing ● DIN 4102-12 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components – Part 12: Circuit integrity maintenance of electric cable systems; 	<p>Wells and glazing resistant against fire, definition, requirements and tests</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4102-07 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 7:Roofing; definitions, requirements and testing ● DIN 4102-09 -Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 9: Seals for cable penetrations; concepts, requirements and testing ● DIN 4102-12 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components – Part 12: Circuit integrity maintenance 	<p>Wells and glazing resistant against fire, definition, requirements and tests</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4102-09 -Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 9: Seals for cable penetrations; concepts, requirements and testing ● DIN 4102-12 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components – Part 12: Circuit integrity maintenance of electric cable systems; requirements and testing ● DIN 4102-13 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - 	<p>Wells and glazing resistant against fire, definition, requirements and tests</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4102-09 -Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 9: Seals for cable penetrations; concepts, requirements and testing ● DIN 4102-12 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components – Part 12: Circuit integrity maintenance of electric cable systems; requirements and testing ● DIN 4102-13 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - 	<p>Wells and glazing resistant against fire, definition, requirements and tests</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4102-09 -Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 9: Seals for cable penetrations; concepts, requirements and testing ● DIN 4102-12 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components – Part 12: Circuit integrity maintenance of electric cable systems; requirements and testing ● DIN 4102-13 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components -
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	requirements and testing	of electric cable systems; requirements and testing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 4102-13 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 13: Fire resistant glazing; concepts, requirements and testing	Part 13: Fire resistant glazing; concepts, requirements and testing	Part 13: Fire resistant glazing; concepts, requirements and testing	Part 13: Fire resistant glazing; concepts, requirements and testing
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 4102-13 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 13: Fire resistant glazing; concepts, requirements and testing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18234-1 - Fire safety of large roofs for buildings - Fire exposure from below - Part 1: Definitions, requirements and tests; Roof areas without openings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 4102-13 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 13: Fire resistant glazing; concepts, requirements and testing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18234-1 - Fire safety of large roofs for buildings - Fire exposure from below - Part 1: Definitions, requirements and tests; Roof areas without openings			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN MLTB 09/2009, Attachment 2.6/11 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevention of fire spread over the space between: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timber depth of the gap < 50 mm • Metal depth of the gap < 150 mm • Horizontal fire barrier on each second floor > classification of fire zones > low damaging in case of fire • Interruption of the gap of

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18234-2 - Fire safety of large roofs for buildings - Fire exposure from below - Part 2: List of roofs, which fulfil the requirements of DIN 18234-1; Roof areas without openings ● DIN 18234-3 - Fire safety of large roofs for buildings - Fire exposure from below - Part 3: Definitions, requirements and tests at roof penetrations and roof edges ● DIN 18234-4 - Fire safety of large roofs for buildings - Fire exposure from below - Part 4: List of roof penetrations and roof edges, which fulfil the requirements of DIN 18234-3 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18234-2 - Fire safety of large roofs for buildings - Fire exposure from below - Part 2: List of roofs, which fulfil the requirements of DIN 18234-1; Roof areas without openings ● DIN 18234-3 - Fire safety of large roofs for buildings - Fire exposure from below - Part 3: Definitions, requirements and tests at roof penetrations and roof edges ● DIN 18234-4 - Fire safety of large roofs for buildings - Fire exposure from below - Part 4: List of roof penetrations and roof edges, which fulfil the requirements of DIN 18234-3 			<p>the fire walls > Packing with fire resistant insulation (polystyrene foam [EPS] is not permitted)</p>
safety in use					

						<p><u>Constructive requirements for ventilated façades:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18516-4 <p>The casing of the exterior wall has to be mounted free of constraint forces by using fixed- and sliding spots. Thus a local separation as a result of deformations or a possible noise development because of wind and thermal stress can be avoided.</p> <p>Dividing the casings in districts of 50 m²</p> <p>Distances horizontal, every 8 m</p> <p>vertical, every 2 levels</p> <p>Edge distance of connection and fastening in the casing: at least 10 mm</p>
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						<p><u>Stability of the substructure of a ventilated façade:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18516-6 • DIN 18202 <p>The stability of the load bearing dowel must be covered by the national technical approval (AbZ). Metal substructures are mounted on support profile according to DIN 18202.</p>
						<p><u>Stability of the cladding of a ventilated façade:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18516-6 <p>Cladding elements must be fixed separately. The cladding may not touch the insulation, the mounting system or the wall in case of its deformation. The stiffness ratio between the</p>

						substructure and the cladding needs to be considered.
	water tightness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52461 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Rain strength of just applied sprayable jointing products • DIN 7863-1 - Elastomer glazing and panel gaskets for windows and claddings - Technical delivery conditions – Part 1: Non-cellular elastomer glazing and panel gaskets • DIN 7863-2 - Elastomer glazing and panel gaskets for windows and claddings - Technical delivery conditions – Part 2: Cellular 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52461 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Rain strength of just applied sprayable jointing products • DIN V 20000-201 - Waterproofness: Adaption standard for flexible sheets for waterproofing according to European standards for the use as waterproofing of roofs • DIN 7863-1 - Elastomer glazing and panel gaskets for windows and claddings - Technical delivery conditions – Part 1: Non- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52461 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Rain strength of just applied sprayable jointing products • DIN 7863-1 - Elastomer glazing and panel gaskets for windows and claddings - Technical delivery conditions – Part 1: Non-cellular elastomer glazing and panel gaskets • DIN 7863-2 - Elastomer glazing and panel gaskets for windows and claddings - Technical delivery conditions – Part 2: Cellular 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52461 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Rain strength of just applied sprayable jointing products • DIN 7863-1 - Elastomer glazing and panel gaskets for windows and claddings - Technical delivery conditions – Part 1: Non-cellular elastomer glazing and panel gaskets • DIN 7863-2 - Elastomer glazing and panel gaskets for windows and claddings - Technical delivery conditions – Part 2: Cellular 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52461 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Rain strength of just applied sprayable jointing products • DIN 7863-1 - Elastomer glazing and panel gaskets for windows and claddings - Technical delivery conditions – Part 1: Non-cellular elastomer glazing and panel gaskets • DIN 7863-2 - Elastomer glazing and panel gaskets for windows and claddings - Technical delivery conditions – Part 2: Cellular

		elastomer glazing and panel gaskets	cellular elastomer glazing and panel gaskets • DIN 7863-2 - Elastomer glazing and panel gaskets for windows and claddings - Technical delivery conditions – Part 2: Cellular elastomer glazing and panel gaskets	elastomer glazing and panel gaskets	elastomer glazing and panel gaskets	elastomer glazing and panel gaskets
						The ventilated façade is normative included to the group of stress III according to DIN 4108-3 and it is resistant to driving rain. In the worst case, the driving rain can drain off at the backside of the cover. Thus the thermal insulation is not drenched and it is possible to

						<p>design ventilated façades with open horizontal joints.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18516-4 • DIN 4108-3
	wind resistance and air tightness					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18516-1 - Cladding for external walls, ventilated at rear - Part :Requirements , principles of testing • DIN 18516-3 - Cladding for external walls, ventilated at rear - Part 3:Natural stone; requirements, design • DIN 18516-5 - Cladding for external walls, ventilated at rear - Part 5: Manufactured stone; requirements, design
	resistance against snow and ice loads	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52251-2 - Determination of frost resistance of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52251-2 - Determination of frost resistance of 			

	<p>roofing tiles - Part 2: Indirect methods of determining the frost resistance of roofing tiles; determination of water absorption</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52251-3 <p>-</p> <p>Determination of frost resistance of roofing tiles –</p> <p>Part 3: Indirect methods of determining the frost resistance of roofing tiles; determination of coefficient of impregnation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52251-5 <p>-</p> <p>Determination of frost resistance of roofing tiles –</p> <p>Part 5: Indirect methods of determining the frost resistance of roofing tiles; determination of drying shrinkage and</p>	<p>roofing tiles - Part 2: Indirect methods of determining the frost resistance of roofing tiles; determination of water absorption</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52251-3 <p>-</p> <p>Determination of frost resistance of roofing tiles –</p> <p>Part 3: Indirect methods of determining the frost resistance of roofing tiles; determination of coefficient of impregnation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52251-5 <p>-</p> <p>Determination of frost resistance of roofing tiles –</p> <p>Part 5: Indirect methods of determining the frost resistance of roofing tiles; determination of drying shrinkage and</p>			
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		firing shrinkage	firing shrinkage			
	handling of deformation caused by temperature					<u>Deformation of a ventilated façade:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18516-5 Structures in general can be deformed and the subsoil can be settled because of temperature.
	Cladding	As a rule of thumb in order enough ventilation for the PV module to be provided, the cladding/substructure must provide a gap of around 200 mm between the modules and the roof (???)	As a rule of thumb in order enough ventilation for the PV module to be provided, the cladding/substructure must provide a gap of around 200 mm between the modules and the roof (???)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 55699:2005-02 - Application of thermal insulation composite systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 55699:2005-02 - Application of thermal insulation composite systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 4113 The modules can be separated into two categories. Small modules with a size < 0,4 m² and a weight up to 5,0 kg and bigger modules (see: Construction Products List Part C) (BRL-Teil C). In Germany is a license necessary only for the big modules. In other European countries are no regulations regarding the size of the

						<p>modules.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18516 Part 1-5 <p><u>Structural - physical requirements of the ventilation gaps of ventilated façades:</u></p> <p>Ventilation is necessary to reduce humidity, deposition, conduction of condensation water and for other aspects.</p> <p>Distance: at least 20 mm from the exterior wall Distance can maximal be reduced to 5 mm (roughness of the wall)</p> <p>Free cross section of the ventilation: at least 200 cm²/m</p> <p>Breather hole: at least 50 cm²/1 m length of wall</p>
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	<p>G Terminology, physical properties,...</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1249-11 - Glass in building - Glass edges: concept, characteristics of edge types and finishes ● DIN 1259-1 - Terminology for glass types and groups ● DIN 1259-2 - Terminology of glass products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1249-11 - Glass in building - Glass edges: concept, characteristics of edge types and finishes ● DIN 1259-1 - Terminology for glass types and groups ● DIN 1259-2 - Terminology of glass products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1249-11 - Glass in building - Glass edges: concept, characteristics of edge types and finishes ● DIN 1259-1 - Terminology for glass types and groups ● DIN 1259-2 - Terminology of glass products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1249-11 - Glass in building - Glass edges: concept, characteristics of edge types and finishes ● DIN 1259-1 - Terminology for glass types and groups ● DIN 1259-2 - Terminology of glass products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1249-11 - Glass in building - Glass edges: concept, characteristics of edge types and finishes ● DIN 1259-1 - Terminology for glass types and groups ● DIN 1259-2 - Terminology of glass products
	types of glazing					<p>strengthened glass:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18516-4 - Back-ventilated, non-loadbearing, external enclosures of buildings, made from tempered safety glass panels: Requirements, design and testing methods
	Sealing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52460 - Sealing and glazing: Vocabulary and Terminology ● DIN 18545-1 - Sealing of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52460 - Sealing and glazing: Vocabulary and Terminology ● DIN 18545-1 - Sealing of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52460 - Sealing and glazing: Vocabulary and Terminology ● DIN 18545-1 - Sealing of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52460 - Sealing and glazing: Vocabulary and Terminology ● DIN 18545-1 - Sealing of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52460 - Sealing and glazing: Vocabulary and Terminology ● DIN 18545-1 - Sealing of

	<p>glazing with sealants - Part 1: Requirements, shapes, dimensions, materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18545-2 - Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 2: Sealants, designation, requirements, testing ● DIN 18545-3 - Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 3: Glazing systems, performance ● DIN 52452-2 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility with chemicals ● DIN 52452-4 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Testing of sealing 	<p>glazing with sealants - Part 1: Requirements, shapes, dimensions, materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18545-2 - Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 2: Sealants, designation, requirements, testing ● DIN 18545-3 - Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 3: Glazing systems, performance ● DIN 52452-2 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility with chemicals ● DIN 52452-4 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Testing of sealing 	<p>glazing with sealants - Part 1: Requirements, shapes, dimensions, materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18545-2 - Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 2: Sealants, designation, requirements, testing ● DIN 18545-3 - Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 3: Glazing systems, performance ● DIN 52452-2 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility with chemicals ● DIN 52452-4 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Testing of sealing 	<p>glazing with sealants - Part 1: Requirements, shapes, dimensions, materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18545-2 - Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 2: Sealants, designation, requirements, testing ● DIN 18545-3 - Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 3: Glazing systems, performance ● DIN 52452-2 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility with chemicals ● DIN 52452-4 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Testing of sealing 	<p>glazing with sealants - Part 1: Requirements, shapes, dimensions, materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18545-2 - Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 2: Sealants, designation, requirements, testing ● DIN 18545-3 - Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 3: Glazing systems, performance ● DIN 52452-2 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility with chemicals ● DIN 52452-4 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions: Testing of sealing
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	<p>compounds in building constructions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52453-2 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds for sealing and glazing in building constructions - Part 2: Determination of the migration of binder by filter paper method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52455-1 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 1: Conditioning in standard atmospheres, water, or increased temperatures</p>	<p>compounds in building constructions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52453-2 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds for sealing and glazing in building constructions - Part 2: Determination of the migration of binder by filter paper method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52455-1 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 1: Conditioning in standard atmospheres, water, or increased temperatures</p>	<p>compounds in building constructions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52453-2 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds for sealing and glazing in building constructions - Part 2: Determination of the migration of binder by filter paper method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52455-1 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 1: Conditioning in standard atmospheres, water, or increased temperatures</p>	<p>compounds in building constructions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52453-2 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds for sealing and glazing in building constructions - Part 2: Determination of the migration of binder by filter paper method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52455-1 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 1: Conditioning in standard atmospheres, water, or increased temperatures</p>	<p>compounds in building constructions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52453-2 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds for sealing and glazing in building constructions - Part 2: Determination of the migration of binder by filter paper method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52455-1 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 1: Conditioning in standard atmospheres, water, or increased temperatures</p>
<p>General technical rules for usage of glazing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18008-1 <p>- Design and rules of construction– Part 1: Terms and general rules for design and construction</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18008-1 <p>- Design and rules of construction– Part 1: Terms and general rules for design and construction</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18008-1 <p>- Design and rules of construction– Part 1: Terms and general rules for design and construction</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18008-1 <p>- Design and rules of construction– Part 1: Terms and general rules for design and construction</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18008-1 <p>- Design and rules of construction– Part 1: Terms and general rules for design and construction</p>

	<p>and testing standards</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18008-2 - Design and rules of construction – Part 2: Linear supported glazing ● DIN 18008-3 - Design and rules of construction – Part 3: Point fixed glazing ● DIN 18008-4 - Design and rules of construction – Part 4: Additional requirements for glazing that prevents from falling ● DIN V 11535-1 - Greenhouses – Part 1: Accomplishment and measurement 	<p>and testing standards</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18008-2 - Design and rules of construction – Part 2: Linear supported glazing ● DIN 18008-3 - Design and rules of construction – Part 3: Point fixed glazing ● DIN 18008-4 - Design and rules of construction – Part 4: Additional requirements for glazing that prevents from falling ● DIN V 11535-1 - Greenhouses – Part 1: Accomplishment and measurement 	<p>and testing standards</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18008-2 - Design and rules of construction – Part 2: Linear supported glazing ● DIN 18008-3 - Design and rules of construction – Part 3: Point fixed glazing ● DIN 18008-4 - Design and rules of construction – Part 4: Additional requirements for glazing that prevents from falling ● DIN V 11535-1 - Greenhouses – Part 1: Accomplishment and measurement 	<p>and testing standards</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18008-2 - Design and rules of construction – Part 2: Linear supported glazing ● DIN 18008-3 - Design and rules of construction – Part 3: Point fixed glazing ● DIN 18008-4 - Design and rules of construction – Part 4: Additional requirements for glazing that prevents from falling ● DIN V 11535-1 - Greenhouses – Part 1: Accomplishment and measurement 	<p>and testing standards</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18008-2 - Design and rules of construction – Part 2: Linear supported glazing ● DIN 18008-3 - Design and rules of construction – Part 3: Point fixed glazing ● DIN 18008-4 - Design and rules of construction – Part 4: Additional requirements for glazing that prevents from falling ● DIN V 11535-1 - Greenhouses – Part 1: Accomplishment and measurement
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●DIN 18008-1 This standard is not applicable to individual panes of nominal glass thicknesses of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●DIN 18008-1 This standard is not applicable to individual panes of nominal glass thicknesses of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●DIN 18008-1 This standard is not applicable to individual panes of nominal glass thicknesses of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●DIN 18008-1 This standard is not applicable to individual panes of nominal glass thicknesses of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●DIN 18008-1 This standard is not applicable to individual panes of nominal glass thicknesses of

	<p>less than 3 mm and greater than 19 mm, respectively. Mounting systems are usually point- or linear supported. It is possible to fit in concealed fittings on the back, so the glass edge cover disappears. The glass edges in general have to be verified before fitting. The thickness of glass should not be less than 6 mm and the edges must be bordered that all sharp pieces are removed. Damages may not go further than 15 % of the thickness of the glass pane into the whole glass body. The</p>	<p>less than 3 mm and greater than 19 mm, respectively. Mounting systems are usually point- or linear supported. It is possible to fit in concealed fittings on the back, so the glass edge cover disappears. The glass edges in general have to be verified before fitting. The thickness of glass should not be less than 6 mm and the edges must be bordered that all sharp pieces are removed. Damages may not go further than 15 % of the thickness of the glass pane into the whole glass body. The</p>	<p>less than 3 mm and greater than 19 mm, respectively. Mounting systems are usually point- or linear supported. It is possible to fit in concealed fittings on the back, so the glass edge cover disappears. The glass edges in general have to be verified before fitting. The thickness of glass should not be less than 6 mm and the edges must be bordered that all sharp pieces are removed. Damages may not go further than 15 % of the thickness of the glass pane into the whole glass body. The</p>	<p>less than 3 mm and greater than 19 mm, respectively. Mounting systems are usually point- or linear supported. It is possible to fit in concealed fittings on the back, so the glass edge cover disappears. The glass edges in general have to be verified before fitting. The thickness of glass should not be less than 6 mm and the edges must be bordered that all sharp pieces are removed. Damages may not go further than 15 % of the thickness of the glass pane into the whole glass body. The</p>	<p>less than 3 mm and greater than 19 mm, respectively. Mounting systems are usually point- or linear supported. It is possible to fit in concealed fittings on the back, so the glass edge cover disappears. The glass edges in general have to be verified before fitting. The thickness of glass should not be less than 6 mm and the edges must be bordered that all sharp pieces are removed. Damages may not go further than 15 % of the thickness of the glass pane into the whole glass body. The</p>
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	<p>mounting of point supported tempered safety glass (ESG) higher than 8 m is inspected by an institute accredited by the building authorities. The rated value of the support-resistance by using laminated and laminated safety glass can be increased by 10%.</p>	<p>mounting of point supported tempered safety glass (ESG) higher than 8 m is inspected by an institute accredited by the building authorities. The rated value of the support-resistance by using laminated and laminated safety glass can be increased by 10%.</p>	<p>mounting of point supported tempered safety glass (ESG) higher than 8 m is inspected by an institute accredited by the building authorities. The rated value of the support-resistance by using laminated and laminated safety glass can be increased by 10%.</p>	<p>mounting of point supported tempered safety glass (ESG) higher than 8 m is inspected by an institute accredited by the building authorities. The rated value of the support-resistance by using laminated and laminated safety glass can be increased by 10%.</p>	<p>mounting of point supported tempered safety glass (ESG) higher than 8 m is inspected by an institute accredited by the building authorities. The rated value of the support-resistance by using laminated and laminated safety glass can be increased by 10%.</p>
	<p>According to glass drill holes and recesses: Glass drill holes and recesses shall be continuous and shall only be produced in glass which is subsequently thermally toughened or heat strengthened. Note: In the</p>	<p>According to glass drill holes and recesses: Glass drill holes and recesses shall be continuous and shall only be produced in glass which is subsequently thermally toughened or heat strengthened. Note: In the</p>	<p>According to glass drill holes and recesses: Glass drill holes and recesses shall be continuous and shall only be produced in glass which is subsequently thermally toughened or heat strengthened. Note: In the</p>	<p>According to glass drill holes and recesses: Glass drill holes and recesses shall be continuous and shall only be produced in glass which is subsequently thermally toughened or heat strengthened. Note: In the</p>	<p>According to glass drill holes and recesses: Glass drill holes and recesses shall be continuous and shall only be produced in glass which is subsequently thermally toughened or heat strengthened. Note: In the</p>

	<p>case of laminated glass and laminated safety glass, the term ‘continuous’ refers to the individual monolithic pane.</p> <p>The remaining width of glass between drill holes or recesses and adjacent drill holes or recesses shall be 80 mm as a minimum.</p> <p>In the case of the remaining width of glass between the edges of the drill holes or between the edges of the drill holes and the edges of the glass being less than 80 mm, the design value of the load-bearing resistance of the respective base glass shall be taken</p>	<p>case of laminated glass and laminated safety glass, the term ‘continuous’ refers to the individual monolithic pane.</p> <p>The remaining width of glass between drill holes or recesses and adjacent drill holes or recesses shall be 80 mm as a minimum.</p> <p>In the case of the remaining width of glass between the edges of the drill holes or between the edges of the drill holes and the edges of the glass being less than 80 mm, the design value of the load-bearing resistance of the respective base glass shall be taken</p>	<p>case of laminated glass and laminated safety glass, the term ‘continuous’ refers to the individual monolithic pane.</p> <p>The remaining width of glass between drill holes or recesses and adjacent drill holes or recesses shall be 80 mm as a minimum.</p> <p>In the case of the remaining width of glass between the edges of the drill holes or between the edges of the drill holes and the edges of the glass being less than 80 mm, the design value of the load-bearing resistance of the respective base glass shall be taken</p>	<p>case of laminated glass and laminated safety glass, the term ‘continuous’ refers to the individual monolithic pane.</p> <p>The remaining width of glass between drill holes or recesses and adjacent drill holes or recesses shall be 80 mm as a minimum.</p> <p>In the case of the remaining width of glass between the edges of the drill holes or between the edges of the drill holes and the edges of the glass being less than 80 mm, the design value of the load-bearing resistance of the respective base glass shall be taken</p>	<p>case of laminated glass and laminated safety glass, the term ‘continuous’ refers to the individual monolithic pane.</p> <p>The remaining width of glass between drill holes or recesses and adjacent drill holes or recesses shall be 80 mm as a minimum.</p> <p>In the case of the remaining width of glass between the edges of the drill holes or between the edges of the drill holes and the edges of the glass being less than 80 mm, the design value of the load-bearing resistance of the respective base glass shall be taken</p>
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		as a basis for design at the edge of the drill hole.	as a basis for design at the edge of the drill hole.	as a basis for design at the edge of the drill hole.	as a basis for design at the edge of the drill hole.	as a basis for design at the edge of the drill hole.
		<p>●DIN 18008-2 The glass bite shall be chosen such that long-term structural stability of the glazing is ensured. Unless specified otherwise in the following, a minimum edge cover of 10 mm is required. The linear support shall be bilaterally effective (for pressure and suction) on at least two opposite sides, normal to the plane of the pane. In the case of multiple layers, the linear support shall be effective for all panes. Monolithic single glazing</p>	<p>●DIN 18008-2 The glass bite shall be chosen such that long-term structural stability of the glazing is ensured. Unless specified otherwise in the following, a minimum edge cover of 10 mm is required. The linear support shall be bilaterally effective (for pressure and suction) on at least two opposite sides, normal to the plane of the pane. In the case of multiple layers, the linear support shall be effective for all panes. Monolithic single glazing</p>	<p>●DIN 18008-2 The glass bite shall be chosen such that long-term structural stability of the glazing is ensured. Unless specified otherwise in the following, a minimum edge cover of 10 mm is required. The linear support shall be bilaterally effective (for pressure and suction) on at least two opposite sides, normal to the plane of the pane. In the case of multiple layers, the linear support shall be effective for all panes. Monolithic single glazing</p>	<p>●DIN 18008-2 The glass bite shall be chosen such that long-term structural stability of the glazing is ensured. Unless specified otherwise in the following, a minimum edge cover of 10 mm is required. The linear support shall be bilaterally effective (for pressure and suction) on at least two opposite sides, normal to the plane of the pane. In the case of multiple layers, the linear support shall be effective for all panes. Monolithic single glazing</p>	<p>●DIN 18008-2 The glass bite shall be chosen such that long-term structural stability of the glazing is ensured. Unless specified otherwise in the following, a minimum edge cover of 10 mm is required. The linear support shall be bilaterally effective (for pressure and suction) on at least two opposite sides, normal to the plane of the pane. In the case of multiple layers, the linear support shall be effective for all panes. Monolithic single glazing</p>

	<p>made of types of glass that break into large pieces (e.g. float glass, heat-strengthened glass (TVG), drawn sheet glass, patterned glass) and laminated glass (VG), whose upper edge lies more than 4 m above any public areas, shall be supported on all sides.</p> <p>Monolithic single glazing made of fully toughened safety glass (ESG), whose upper edge lies more than 4 m above any public areas, shall be heat soaked toughened safety glass (ESG-H). This also applies to monolithic toughened</p>	<p>made of types of glass that break into large pieces (e.g. float glass, heat-strengthened glass (TVG), drawn sheet glass, patterned glass) and laminated glass (VG), whose upper edge lies more than 4 m above any public areas, shall be supported on all sides.</p> <p>Monolithic single glazing made of fully toughened safety glass (ESG), whose upper edge lies more than 4 m above any public areas, shall be heat soaked toughened safety glass (ESG-H). This also applies to monolithic toughened</p>	<p>made of types of glass that break into large pieces (e.g. float glass, heat-strengthened glass (TVG), drawn sheet glass, patterned glass) and laminated glass (VG), whose upper edge lies more than 4 m above any public areas, shall be supported on all sides.</p> <p>Monolithic single glazing made of fully toughened safety glass (ESG), whose upper edge lies more than 4 m above any public areas, shall be heat soaked toughened safety glass (ESG-H). This also applies to monolithic toughened</p>	<p>made of types of glass that break into large pieces (e.g. float glass, heat-strengthened glass (TVG), drawn sheet glass, patterned glass) and laminated glass (VG), whose upper edge lies more than 4 m above any public areas, shall be supported on all sides.</p> <p>Monolithic single glazing made of fully toughened safety glass (ESG), whose upper edge lies more than 4 m above any public areas, shall be heat soaked toughened safety glass (ESG-H). This also applies to monolithic toughened</p>	<p>made of types of glass that break into large pieces (e.g. float glass, heat-strengthened glass (TVG), drawn sheet glass, patterned glass) and laminated glass (VG), whose upper edge lies more than 4 m above any public areas, shall be supported on all sides.</p> <p>Monolithic single glazing made of fully toughened safety glass (ESG), whose upper edge lies more than 4 m above any public areas, shall be heat soaked toughened safety glass (ESG-H). This also applies to monolithic toughened</p>
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	safety glass in insulating glass units.				
technical rules for usage point supported glazing	<p>●DIN 18008-3 Additional provision for vertical glazing:</p> <p>The following glazing can be used for vertical glazing: Laminated safety glass made of fully toughened safety glass, Laminated safety glass made of heat soaked toughened safety glass, Laminated safety glass made of heat-strengthened glass (each with drilled or clamped)</p> <p>For vertical glazing that is supported by clamps the following glass can be used: heat soaked</p>	<p>●DIN 18008-3 Additional provision for vertical glazing:</p> <p>The following glazing can be used for vertical glazing: Laminated safety glass made of fully toughened safety glass, Laminated safety glass made of heat soaked toughened safety glass, Laminated safety glass made of heat-strengthened glass (each with drilled or clamped)</p> <p>For vertical glazing that is supported by clamps the following glass can be used: heat soaked</p>	<p>●DIN 18008-3 Additional provision for vertical glazing:</p> <p>The following glazing can be used for vertical glazing: Laminated safety glass made of fully toughened safety glass, Laminated safety glass made of heat soaked toughened safety glass, Laminated safety glass made of heat-strengthened glass (each with drilled or clamped)</p> <p>For vertical glazing that is supported by clamps the following glass can be used: heat soaked</p>	<p>●DIN 18008-3 Additional provision for vertical glazing:</p> <p>The following glazing can be used for vertical glazing: Laminated safety glass made of fully toughened safety glass, Laminated safety glass made of heat soaked toughened safety glass, Laminated safety glass made of heat-strengthened glass (each with drilled or clamped)</p> <p>For vertical glazing that is supported by clamps the following glass can be used: heat soaked</p>	<p>●DIN 18008-3 Additional provision for vertical glazing:</p> <p>The following glazing can be used for vertical glazing: Laminated safety glass made of fully toughened safety glass, Laminated safety glass made of heat soaked toughened safety glass, Laminated safety glass made of heat-strengthened glass (each with drilled or clamped)</p> <p>For vertical glazing that is supported by clamps the following glass can be used: heat soaked</p>

	<p>toughened safety glass with a normal thickness of 6 mm, insulating glass made of heat soaked toughened safety glass, heat-strengthened glass TVG or float glass, Laminated safety glass made of float glass</p> <p>Glass edge of fully toughened safety glass, heat soaked toughened safety glass and heat-strengthened glass requires a seam. Glass edges of float glass require sanding.</p>	<p>toughened safety glass with a normal thickness of 6 mm, insulating glass made of heat soaked toughened safety glass, heat-strengthened glass TVG or float glass, Laminated safety glass made of float glass</p> <p>Glass edge of fully toughened safety glass, heat soaked toughened safety glass and heat-strengthened glass requires a seam. Glass edges of float glass require sanding.</p>	<p>toughened safety glass with a normal thickness of 6 mm, insulating glass made of heat soaked toughened safety glass, heat-strengthened glass TVG or float glass, Laminated safety glass made of float glass</p> <p>Glass edge of fully toughened safety glass, heat soaked toughened safety glass and heat-strengthened glass requires a seam. Glass edges of float glass require sanding.</p>	<p>toughened safety glass with a normal thickness of 6 mm, insulating glass made of heat soaked toughened safety glass, heat-strengthened glass TVG or float glass, Laminated safety glass made of float glass</p> <p>Glass edge of fully toughened safety glass, heat soaked toughened safety glass and heat-strengthened glass requires a seam. Glass edges of float glass require sanding.</p>	<p>toughened safety glass with a normal thickness of 6 mm, insulating glass made of heat soaked toughened safety glass, heat-strengthened glass TVG or float glass, Laminated safety glass made of float glass</p> <p>Glass edge of fully toughened safety glass, heat soaked toughened safety glass and heat-strengthened glass requires a seam. Glass edges of float glass require sanding.</p>
mechanical resistance and stability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● C.1 Depending on application and national requirements ● Annex A: Methods for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● C.1 Depending on application and national requirements ● <u>Glass in</u> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Glass in building</u> ● DIN 52314 - Testing of glass: Tensile test for the determination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Glass in building</u> ● DIN 52314 - Testing of glass: Tensile test for the determination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Glass in building</u> ● DIN 52314 - Testing of glass: Tensile test for the determination

	<p>determining the uplift resistance of BIPV roof elements and their snow-load-bearing capability</p> <p>-Requirements are set by the Eurocode 1 for wind and snows</p> <p><u>Glass in building</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52314 - Testing of glass: Tensile test for the determination of stress optical coefficient ● DIN 52327-1 - Testing of glass: Determination of stresses in glass-to-glass sealing ● DIN 52327-2 - Testing of glass: Determination of stresses in glass-to metal belts sealing 	<p><u>building</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52314 - Testing of glass: Tensile test for the determination of stress optical coefficient ● DIN 52327-1 - Testing of glass: Determination of stresses in glass-to-glass sealing ● DIN 52327-2 - Testing of glass: Determination of stresses in glass-to metal belts sealing 	<p>of stress optical coefficient</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52327-1 - Testing of glass: Determination of stresses in glass-to-glass sealing ● DIN 52327-2 - Testing of glass: Determination of stresses in glass-to metal belts sealing 	<p>of stress optical coefficient</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52327-1 - Testing of glass: Determination of stresses in glass-to-glass sealing ● DIN 52327-2 - Testing of glass: Determination of stresses in glass-to metal belts sealing 	<p>of stress optical coefficient</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 52327-1 - Testing of glass: Determination of stresses in glass-to-glass sealing ● DIN 52327-2 - Testing of glass: Determination of stresses in glass-to metal belts sealing
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18032-3 - Sport halls - Halls for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18032-3 - Sport halls - Halls for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18032-3 - Sport halls - Halls for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18032-3 - Sport halls - Halls for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 18032-3 - Sport halls - Halls for

		gymnastics, games and multi-purpose use - Part 3: Testing of safety against ball throwing ● DIN 52338 - Testing method for flat glass in buildings: Falling ball test for laminated glass	gymnastics, games and multi-purpose use - Part 3: Testing of safety against ball throwing ● DIN 52338 - Testing method for flat glass in buildings: Falling ball test for laminated glass	gymnastics, games and multi-purpose use - Part 3: Testing of safety against ball throwing ● DIN 52338 - Testing method for flat glass in buildings: Falling ball test for laminated glass	gymnastics, games and multi-purpose use - Part 3: Testing of safety against ball throwing ● DIN 52338 - Testing method for flat glass in buildings: Falling ball test for laminated glass	gymnastics, games and multi-purpose use - Part 3: Testing of safety against ball throwing ● DIN 52338 - Testing method for flat glass in buildings: Falling ball test for laminated glass
	seismic actions and rules for buildings					
	Hygiene/toxicity	● Annex B, rain penetration test Characterization of resistance to wind-driven rain	Transition from the Construction Products Directive (CPD) to the Construction Products Regulation (CPR): http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/sectors/construction/legislation/transition/index_en.htm Definitely, the data required	Transition from the Construction Products Directive (CPD) to the Construction Products Regulation (CPR): http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/sectors/construction/legislation/transition/index_en.htm Definitely, the data required	Transition from the Construction Products Directive (CPD) to the Construction Products Regulation (CPR): http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/sectors/construction/legislation/transition/index_en.htm Definitely, the data required	Transition from the Construction Products Directive (CPD) to the Construction Products Regulation (CPR): http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/sectors/construction/legislation/transition/index_en.htm Definitely, the data required

			by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials and optionally LCIA= Life Cycle Impact Assessment.	by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials and optionally LCIA= Life Cycle Impact Assessment.	by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials and optionally LCIA= Life Cycle Impact Assessment.	
	replacement strategy / maintenance (otherwise application is not 'safe')	The roof manufacturer is obliged to provide a strategy for the possible replacement of solar panels. The manufacturer of the laminated PV-glass panels is obliged to provide a strategy for the replacement with aesthetically equivalent PV-panels. The corresponding criteria are to	The roof manufacturer is obliged to provide a strategy for the possible replacement of solar panels. The manufacturer of the laminated PV-glass panels is obliged to provide a strategy for the replacement with aesthetically equivalent PV-panels. The corresponding criteria are to	The façade manufacturer is obliged to provide a strategy for the possible replacement of solar panels. The manufacturer of the laminated PV-glass panels is obliged to provide a strategy for the replacement with aesthetically equivalent PV-panels. The corresponding criteria are to	The façade manufacturer is obliged to provide a strategy for the possible replacement of solar panels. The manufacturer of the laminated PV-glass panels is obliged to provide a strategy for the replacement with aesthetically equivalent PV-panels. The corresponding criteria are to	The façade manufacturer is obliged to provide a strategy for the possible replacement of solar panels. The manufacturer of the laminated PV-glass panels is obliged to provide a strategy for the replacement with aesthetically equivalent PV-panels. The corresponding criteria are to

	<p>be defined upfront. --> checklist to be developed in ConstructPV</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4426 - Equipment for building maintenance - Safety requirements for workplaces and accesses: Design and execution 	<p>be defined upfront. --> checklist to be developed in ConstructPV</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4426 - Equipment for building maintenance - Safety requirements for workplaces and accesses: Design and execution 	<p>be defined upfront. --> checklist to be developed in ConstructPV</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4426 - Equipment for building maintenance - Safety requirements for workplaces and accesses: Design and execution 	<p>be defined upfront. --> checklist to be developed in ConstructPV</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4426 - Equipment for building maintenance - Safety requirements for workplaces and accesses: Design and execution 	<p>be defined upfront. --> checklist to be developed in ConstructPV</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4426 - Equipment for building maintenance - Safety requirements for workplaces and accesses: Design and execution
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Recycleability of (ventilated) roofs:</u> One crucial factor for sustainability is the recyclability of structural components and building materials. Ventilated roofs are able to fractionate the components into individual elements and they are able to recycle each element to the recovered 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Recycleability of (ventilated) roofs:</u> One crucial factor for sustainability is the recyclability of structural components and building materials. Ventilated roofs are able to fractionate the components into individual elements and they are able to recycle each element to the recovered 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Recycleability of façades:</u> One crucial factor for sustainability is the recyclability of structural components and building materials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Recycleability of façades:</u> One crucial factor for sustainability is the recyclability of structural components and building materials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Recycleability of (ventilated) façades:</u> One crucial factor for sustainability is the recyclability of structural components and building materials. Ventilated façades are able to fractionate the components into individual elements and they are able to recycle each element to the recovered

		substance cycle.	substance cycle.			substance cycle.
f u n c t i o n / p e r f o r m a n c e	noise protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1320 - Acoustics: Vocabulary ant Terminology ● DIN 4109 - Sound insulation in buildings: Requirements and testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1320 - Acoustics: Vocabulary ant Terminology ● DIN 4109 - Sound insulation in buildings: Requirements and testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1320 - Acoustics: Vocabulary ant Terminology ● DIN 4109 - Sound insulation in buildings: Requirements and testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1320 - Acoustics: Vocabulary ant Terminology ● DIN 4109 - Sound insulation in buildings: Requirements and testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1320 - Acoustics: Vocabulary ant Terminology ● DIN 4109 (-) - Sound insulation in buildings: Requirements and testing <p>The requirements of the sound insulation are achieved by the calm-shell construction, especially by the connection with massive main walls. According to the thickness of the insulation, the mass of the casing and the percentage of open joints, the sound insulation can be increased to 14 dB. (FVHF)</p>
	Insect protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 68800-2 () <p>A grate has to</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 68800-2 () <p>A grate has to</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 68800-2 () <p>A grate has to</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 68800-2 () <p>A grate has to</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 68800-2 () <p>A grate has to</p>

		<p>be attached to avoid the infiltration by insects or birds. Remaining minimum cross section: 2 ‰ or 1/500 of the roof area according to 68800-2 DIN 1320</p>	<p>be attached to avoid the infiltration by insects or birds. Remaining minimum cross section: 2 ‰ or 1/500 of the roof area according to 68800-2</p>	<p>be attached to avoid the infiltration by insects or birds. Remaining minimum cross section: 2 ‰ or 1/500 of the wall area according to 68800-2</p>	<p>be attached to avoid the infiltration by insects or birds. Remaining minimum cross section: 2 ‰ or 1/500 of the wall area according to 68800-2</p>	<p>be attached to avoid the infiltration by insects or birds. Remaining minimum cross section: 2 ‰ or 1/500 of the wall area according to 68800-2</p>
	insulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-10 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 10: Application-related requirements for thermal insulation materials – Factory made products ● DIN 4108-2 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 2: Minimum requirements to thermal insulation ● DIN 52619-3 - Testing of thermal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-10 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 10: Application-related requirements for thermal insulation materials – Factory made products ● DIN 4108-2 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 2: Minimum requirements to thermal insulation ● DIN 52619-3 - Testing of thermal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-10 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 10: Application-related requirements for thermal insulation materials – Factory made products ● DIN 4108-2 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 2: Minimum requirements to thermal insulation ● DIN 52619-3 - Testing of thermal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-10 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 10: Application-related requirements for thermal insulation materials – Factory made products ● DIN 4108-2 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 2: Minimum requirements to thermal insulation ● DIN 52619-3 - Testing of thermal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-10 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 10: Application-related requirements for thermal insulation materials – Factory made products ● DIN 4108-2 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 2: Minimum requirements to thermal insulation ● DIN 52619-3 - Testing of thermal

		insulation: Determination of the thermal resistance and the thermal transmission coefficient of windows; determination on frames	insulation: Determination of the thermal resistance and the thermal transmission coefficient of windows; determination on frames	insulation: Determination of the thermal resistance and the thermal transmission coefficient of windows; determination on frames	insulation: Determination of the thermal resistance and the thermal transmission coefficient of windows; determination on frames	insulation: Determination of the thermal resistance and the thermal transmission coefficient of windows; determination on frames
	Energy economy and heat retention					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● light and solar energy characteristics might be required (e.g. light transmittance of PV-blinds and shutters or solar reflectance because of façade surface temperature or urban heat island effect)
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1341 - Heat transfer: Concepts dimensionless parameters: Terms, conduction, radiation and convection ● DIN 1345 - Thermodynamics: Terminology, quantities and concepts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1341 - Heat transfer: Concepts dimensionless parameters: Terms, conduction, radiation and convection ● DIN 1345 - Thermodynamics: Terminology, quantities and concepts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1341 - Heat transfer: Concepts dimensionless parameters: Terms, conduction, radiation and convection ● DIN 1345 - Thermodynamics: Terminology, quantities and concepts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1341 - Heat transfer: Concepts dimensionless parameters: Terms, conduction, radiation and convection ● DIN 1345 - Thermodynamics: Terminology, quantities and concepts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1341 - Heat transfer: Concepts dimensionless parameters: Terms, conduction, radiation and convection ● DIN 1345 - Thermodynamics: Terminology, quantities and concepts

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-3 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 3: Protection against moisture caused by the climate, Requirements and directions for planning and construction ● DIN 4108-4 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 4: Hygrothermal design values ● DIN V 4108-6 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 6: Calculation of annual heat and energy use ● DIN 4108-7 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-3 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 3: Protection against moisture caused by the climate, Requirements and directions for planning and construction ● DIN 4108-4 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 4: Hygrothermal design values ● DIN V 4108-6 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 6: Calculation of annual heat and energy use ● DIN 4108-7 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-3 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 3: Protection against moisture caused by the climate, Requirements and directions for planning and construction ● DIN 4108-4 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 4: Hygrothermal design values ● DIN V 4108-6 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 6: Calculation of annual heat and energy use ● DIN 4108-7 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-3 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 3: Protection against moisture caused by the climate, Requirements and directions for planning and construction ● DIN 4108-4 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 4: Hygrothermal design values ● DIN V 4108-6 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 6: Calculation of annual heat and energy use ● DIN 4108-7 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-3 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 3: Protection against moisture caused by the climate, Requirements and directions for planning and construction ● DIN 4108-4 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 4: Hygrothermal design values ● DIN V 4108-6 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 6: Calculation of annual heat and energy use ● DIN 4108-7 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part
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		7: Air tightness of buildings - Requirements, recommendations and examples for planning and performance	7: Air tightness of buildings - Requirements, recommendations and examples for planning and performance	7: Air tightness of buildings - Requirements, recommendations and examples for planning and performance	7: Air tightness of buildings - Requirements, recommendations and examples for planning and performance	7: Air tightness of buildings - Requirements, recommendations and examples for planning and performance Coefficient of heat:
tolerance in visual appearance (especially color uniformity under different viewing angles and irradiation conditions. Also important for subsequent supply)	In case of big projects it is strongly recommended to include a visual mock-up as contractually binding basis for all aesthetical aspects (such as cell and glass color, cell arrangement, cell shape, ...)	In case of big projects it is strongly recommended to include a visual mock-up as contractually binding basis for all aesthetical aspects (such as cell and glass color, cell arrangement, cell shape, ...)	In case of big projects it is strongly recommended to include a visual mock-up as contractually binding basis for all aesthetical aspects (such as cell and glass color, cell arrangement, cell shape, ...)	In case of big projects it is strongly recommended to include a visual mock-up as contractually binding basis for all aesthetical aspects (such as cell and glass color, cell arrangement, cell shape, ...)	In case of big projects it is strongly recommended to include a visual mock-up as contractually binding basis for all aesthetical aspects (such as cell and glass color, cell arrangement, cell shape, ...)	In case of big projects it is strongly recommended to include a visual mock-up as contractually binding basis for all aesthetical aspects (such as cell and glass color, cell arrangement, cell shape, ...)
outside glare	●Glare should also be considered for special applications such as airport proximity, urban density areas etc. - Lack of european	●Glare should also be considered for special applications such as airport proximity, urban density areas etc. - Lack of european		● difficult but practically important. D: Preliminary national requirements have been layed down in September 2012 in a very bad and	● difficult but practically important. D: Preliminary national requirements have been layed down in September 2012 in a very bad and	

		regulations. Only FAA (Federal Aviation Administration -USA) has established some guidelines	regulations. Only FAA (Federal Aviation Administration -USA) has established some guidelines		primitive document by the 'Landesumwel tämter'. The title is 'Hinweise zur Messung, Beurteilung und Minderung von Lichtimmission en' and it defines the allowable glare level for any kind of PV system. --> dangerous	primitive document by the 'Landesumwel tämter'. The title is 'Hinweise zur Messung, Beurteilung und Minderung von Lichtimmission en' and it defines the allowable glare level for any kind of PV system. --> dangerous
	additional standards (vocabula ry etc.)					<u>Terminology</u> <u>Additional</u> <u>Standards of a</u> <u>ventilated</u> <u>façade:</u> ●DIN 18351, 2010-04 VOB German construction contract procedure, Part C: General technical conditions of contract Ventilated façades
		● DIN 1341 - Heat transfer:	● DIN 1341 - Heat transfer:	● DIN 1341 - Heat transfer:	● DIN 1341 - Heat transfer:	● DIN 1341 - Heat transfer:

	<p>Concepts dimensionless parameters: Terms, conduction, radiation and convection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1345 - Thermodynamics: <p>Terminology, quantities and concepts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-3 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 3: Protection against moisture caused by the climate, Requirements and directions for planning and construction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-4 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 4: Hygrothermal design values <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN V 4108-6 - Thermal protection and 	<p>Concepts dimensionless parameters: Terms, conduction, radiation and convection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1345 - Thermodynamics: <p>Terminology, quantities and concepts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-3 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 3: Protection against moisture caused by the climate, Requirements and directions for planning and construction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-4 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 4: Hygrothermal design values <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN V 4108-6 - Thermal protection and 	<p>Concepts dimensionless parameters: Terms, conduction, radiation and convection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1345 - Thermodynamics: <p>Terminology, quantities and concepts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-3 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 3: Protection against moisture caused by the climate, Requirements and directions for planning and construction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-4 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 4: Hygrothermal design values <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN V 4108-6 - Thermal protection and 	<p>Concepts dimensionless parameters: Terms, conduction, radiation and convection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1345 - Thermodynamics: <p>Terminology, quantities and concepts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-3 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 3: Protection against moisture caused by the climate, Requirements and directions for planning and construction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-4 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 4: Hygrothermal design values <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN V 4108-6 - Thermal protection and 	<p>Concepts dimensionless parameters: Terms, conduction, radiation and convection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 1345 - Thermodynamics: <p>Terminology, quantities and concepts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-3 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 3: Protection against moisture caused by the climate, Requirements and directions for planning and construction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN 4108-4 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 4: Hygrothermal design values <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DIN V 4108-6 - Thermal protection and
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		energy economy in buildings - Part 6: Calculation of annual heat and energy use ● DIN 4108-7 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 7: Air tightness of buildings - Requirements, recommendations and examples for planning and performance	energy economy in buildings - Part 6: Calculation of annual heat and energy use ● DIN 4108-7 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 7: Air tightness of buildings - Requirements, recommendations and examples for planning and performance	energy economy in buildings - Part 6: Calculation of annual heat and energy use ● DIN 4108-7 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 7: Air tightness of buildings - Requirements, recommendations and examples for planning and performance	energy economy in buildings - Part 6: Calculation of annual heat and energy use ● DIN 4108-7 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 7: Air tightness of buildings - Requirements, recommendations and examples for planning and performance	energy economy in buildings - Part 6: Calculation of annual heat and energy use ● DIN 4108-7 - Thermal protection and energy economy in buildings - Part 7: Air tightness of buildings - Requirements, recommendations and examples for planning and performance Coefficient of heat:
economically requirements	sufficiently big market for industrialization	PV-Modules resumes the function of the outer wall, the cladding wall of a cold façade. The costs for BIPV on coldfaçades are the balance between the outer wall and the PV façade. -> Saving costs for cold façade. Important is	PV-Modules resumes the function of the outer wall, the cladding wall of a cold façade. The costs for BIPV on coldfaçades are the balance between the outer wall and the PV façade. -> Saving costs for cold façade. Important is	PV-Modules resumes the function of the outer wall, the cladding wall of a cold façade. The costs for BIPV on coldfaçades are the balance between the outer wall and the PV façade. -> Saving costs for cold façade. Important is	PV-Modules resumes the function of the outer wall, the cladding wall of a cold façade. The costs for BIPV on coldfaçades are the balance between the outer wall and the PV façade. -> Saving costs for cold façade. Important is	PV-Modules resumes the function of the outer wall, the cladding wall of a cold façade. The costs for BIPV on coldfaçades are the balance between the outer wall and the PV façade. -> Saving costs for cold façade. Important is

		the Power income.				
	profitable product	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is needed	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is needed	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is needed	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is needed	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is needed
	low risk product	decreased cost of installation				
		Modules requirements to be a low risk product: high	Modules requirements to be a low risk product: high	Modules requirements to be a low risk product: high	Modules requirements to be a low risk product: high	Modules requirements to be a low risk product: high

		durability, high current production, cheap in production, temperature stability, quick replaceability	durability, high current production, cheap in production, temperature stability, quick replaceability	durability, high current production, cheap in production, temperature stability, quick replaceability	durability, high current production, cheap in production, temperature stability, quick replaceability	durability, high current production, cheap in production, temperature stability, quick replaceability.
	creditworthy/bankable product	Important: to check the investment horizon, amortisation is often after 5-10 years, break even point, costs of opportunity	Important: to check the investment horizon, amortisation is often after 5-10 years, break even point, costs of opportunity	Important: to check the investment horizon, amortisation is often after 5-10 years, break even point, costs of opportunity	Important: to check the investment horizon, amortisation is often after 5-10 years, break even point, costs of opportunity	Important: to check the investment horizon, amortisation is often after 5-10 years, break even point, costs of opportunity
f	e a s i b i l i t y p r o d u c i b i l i t y	See next worksheet ('Producability')	See next worksheet ('Producability')	See next worksheet ('Producability')	See next worksheet ('Producability')	See next worksheet ('Producability')
		possibility to replace/reuse/recycle individual panels in case of future requirements (example aesthetic changes, renovation,	possibility to replace/reuse/recycle individual panels in case of future requirements (example aesthetic changes, renovation,			

		partial damage etc.)	partial damage etc.)			
s o c i a l c r i t e r i a	to gain recognition	correspondingly the roof could be also a 'recognizable characteristic' for a building	correspondingly the roof could be also a 'recognizable characteristic' for a building	requirements on visual aspects. A façade is the 'skin' of a building. Buildings are automatically judged visual.	requirements on visual aspects. A façade is the 'skin' of a building. Buildings are automatically judged visual.	requirements on visual aspects. A façade is the 'skin' of a building. Buildings are automatically judged visual.
	compliance with ethic goals	The façade have to fulfill goals in CO2 saving, sustainability and renewability.	The façade have to fulfill goals in CO2 saving, sustainability and renewability.	The façade have to fulfill goals in CO2 saving, sustainability and renewability.	The façade have to fulfill goals in CO2 saving, sustainability and renewability.	The façade have to fulfill goals in CO2 saving, sustainability and renewability.

5.3 French national standards

		Category A Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	Category B Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	Category C transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	Category D transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	Category E cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
s	electrical safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-105 - Crystalline silicon terrestrial photovoltaic modules - Design qualification and type approval 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-105 - Crystalline silicon terrestrial photovoltaic modules - Design qualification and type approval 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-105 - Crystalline silicon terrestrial photovoltaic modules - Design qualification and type approval 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-105 - Crystalline silicon terrestrial photovoltaic modules - Design qualification and type approval 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-105 - Crystalline silicon terrestrial photovoltaic modules - Design qualification and type approval
a		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-310 - Direct transformation of solar energy into electrical energy. Photovoltaic pumping system. Predicted characteristics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-310 - Direct transformation of solar energy into electrical energy. Photovoltaic pumping system. Predicted characteristics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-310 - Direct transformation of solar energy into electrical energy. Photovoltaic pumping system. Predicted characteristics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-310 - Direct transformation of solar energy into electrical energy. Photovoltaic pumping system. Predicted characteristics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-310 - Direct transformation of solar energy into electrical energy. Photovoltaic pumping system. Predicted characteristics
f		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-300 - Photovoltaic system performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-300 - Photovoltaic system performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-300 - Photovoltaic system performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-300 - Photovoltaic system performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF C57-300 - Photovoltaic system performance

		monitoring - Guidelines for measurement, data exchange and analysis				
	safety in use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3228 - Guideline of the CSTB about shock test ● NF P20-501 - Test methods for windows ● NF P24-301 - Technical specifications for metal windows, french windows and fixed frame 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3228 - Guideline of the CSTB about shock test ● NF P20-501 - Test methods for windows ● NF P24-301 - Technical specifications for metal windows, french windows and fixed frame 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3228 - Guideline of the CSTB about shock test ● NF P20-501 - Test methods for windows ● NF P24-301 - Technical specifications for metal windows, french windows and fixed frame 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3228 - Guideline of the CSTB about shock test ● NF P20-501 - Test methods for windows ● NF P24-301 - Technical specifications for metal windows, french windows and fixed frame 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3228 - Guideline of the CSTB about shock test ● NF P20-501 - Test methods for windows ● NF P24-301 - Technical specifications for metal windows, french windows and fixed frame
						<u>Constructive requirements for ventilated façades:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF DTU 33.1:2008 - Building Construction Works - Curtain- walling - Part 1-1: Contract Bill Of Technical Model Clauses - Part 1-2: General Criteria For Selection Of

						<p>Materials - Part 2: Contract Bill Of Special Administrative Model Clauses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P24-351 - Metal joinery. Windows, curtain walling, metal frame panels. Protection against corrosion and conservation of surface conditions + (NF P24- 351/A1 July 2003; NF P24- 351/A2 March 2012)
slate, shingles and roofing tiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P31-201 - DTU 40-22. Building works. Roof- covering made from hollow terracotta tiles. Part 1 : technical specifications - Part 2 : special clauses. + (NF P31-201-1/A1 December 1996; NF P31- 201-1/A2 January 1999; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P31-201 - DTU 40-22. Building works. Roof- covering made from hollow terracotta tiles. Part 1 : technical specifications - Part 2 : special clauses. + (NF P31-201-1/A1 December 1996; NF P31- 201-1/A2 January 1999; 				

		<p>NF P31-201-1/A3 September 2001; NF P31-201-1/A4 October 2010)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P31-204-1 - DTU 40-23. Building works. Roof covering made of clay plain roofing tiles. Part 1 : technical specifications + (NF P31-204-1/A1:2001-09-01; NF P31-204-1/A2:2007-09-01) ● NF P31-207-1 - DTU 40-24. Building works. Roof covering made of interlocking concrete tiles. Part 1 : technical specifications + (NF P31-207-1/A1:1999-02-01 ; NF P31-207-1/A2:2001-06-01) ● NF P31-305 - Clay curved roofing tiles. 	<p>NF P31-201-1/A3 September 2001; NF P31-201-1/A4 October 2010)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P31-204-1 - DTU 40-23. Building works. Roof covering made of clay plain roofing tiles. Part 1 : technical specifications + (NF P31-204-1/A1:2001-09-01; NF P31-204-1/A2:2007-09-01) ● NF P31-207-1 - DTU 40-24. Building works. Roof covering made of interlocking concrete tiles. Part 1 : technical specifications + (NF P31-207-1/A1:1999-02-01 ; NF P31-207-1/A2:2001-06-01) ● NF P31-305 - Clay curved roofing tiles. 			
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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P31-313 - Roofing products. Concrete roofing tiles with longitudinal interlock, mountain class. Definition, characteristics , marking ● NF P32-201-1 - DTU 40-11. Building works. Roof covering made of slates. Part 1 : technical specifications. ● NF P39-201-1 -DTU 40-14. Building works. Roof covering made of asphalt shingles. Part 1 : technical specifications. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P31-313 - Roofing products. Concrete roofing tiles with longitudinal interlock, mountain class. Definition, characteristics , marking ● NF P32-201-1 - DTU 40-11. Building works. Roof covering made of slates. Part 1 : technical specifications. ● NF P39-201-1 -DTU 40-14. Building works. Roof covering made of asphalt shingles. Part 1 : technical specifications. 			
	water tightness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-302 - Characteristics of windows ● NF P20-505 - Windows and doors - Watertightness - Test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-302 - Characteristics of windows ● NF P20-505 - Windows and doors - Watertightness - Test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-302 - Characteristics of windows ● NF P20-505 - Windows and doors - Watertightness - Test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-302 - Characteristics of windows ● NF P20-505 - Windows and doors - Watertightness - Test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-302 - Characteristics of windows ● NF P20-505 - Windows and doors - Watertightness - Test method
	wind resistance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-302 - Characteristics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-302 - Characteristics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-302 - Characteristics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-302 - Characteristics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-302 - Characteristics

	and air tightness	<p>of windows</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-502- Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method ● NF P20-503 - Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method 	<p>of windows</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-502- Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method ● NF P20-503 - Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method 	<p>of windows</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-502- Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method ● NF P20-503 - Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method 	<p>of windows</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-502- Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method ● NF P20-503 - Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method 	<p>of windows</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-502- Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method ● NF P20-503 - Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method
	Cladding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3075 - Guideline of the CSTB about claddings in the façade 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3075 - Guideline of the CSTB about claddings in the façade 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3075 - Guideline of the CSTB about claddings in the façade 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3075 - Guideline of the CSTB about claddings in the façade 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3075 - Guideline of the CSTB about claddings in the façade
G	Terminology, physical properties,...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NFB 30 - 102 - Glass - Determination Of Softening Point - (litleton Point) ● NFB 30 - 104 - Glass - Determination of softening point. (litleton point) ● NFB 30 - 105 - Determination Of Annealing Point And Strain Point Of Glass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NFB 30 - 102 - Glass - Determination Of Softening Point - (litleton Point) ● NFB 30 - 104 - Glass - Determination of softening point. (litleton point) ● NFB 30 - 105 - Determination Of Annealing Point And Strain Point Of Glass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NFB 30 - 102 - Glass - Determination Of Softening Point - (litleton Point) ● NFB 30 - 104 - Glass - Determination of softening point. (litleton point) ● NFB 30 - 105 - Determination Of Annealing Point And Strain Point Of Glass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NFB 30 - 102 - Glass - Determination Of Softening Point - (litleton Point) ● NFB 30 - 104 - Glass - Determination of softening point. (litleton point) ● NFB 30 - 105 - Determination Of Annealing Point And Strain Point Of Glass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NFB 30 - 102 - Glass - Determination Of Softening Point - (litleton Point) ● NFB 30 - 104 - Glass - Determination of softening point. (litleton point) ● NFB 30 - 105 - Determination Of Annealing Point And Strain Point Of Glass

	types of glazing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF B32-002 - Drawn Sheet Glass - General ● NF B32-003 - Plate And Float Clear Glass - General ● NF B32-500 - Glass. Safety glasses for glazing, Generalities, Terminology ● NF P78-201 - Building works - Glazing and mirror glass works - Part 1-1 : contract bill of technical clauses - Part 1-2 : general criteria for selection of materials - Part 2 : contract bill of special clauses - Part 3 : calculation memorandum for thermal stress - Part 4 : memorandum for glass thickness calculation - Part 5 : safety memorandum. ● NF P78-301 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF B32-002 - Drawn Sheet Glass - General ● NF B32-003 - Plate And Float Clear Glass - General ● NF B32-500 - Glass. Safety glasses for glazing, Generalities, Terminology ● NF P78-201 - Building works - Glazing and mirror glass works - Part 1-1 : contract bill of technical clauses - Part 1-2 : general criteria for selection of materials - Part 2 : contract bill of special clauses - Part 3 : calculation memorandum for thermal stress - Part 4 : memorandum for glass thickness calculation - Part 5 : safety memorandum. ● NF P78-301 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF B32-002 - Drawn Sheet Glass - General ● NF B32-003 - Plate And Float Clear Glass - General ● NF B32-500 - Glass. Safety glasses for glazing, Generalities, Terminology ● NF P78-201 - Building works - Glazing and mirror glass works - Part 1-1 : contract bill of technical clauses - Part 1-2 : general criteria for selection of materials - Part 2 : contract bill of special clauses - Part 3 : calculation memorandum for thermal stress - Part 4 : memorandum for glass thickness calculation - Part 5 : safety memorandum. ● NF P78-301 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF B32-002 - Drawn Sheet Glass - General ● NF B32-003 - Plate And Float Clear Glass - General ● NF B32-500 - Glass. Safety glasses for glazing, Generalities, Terminology ● NF P78-201 - Building works - Glazing and mirror glass works - Part 1-1 : contract bill of technical clauses - Part 1-2 : general criteria for selection of materials - Part 2 : contract bill of special clauses - Part 3 : calculation memorandum for thermal stress - Part 4 : memorandum for glass thickness calculation - Part 5 : safety memorandum. ● NF P78-301 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF B32-002 - Drawn Sheet Glass - General ● NF B32-003 - Plate And Float Clear Glass - General ● NF B32-500 - Glass. Safety glasses for glazing, Generalities, Terminology ● NF P78-201 - Building works - Glazing and mirror glass works - Part 1-1 : contract bill of technical clauses - Part 1-2 : general criteria for selection of materials - Part 2 : contract bill of special clauses - Part 3 : calculation memorandum for thermal stress - Part 4 : memorandum for glass thickness calculation - Part 5 : safety memorandum. ● NF P78-301
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	- Glazing And Mirrors - Sheet Glass For Glazing For Buildings	- Glazing And Mirrors - Sheet Glass For Glazing For Buildings	- Glazing And Mirrors - Sheet Glass For Glazing For Buildings	- Glazing And Mirrors - Sheet Glass For Glazing For Buildings	- Glazing And Mirrors - Sheet Glass For Glazing For Buildings
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P78-453 - Glazing and mirrors - Insulating glazing. Determination method of greasy deposits on metal spacers ● NF P78-455 - Glazing and mirrors - Insulating glazing. Determination method of the stiffness coefficient kv and of the distortion ability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P78-453 - Glazing and mirrors - Insulating glazing. Determination method of greasy deposits on metal spacers ● NF P78-455 - Glazing and mirrors - Insulating glazing. Determination method of the stiffness coefficient kv and of the distortion ability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P78-453 - Glazing and mirrors - Insulating glazing. Determination method of greasy deposits on metal spacers ● NF P78-455 - Glazing and mirrors - Insulating glazing. Determination method of the stiffness coefficient kv and of the distortion ability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P78-453 - Glazing and mirrors - Insulating glazing. Determination method of greasy deposits on metal spacers ● NF P78-455 - Glazing and mirrors - Insulating glazing. Determination method of the stiffness coefficient kv and of the distortion ability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P78-453 - Glazing and mirrors - Insulating glazing. Determination method of greasy deposits on metal spacers ● NF P78-455 - Glazing and mirrors - Insulating glazing. Determination method of the stiffness coefficient kv and of the distortion ability
	<p><u>SSG:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3488 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about adhered façade-glazings 	<p><u>SSG:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3488 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about adhered façade-glazings 	<p><u>SSG:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3488 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about adhered façade-glazings 	<p><u>SSG:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3488 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about adhered façade-glazings 	<p><u>SSG:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3488 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about adhered façade-glazings
Sealing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P85-553 - Jointing products. Glazing materials and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P85-553 - Jointing products. Glazing materials and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P85-553 - Jointing products. Glazing materials and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P85-553 - Jointing products. Glazing materials and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P85-553 - Jointing products. Glazing materials and

		compounds for sealing. Sealants in preformed strips. Assessment of rheological stability	compounds for sealing. Sealants in preformed strips. Assessment of rheological stability	compounds for sealing. Sealants in preformed strips. Assessment of rheological stability	compounds for sealing. Sealants in preformed strips. Assessment of rheological stability	compounds for sealing. Sealants in preformed strips. Assessment of rheological stability
	General technical rules for usage of glazing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF DTU 39 - Building works - Glazing and mirror glass works - Part 1-1 : contract bill of technical clauses - Part 1-2 : general criteria for selection of materials - Part 2 : contract bill of special clauses - Part 3 : calculation memorandum for thermal stress - Part 4 : memorandum for glass thickness calculation - Part 5 : safety memorandum. ● CSTB-Cahier 3574 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about attached façade- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF DTU 39 - Building works - Glazing and mirror glass works - Part 1-1 : contract bill of technical clauses - Part 1-2 : general criteria for selection of materials - Part 2 : contract bill of special clauses - Part 3 : calculation memorandum for thermal stress - Part 4 : memorandum for glass thickness calculation - Part 5 : safety memorandum. ● CSTB-Cahier 3574 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about attached façade- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF DTU 39 - Building works - Glazing and mirror glass works - Part 1-1 : contract bill of technical clauses - Part 1-2 : general criteria for selection of materials - Part 2 : contract bill of special clauses - Part 3 : calculation memorandum for thermal stress - Part 4 : memorandum for glass thickness calculation - Part 5 : safety memorandum. ● CSTB-Cahier 3574 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about attached façade- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF DTU 39 - Building works - Glazing and mirror glass works - Part 1-1 : contract bill of technical clauses - Part 1-2 : general criteria for selection of materials - Part 2 : contract bill of special clauses - Part 3 : calculation memorandum for thermal stress - Part 4 : memorandum for glass thickness calculation - Part 5 : safety memorandum. ● CSTB-Cahier 3574 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about attached façade- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF DTU 39 - Building works - Glazing and mirror glass works - Part 1-1 : contract bill of technical clauses - Part 1-2 : general criteria for selection of materials - Part 2 : contract bill of special clauses - Part 3 : calculation memorandum for thermal stress - Part 4 : memorandum for glass thickness calculation - Part 5 : safety memorandum. ● CSTB-Cahier 3574 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about attached façade-

		glazings ● CSTB-Cahier 3488 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about adhered façade-glazings ● CSTB-Cahier 3242 - Guideline of the CSTB about climatic and temperature conditions of glazings	glazings ● CSTB-Cahier 3488 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about adhered façade-glazings ● CSTB-Cahier 3242 - Guideline of the CSTB about climatic and temperature conditions of glazings	glazings ● CSTB-Cahier 3488 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about adhered façade-glazings ● CSTB-Cahier 3242 - Guideline of the CSTB about climatic and temperature conditions of glazings	glazings ● CSTB-Cahier 3488 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about adhered façade-glazings ● CSTB-Cahier 3242 - Guideline of the CSTB about climatic and temperature conditions of glazings	glazings ● CSTB-Cahier 3488 V2 - Guideline of the CSTB about adhered façade-glazings ● CSTB-Cahier 3242 - Guideline of the CSTB about climatic and temperature conditions of glazings
	mechanical resistance and stability	● NFB 30 101 - Glass - Bend Test Of A Dual-glass Test Specimen ● NF P20-506 - Methods of testing windows. Mechanical tests	● NFB 30 101 - Glass - Bend Test Of A Dual-glass Test Specimen ● NF P20-506 - Methods of testing windows. Mechanical tests	● NFB 30 101 - Glass - Bend Test Of A Dual-glass Test Specimen ● NF P20-506 - Methods of testing windows. Mechanical tests	● NFB 30 101 - Glass - Bend Test Of A Dual-glass Test Specimen ● NF P20-506 - Methods of testing windows. Mechanical tests	● NFB 30 101 - Glass - Bend Test Of A Dual-glass Test Specimen ● NF P20-506 - Methods of testing windows. Mechanical tests
f u n c t i o n p e r f o r	noise protection	NF S31-050 - Acoustics. Measurement of the acoustic insulation of building and building components. Specifications relating to laboratories	NF S31-050 - Acoustics. Measurement of the acoustic insulation of building and building components. Specifications relating to laboratories	NF S31-050 - Acoustics. Measurement of the acoustic insulation of building and building components. Specifications relating to laboratories	NF S31-050 - Acoustics. Measurement of the acoustic insulation of building and building components. Specifications relating to laboratories	NF S31-050 - Acoustics. Measurement of the acoustic insulation of building and building components. Specifications relating to laboratories

m a n c e						
	insulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P75-101 - Thermal insulation for building purposes. Definition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P75-101 - Thermal insulation for building purposes. Definition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P75-101 - Thermal insulation for building purposes. Definition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P75-101 - Thermal insulation for building purposes. Definition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P75-101 - Thermal insulation for building purposes. Definition
	Energy economy and heat retention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3242 - Guideline of the CSTB about climatic and temperature conditions of glazings ● NF X10-022 - Determination in laboratory of thermal transmission coefficients of constitutive partition wall by method of hot guarded box ● Decree N° 2000-1153 from November 29, 2000; Defines thermal characteristics of new buildings and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3242 - Guideline of the CSTB about climatic and temperature conditions of glazings ● NF X10-022 - Determination in laboratory of thermal transmission coefficients of constitutive partition wall by method of hot guarded box ● Decree N° 2000-1153 from November 29, 2000; Defines thermal characteristics of new buildings and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3242 - Guideline of the CSTB about climatic and temperature conditions of glazings ● NF X10-022 - Determination in laboratory of thermal transmission coefficients of constitutive partition wall by method of hot guarded box ● Decree N° 2000-1153 from November 29, 2000; Defines thermal characteristics of new buildings and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3242 - Guideline of the CSTB about climatic and temperature conditions of glazings ● NF X10-022 - Determination in laboratory of thermal transmission coefficients of constitutive partition wall by method of hot guarded box ● Decree N° 2000-1153 from November 29, 2000; Defines thermal characteristics of new buildings and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSTB-Cahier 3242 - Guideline of the CSTB about climatic and temperature conditions of glazings ● NF X10-022 - Determination in laboratory of thermal transmission coefficients of constitutive partition wall by method of hot guarded box ● Decree N° 2000-1153 from November 29, 2000; Defines thermal characteristics of new buildings and

		new parts of buildings				
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5.4 Greek national standards

	<u>Category A</u> Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	<u>Category B</u> Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	<u>Category C</u> transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	<u>Category D</u> transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	<u>Category E</u> cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
safety	<p><u>In Greece exist no Standards or Guidelines about the construction of building-integrated-Photovoltaic.</u></p> <p>There are some different laws, which are related to this issue. They are mentioned in teh following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Law 3468/2006: ‘Generation of Electricity using Renewable Energy Sources and High-Efficiency Cogeneration of Electricity and Heat and Miscellaneous 	<p><u>In Greece exist no Standards or Guidelines about the construction of building-integrated-Photovoltaic.</u></p> <p>There are some different laws, which are related to this issue. They are mentioned in teh following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Law 3468/2006: ‘Generation of Electricity using Renewable Energy Sources and High-Efficiency 	<p><u>In Greece exist no Standards or Guidelines about the construction of building-integrated-Photovoltaic.</u></p> <p>There are some different laws, which are related to this issue. They are mentioned in teh following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Law 3468/2006: ‘Generation of Electricity using Renewable Energy Sources and High-Efficiency 	<p><u>In Greece exist no Standards or Guidelines about the construction of building-integrated-Photovoltaic.</u></p> <p>There are some different laws, which are related to this issue. They are mentioned in teh following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Law 3468/2006: ‘Generation of Electricity using Renewable Energy Sources and High-Efficiency 	<p><u>In Greece exist no Standards or Guidelines about the construction of building-integrated-Photovoltaic.</u></p> <p>There are some different laws, which are related to this issue. They are mentioned in teh following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Law 3468/2006: ‘Generation of Electricity using Renewable Energy Sources and High-Efficiency

	<p>Provisions”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Law 3734/2009: ‘Promotion of Cogeneration two or more useful forms of energy, regulation of issues related to the Hydroelectric Project Mesochora and other provisions” ● Law 3851/2010: ‘Concerning The Acceleration Of The Development Of Renewable Energy Sources” ● Law 4067/2012: ‘New Building Code” 	<p>Cogeneration of Electricity and Heat and Miscellaneous Provisions”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Law 3734/2009: ‘Promotion of Cogeneration two or more useful forms of energy, regulation of issues related to the Hydroelectric Project Mesochora and other provisions” ● Law 3851/2010: ‘Concerning The Acceleration Of The Development Of Renewable Energy Sources” ● Law 4067/2012: ‘New Building Code” 	<p>Cogeneration of Electricity and Heat and Miscellaneous Provisions”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Law 3734/2009: ‘Promotion of Cogeneration two or more useful forms of energy, regulation of issues related to the Hydroelectric Project Mesochora and other provisions” ● Law 3851/2010: ‘Concerning The Acceleration Of The Development Of Renewable Energy Sources” ● Law 4067/2012: ‘New Building Code” 	<p>Cogeneration of Electricity and Heat and Miscellaneous Provisions”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Law 3734/2009: ‘Promotion of Cogeneration two or more useful forms of energy, regulation of issues related to the Hydroelectric Project Mesochora and other provisions” ● Law 3851/2010: ‘Concerning The Acceleration Of The Development Of Renewable Energy Sources” ● Law 4067/2012: ‘New Building Code” 	<p>Cogeneration of Electricity and Heat and Miscellaneous Provisions”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Law 3734/2009: ‘Promotion of Cogeneration two or more useful forms of energy, regulation of issues related to the Hydroelectric Project Mesochora and other provisions” ● Law 3851/2010: ‘Concerning The Acceleration Of The Development Of Renewable Energy Sources” ● Law 4067/2012: ‘New Building Code”
	<p>These laws are extended by different ministerial decisions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ministerial decision 13717/4.6.2009: 	<p>These laws are extended by different ministerial decisions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ministerial decision 13717/4.6.2009: 	<p>These laws are extended by different ministerial decisions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ministerial decision 13717/4.6.2009: 	<p>These laws are extended by different ministerial decisions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ministerial decision 13717/4.6.2009: 	<p>These laws are extended by different ministerial decisions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ministerial decision 13717/4.6.2009:

	<p>‘Special Program of PV Systems Development in building facilities and especially in flat roofs’.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ministerial decision 36720/6.9.2010: ‘Approval of special terms for the installation of PV and solar systems in buildings and sites within urban planning areas and settlements’. ● Ministerial decision 40158/22.9.2010: ‘Approval of special terms for the installation of PV and solar systems in buildings and sites outside urban planning areas’. ● Ministerial decision 16934/10.8.2012: ‘Amendment of Special Program of PV Systems Development in building facilities 	<p>‘Special Program of PV Systems Development in building facilities and especially in flat roofs’.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ministerial decision 36720/6.9.2010: ‘Approval of special terms for the installation of PV and solar systems in buildings and sites within urban planning areas and settlements’. ● Ministerial decision 40158/22.9.2010: ‘Approval of special terms for the installation of PV and solar systems in buildings and sites outside urban planning areas’. ● Ministerial decision 16934/10.8.2012: ‘Amendment of Special Program of PV Systems Development in building facilities 	<p>‘Special Program of PV Systems Development in building facilities and especially in flat roofs’.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ministerial decision 36720/6.9.2010: ‘Approval of special terms for the installation of PV and solar systems in buildings and sites within urban planning areas and settlements’. ● Ministerial decision 40158/22.9.2010: ‘Approval of special terms for the installation of PV and solar systems in buildings and sites outside urban planning areas’. ● Ministerial decision 16934/10.8.2012: ‘Amendment of Special Program of PV Systems Development in building facilities 	<p>‘Special Program of PV Systems Development in building facilities and especially in flat roofs’.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ministerial decision 36720/6.9.2010: ‘Approval of special terms for the installation of PV and solar systems in buildings and sites within urban planning areas and settlements’. ● Ministerial decision 40158/22.9.2010: ‘Approval of special terms for the installation of PV and solar systems in buildings and sites outside urban planning areas’. ● Ministerial decision 16934/10.8.2012: ‘Amendment of Special Program of PV Systems Development in building facilities 	<p>‘Special Program of PV Systems Development in building facilities and especially in flat roofs’.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ministerial decision 36720/6.9.2010: ‘Approval of special terms for the installation of PV and solar systems in buildings and sites within urban planning areas and settlements’. ● Ministerial decision 40158/22.9.2010: ‘Approval of special terms for the installation of PV and solar systems in buildings and sites outside urban planning areas’. ● Ministerial decision 16934/10.8.2012: ‘Amendment of Special Program of PV Systems Development in building facilities
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	and especially in flat roofs".				
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5.5 Swiss national standards

		Category A Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	Category B Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	Category C transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	Category D transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	Category E cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
s a f e t y	electrical safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● STI 233.0710 - Solar Photovoltaic - Power supply systems ● 219.0201 - Parallel operation of power plants in the low voltage system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● STI 233.0710 - Solar Photovoltaic - Power supply systems ● 219.0201 - Parallel operation of power plants in the low voltage system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● STI 233.0710 - Solar Photovoltaic - Power supply systems ● 219.0201 - Parallel operation of power plants in the low voltage system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● STI 233.0710 - Solar Photovoltaic - Power supply systems ● 219.0201 - Parallel operation of power plants in the low voltage system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● STI 233.0710 - Solar Photovoltaic - Power supply systems ● 219.0201 - Parallel operation of power plants in the low voltage system
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 380-4 / SN 520380-4 - Electrical energy in buildings ● SR 734.31 - Ordinance on electrical cable ● SR 734.25 - Ordinance on the approval procedure of electrical installations ● SR 734.26 - Ordinance on electrical low voltage (NEV) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 380-4 / SN 520380-4 - Electrical energy in buildings ● SR 734.31 - Ordinance on electrical cable ● SR 734.25 - Ordinance on the approval procedure of electrical installations ● SR 734.26 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 380-4 / SN 520380-4 - Electrical energy in buildings ● SR 734.31 - Ordinance on electrical cable ● SR 734.25 - Ordinance on the approval procedure of electrical installations ● SR 734.26 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 380-4 / SN 520380-4 - Electrical energy in buildings ● SR 734.31 - Ordinance on electrical cable ● SR 734.25 - Ordinance on the approval procedure of electrical installations ● SR 734.26 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 380-4 / SN 520380-4 - Electrical energy in buildings ● SR 734.31 - Ordinance on electrical cable ● SR 734.25 - Ordinance on the approval procedure of electrical installations ● SR 734.26 -

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SR 734.27 - Ordinance on electrical low voltage (NIV) ● SEV 1000:2010, chapter 7.12 / STI 233.1104 - Standard for low voltage installations (NIBT) 	<p>Ordinance on electrical low voltage (NEV)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SR 734.27 - Ordinance on electrical low voltage (NIV) ● SEV 1000:2010, chapter 7.12 / STI 233.1104 - Standard for low voltage installations (NIBT) 	<p>Ordinance on electrical low voltage (NEV)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SR 734.27 - Ordinance on electrical low voltage (NIV) ● SEV 1000:2010, chapter 7.12 / STI 233.1104 - Standard for low voltage installations (NIBT) 	<p>Ordinance on electrical low voltage (NEV)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SR 734.27 - Ordinance on electrical low voltage (NIV) ● SEV 1000:2010, chapter 7.12 / STI 233.1104 - Standard for low voltage installations (NIBT) 	<p>Ordinance on electrical low voltage (NEV)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SR 734.27 - Ordinance on electrical low voltage (NIV) ● SEV 1000:2010, chapter 7.12 / STI 233.1104 - Standard for low voltage installations (NIBT)
Lightning protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SEV 4022:2008 - Principles on the systems of lightning protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SEV 4022:2008 - Principles on the systems of lightning protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SEV 4022:2008 - Principles on the systems of lightning protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SEV 4022:2008 - Principles on the systems of lightning protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SEV 4022:2008 - Principles on the systems of lightning protection
safety in case of fire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● VKF 13-15 - fire safety guideline(: classification of building materials and building elements ● VKF 14-15 - fire safety guideline: building materials ● VKF 13-03 - fire safety guideline: combustible building materials ● VKF 20003- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● VKF 13-15 - fire safety guideline(: classification of building materials and building elements ● VKF 14-15 - fire safety guideline: building materials ● VKF 13-03 - fire safety guideline: combustible building materials ● VKF 20003- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● VKF 13-15 - fire safety guideline(: classification of building materials and building elements ● VKF 14-15 - fire safety guideline: building materials ● VKF 13-03 - fire safety guideline: combustible building materials ● VKF 20003- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● VKF 13-15 - fire safety guideline(: classification of building materials and building elements ● VKF 14-15 - fire safety guideline: building materials ● VKF 13-03 - fire safety guideline: combustible building materials ● VKF 20003- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● VKF 13-15 - fire safety guideline(: classification of building materials and building elements ● VKF 14-15 - fire safety guideline: building materials ● VKF 13-03 - fire safety guideline: combustible building materials ● VKF 20003-

		12:2012 - fire safety - solar collector ● Suissolar STP 22001 - state-of-technology-information sheet - Solaranlagen	12:2012 - fire safety - solar collector ● Suissolar STP 22001 - state-of-technology-information sheet - Solaranlagen	12:2012 - fire safety - solar collector ● Suissolar STP 22001 - state-of-technology-information sheet - Solaranlagen	12:2012 - fire safety - solar collector ● Suissolar STP 22001 - state-of-technology-information sheet - Solaranlagen	12:2012 - fire safety - solar collector ● Suissolar STP 22001 - state-of-technology-information sheet - Solaranlagen
	safety in use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SN 505261 - Actions on Structures ● SN 505263 - Steel structures ● SIA 331 / SN 56331 - Windows and glazed doors ● SIA 462 / SN505462 - Evaluation of the structural safety ● SIA 465 / SN 580465 - Safety in construction and installations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SN 505261 - Actions on Structures ● SN 505263 - Steel structures ● SIA 331 / SN 56331 - Windows and glazed doors ● SIA 462 / SN505462 - Evaluation of the structural safety ● SIA 465 / SN 580465 - Safety in construction and installations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SN 505261 - Actions on Structures ● SN 505263 - Steel structures ● SIA 331 / SN 56331 - Windows and glazed doors ● SIA 462 / SN505462 - Evaluation of the structural safety ● SIA 465 / SN 580465 - Safety in construction and installations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SN 505261 - Actions on Structures ● SN 505263 - Steel structures ● SIA 331 / SN 56331 - Windows and glazed doors ● SIA 462 / SN505462 - Evaluation of the structural safety ● SIA 465 / SN 580465 - Safety in construction and installations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SN 505261 - Actions on Structures ● SN 505263 - Steel structures ● SIA 331 / SN 56331 - Windows and glazed doors ● SIA 462 / SN505462 - Evaluation of the structural safety ● SIA 465 / SN 580465 - Safety in construction and installations
						<u>Constructive requirements for ventilated façades:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SN 564232-2 / SIA 232-2 - ventilated façades ● SN 520329 - curtain walls

	water tightness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA V280/ SN 564280 - (Redommenda tion, not standard) - Tests and requirements for membrane and synthetic sealing (polymer-sealings) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA V280/ SN 564280 - (Redommenda tion, not standard) - Tests and requirements for membrane and synthetic sealing (polymer-sealings) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA V280/ SN 564280 - (Redommenda tion, not standard) - Tests and requirements for membrane and synthetic sealing (polymer-sealings) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA V280/ SN 564280 - (Redommenda tion, not standard) - Tests and requirements for membrane and synthetic sealing (polymer-sealings) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA V280/ SN 564280 - (Redommenda tion, not standard) - Tests and requirements for membrane and synthetic sealing (polymer-sealings)
	seismic actions and rules for buildings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●SIA 2018 - Inspection of the Para seismic safety of existing buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●SIA 2018 - Inspection of the Para seismic safety of existing buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●SIA 2018 - Inspection of the Para seismic safety of existing buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●SIA 2018 - Inspection of the Para seismic safety of existing buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●SIA 2018 - Inspection of the Para seismic safety of existing buildings
	function / performance noise protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 181 / SN 520181 - Protection against noise in buildings ● SIA 331 / SN 563331 - Windows (Protection against noise of PV-glasses) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 181 / SN 520181 - Protection against noise in buildings ● SIA 331 / SN 563331 - Windows (Protection against noise of PV-glasses) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 181 / SN 520181 - Protection against noise in buildings ● SIA 331 / SN 563331 - Windows (Protection against noise of PV-glasses) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 181 / SN 520181 - Protection against noise in buildings ● SIA 331 / SN 563331 - Windows (Protection against noise of PV-glasses) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 181 / SN 520181 - Protection against noise in buildings ● SIA 331 / SN 563331 - Windows (Protection against noise of PV-glasses)
	insulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 331 / SN 56331 - Windows (thermal insulation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 331 / SN 56331 - Windows (thermal insulation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 331 / SN 56331 - Windows (thermal insulation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 331 / SN 56331 - Windows (thermal insulation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 331 / SN 56331 - Windows (thermal insulation)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 180 / SN 520180 - Thermal insulation and protection against humidity in buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 180 / SN 520180 - Thermal insulation and protection against humidity in buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 180 / SN 520180 - Thermal insulation and protection against humidity in buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 180 / SN 520180 - Thermal insulation and protection against humidity in buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 180 / SN 520180 - Thermal insulation and protection against humidity in buildings
	Energy economy and heat retention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 380-1 / SN 520380-1 - Thermal energy in buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 380-1 / SN 520380-1 - Thermal energy in buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 380-1 / SN 520380-1 - Thermal energy in buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 380-1 / SN 520380-1 - Thermal energy in buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 380-1 / SN 520380-1 - Thermal energy in buildings
EPD (environmental product declaration)	EPD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 112-1 - sustainable building (Recommendation, not standard) ● SR 814.01 - Federal law on the protection of the environment ● SR 451 - Law on the protection of nature and landscape ● SR 933.0 - Federal law on building products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 112-1 - sustainable building (Recommendation, not standard) ● SR 814.01 - Federal law on the protection of the environment ● SR 451 - Law on the protection of nature and landscape ● SR 933.0 - Federal law on building products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 112-1 - sustainable building (Recommendation, not standard) ● SR 814.01 - Federal law on the protection of the environment ● SR 451 - Law on the protection of nature and landscape ● SR 933.0 - Federal law on building products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 112-1 - sustainable building (Recommendation, not standard) ● SR 814.01 - Federal law on the protection of the environment ● SR 451 - Law on the protection of nature and landscape ● SR 933.0 - Federal law on building products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA 112-1 - sustainable building (Recommendation, not standard) ● SR 814.01 - Federal law on the protection of the environment ● SR 451 - Law on the protection of nature and landscape ● SR 933.0 - Federal law on building products

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f e a s i b i l i t y	<p>construction process conformity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SR 832.311.141 - Ordinance on safety and health in the workplace for construction work • SUVA-Safety charta 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SR 832.311.141 - Ordinance on safety and health in the workplace for construction work • SUVA-Safety charta 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SR 832.311.141 - Ordinance on safety and health in the workplace for construction work • SUVA-Safety charta 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SR 832.311.141 - Ordinance on safety and health in the workplace for construction work • SUVA-Safety charta 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SR 832.311.141 - Ordinance on safety and health in the workplace for construction work • SUVA-Safety charta

5.6 Italian national standards

		<u>Category A</u> Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	<u>Category B</u> Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	<u>Category C</u> transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	<u>Category D</u> transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	<u>Category E</u> cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
s a f e t y	electrical safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 82-25 - Guide to the realization of photovoltaic power generation systems connected to the electric network of medium and low voltage ● CEI 0-2 - Guide for the definition of project documentation for electrical installations ● CEI 64-8 - Electrical systems using a nominal voltage not exceeding 1000 V ac and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 82-25 - Guide to the realization of photovoltaic power generation systems connected to the electric network of medium and low voltage ● CEI 0-2 - Guide for the definition of project documentation for electrical installations ● CEI 64-8 - Electrical systems using a nominal voltage not exceeding 1000 V ac and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 82-25 - Guide to the realization of photovoltaic power generation systems connected to the electric network of medium and low voltage ● CEI 0-2 - Guide for the definition of project documentation for electrical installations ● CEI 64-8 - Electrical systems using a nominal voltage not exceeding 1000 V ac and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 82-25 - Guide to the realization of photovoltaic power generation systems connected to the electric network of medium and low voltage ● CEI 0-2 - Guide for the definition of project documentation for electrical installations ● CEI 64-8 - Electrical systems using a nominal voltage not exceeding 1000 V ac and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 82-25 - Guide to the realization of photovoltaic power generation systems connected to the electric network of medium and low voltage ● CEI 0-2 - Guide for the definition of project documentation for electrical installations ● CEI 64-8 - Electrical systems using a nominal voltage not exceeding 1000 V ac and

	<p>1500 V dc</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 13-4 - Measurement systems in electricity - Composition, accuracy and verification ● CEI 20-19 - Rubber insulated cables with a rated voltage not exceeding 450/750 V ● CEI 20-20 - PVC insulated cables with a rated voltage not exceeding 450/750 V 	<p>1500 V dc</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 13-4 - Measurement systems in electricity - Composition, accuracy and verification ● CEI 20-19 - Rubber insulated cables with a rated voltage not exceeding 450/750 V ● CEI 20-20 - PVC insulated cables with a rated voltage not exceeding 450/750 V 	<p>1500 V dc</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 13-4 - Measurement systems in electricity - Composition, accuracy and verification ● CEI 20-19 - Rubber insulated cables with a rated voltage not exceeding 450/750 V ● CEI 20-20 - PVC insulated cables with a rated voltage not exceeding 450/750 V 	<p>1500 V dc</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 13-4 - Measurement systems in electricity - Composition, accuracy and verification ● CEI 20-19 - Rubber insulated cables with a rated voltage not exceeding 450/750 V ● CEI 20-20 - PVC insulated cables with a rated voltage not exceeding 450/750 V 	<p>1500 V dc</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 13-4 - Measurement systems in electricity - Composition, accuracy and verification ● CEI 20-19 - Rubber insulated cables with a rated voltage not exceeding 450/750 V ● CEI 20-20 - PVC insulated cables with a rated voltage not exceeding 450/750 V
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 20-91 - Electric cables insulated and sheathed with halogen-free elastomeric, flame retarded with a rated voltage not exceeding 1000 V ac and 1500 V dc for photovoltaic applications ● CEI 0-19 - Reference technical rules for connecting connecting active and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 20-91 - Electric cables insulated and sheathed with halogen-free elastomeric, flame retarded with a rated voltage not exceeding 1000 V ac and 1500 V dc for photovoltaic applications ● CEI 0-19 - Reference technical rules for connecting connecting active and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 20-91 - Electric cables insulated and sheathed with halogen-free elastomeric, flame retarded with a rated voltage not exceeding 1000 V ac and 1500 V dc for photovoltaic applications ● CEI 0-19 - Reference technical rules for connecting connecting active and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 20-91 - Electric cables insulated and sheathed with halogen-free elastomeric, flame retarded with a rated voltage not exceeding 1000 V ac and 1500 V dc for photovoltaic applications ● CEI 0-19 - Reference technical rules for connecting connecting active and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CEI 20-91 - Electric cables insulated and sheathed with halogen-free elastomeric, flame retarded with a rated voltage not exceeding 1000 V ac and 1500 V dc for photovoltaic applications ● CEI 0-19 - Reference technical rules for connecting connecting active and

		passive users to HV and MV electricity distribution companies ● ● CEI 0-21: Reference technical rules for connecting active and passive users BT networks of electricity distribution companies	passive users to HV and MV electricity distribution companies ● ● CEI 0-21: Reference technical rules for connecting active and passive users BT networks of electricity distribution companies	passive users to HV and MV electricity distribution companies ● ● CEI 0-21: Reference technical rules for connecting active and passive users BT networks of electricity distribution companies	passive users to HV and MV electricity distribution companies ● ● CEI 0-21: Reference technical rules for connecting active and passive users BT networks of electricity distribution companies	passive users to HV and MV electricity distribution companies ● ● CEI 0-21: Reference technical rules for connecting active and passive users BT networks of electricity distribution companies
	Lightning protection	● CEI 81-3 - Mean values of the number of lightning strikes per year and square kilometer	● CEI 81-3 - Mean values of the number of lightning strikes per year and square kilometer	● CEI 81-3 - Mean values of the number of lightning strikes per year and square kilometer	● CEI 81-3 - Mean values of the number of lightning strikes per year and square kilometer	● CEI 81-3 - Mean values of the number of lightning strikes per year and square kilometer
	safety in case of fire	● UNI 8457 - EN- Combustible products which can be hit by flame on one surface - Reaction to fire by applying a small flame	● UNI 8457 - EN- Combustible products which can be hit by flame on one surface - Reaction to fire by applying a small flame	● UNI 8457 - EN- Combustible products which can be hit by flame on one surface - Reaction to fire by applying a small flame	● UNI 8457 - EN- Combustible products which can be hit by flame on one surface - Reaction to fire by applying a small flame	● UNI 8457 - EN- Combustible products which can be hit by flame on one surface - Reaction to fire by applying a small flame
	safety in use	● Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni (2008) ● UNI 8088 - Works	● Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni (2008) ● UNI 8088 - Works	● Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni (2008) ● UNI 8088 - Works	● Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni (2008) ● UNI 8088 - Works	● Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni (2008) ● UNI 8088 - Works

	concerning buildings roofings- Safety criteria	concerning buildings roofings- Safety criteria	concerning buildings roofings- Safety criteria	concerning buildings roofings- Safety criteria	concerning buildings roofings- Safety criteria
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UNI 8089- Building - Roofing and related functional components - Terminology related to functional performance ● UNI 8178- Building - Roofings - Analysis of functional components ● UNI 8625-1 + A1 -Building. Tests of discontinuous roofing. Determination of water permeability. ● UNI 8635-14 - Building. Tests of products for discontinuous roofing. Determination of mechanical resistance of fastener elements. ● UNI 8635-15 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UNI 8089- Building - Roofing and related functional components - Terminology related to functional performance ● UNI 8178- Building - Roofings - Analysis of functional components ● UNI 8625-1 + A1 -Building. Tests of discontinuous roofing. Determination of water permeability. ● UNI 8635-14 - Building. Tests of products for discontinuous roofing. Determination of mechanical resistance of fastener elements. ● UNI 8635-15 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UNI 8369-1 - Building- External vertical wall- Classification and terminology. ● UNI 8369-2 - Building- External vertical walls- Classification and terminology ● UNI 8369-4 - Building - External vertical wall - Classification and terminology of shutters and sun screens. ● UNI 8369 - 5 - Building - External vertical wall. Joint between wall and window- Terminology and symbols for dimensioning. ● UNI 8979- Building - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UNI 8369-1 - Building- External vertical wall- Classification and terminology. ● UNI 8369-2 - Building- External vertical walls- Classification and terminology ● UNI 8369-4 - Building - External vertical wall - Classification and terminology of shutters and sun screens. ● UNI 8369 - 5 - Building - External vertical wall. Joint between wall and window- Terminology and symbols for dimensioning. ● UNI 8979- Building - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UNI 8369-1 - Building- External vertical wall- Classification and terminology. ● UNI 8369-2 - Building- External vertical walls- Classification and terminology ● UNI 8369-4 - Building - External vertical wall - Classification and terminology of shutters and sun screens. ● UNI 8369 - 5 - Building - External vertical wall. Joint between wall and window- Terminology and symbols for dimensioning. ● UNI 8979- Building -

		- Building. Tests of products for discontinuous roofing. Determination of number for area unit and areic mass.	- Building. Tests of products for discontinuous roofing. Determination of number for area unit and areic mass.	External vertical walls- Analysis of functional components.	External vertical walls- Analysis of functional components.	External vertical walls- Analysis of functional components.
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UNI 8635-16 - Building. Tests of products for discontinuous roofing. Determination of alkali enclosure in fine clay products. ● UNI 9308-1 - Discontinuous roofing. Design criteria. Water-proofing element. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UNI 8635-16 - Building. Tests of products for discontinuous roofing. Determination of alkali enclosure in fine clay products. ● UNI 9308-1 - Discontinuous roofing. Design criteria. Water-proofing element. 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UNI 11018 - Cladding and anchoring systems for back ventilated external enclosures of buildings - Instructions for the design, installation and maintenance - Ceramic and stone cladding
	slate, shingles and roofing tiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UNI 9460 - Discontinuousl y laid roof coverings - Criteria for design, execution and maintenance of roofing made either of clay or concrete roofing tiles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UNI 9460 - Discontinuousl y laid roof coverings - Criteria for design, execution and maintenance of roofing made either of clay or concrete roofing tiles 			

G l a s s	Terminology, physical properties, ...	● UNI 7697 - Safety criteria for glazing applications	● UNI 7697 - Safety criteria for glazing applications	● UNI 7697 - Safety criteria for glazing applications	● UNI 7697 - Safety criteria for glazing applications	● UNI 7697 - Safety criteria for glazing applications
	General technical rules for usage of glazing	● UNI 6534 - Glazing and fixing of glass for buildings. Design, materials and laying.	● UNI 6534 - Glazing and fixing of glass for buildings. Design, materials and laying.	● UNI 6534 - Glazing and fixing of glass for buildings. Design, materials and laying.	● UNI 6534 - Glazing and fixing of glass for buildings. Design, materials and laying.	● UNI 6534 - Glazing and fixing of glass for buildings. Design, materials and laying.
	mechanical resistance and stability	● Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni (2008) ● UNI ISO 7892 - Vertical building elements. Impact resistance test. Impact bodies and general test procedures.	● Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni (2008) ● UNI ISO 7892 - Vertical building elements. Impact resistance test. Impact bodies and general test procedures.	● Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni (2008) ● UNI ISO 7892 - Vertical building elements. Impact resistance test. Impact bodies and general test procedures.	● Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni (2008) ● UNI ISO 7892 - Vertical building elements. Impact resistance test. Impact bodies and general test procedures.	● Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni (2008) ● UNI ISO 7892 - Vertical building elements. Impact resistance test. Impact bodies and general test procedures.
	seismic actions and rules for buildings	● Norme Tecniche per le Costruzioni (2008)				
	Hygiene/toxicity	Analysis of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon trace in water from the roof	Analysis of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon trace in water from the roof			
f u n c t	Energy economy and heat retention	● UNI/TR 11328-1 - Solar energy - calculation of	● UNI/TR 11328-1 - Solar energy - calculation of	● UNI/TR 11328-1 - Solar energy - calculation of	● UNI/TR 11328-1 - Solar energy - calculation of	● UNI/TR 11328-1 - Solar energy - calculation of

i o n / p e r f o r m a n c e		contirbutions for building applications - Part 1: Evaluation of radiant energy received ●UNI 10349 - Heating and cooling of buildings - climatic data	contirbutions for building applications - Part 1: Evaluation of radiant energy received ●UNI 10349 - Heating and cooling of buildings - climatic data	contirbutions for building applications - Part 1: Evaluation of radiant energy received ●UNI 10349 - Heating and cooling of buildings - climatic data	contirbutions for building applications - Part 1: Evaluation of radiant energy received ●UNI 10349 - Heating and cooling of buildings - climatic data	contirbutions for building applications - Part 1: Evaluation of radiant energy received ●UNI 10349 - Heating and cooling of buildings - climatic data
e c o n o m i	sufficiently big market for industrialization	PV module has to be also a waterproofing element for roofing	PV module has to be also a waterproofing element for roofing			
i c r e q u i r e m e n t s	profitable product	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption	It depends on several points of the module: direction, efficiency of the cells, solar radiation, shadow, angle installation, buyback price (yes in GER). Costumer must have economic advantages. Important is the determination of usage: own consumption or public consumption

		as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is needed	as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is needed	as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is needed	as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is needed	as eg. office buildings -> they often have a peak load from 8am till 6 pm, where more power is needed
		decreased cost of installation EVALUATION OF A BATTERY SYSTEM TO COLLECT POWER AND USE IN THE EVENING NIGHT TIME	decreased cost of installation EVALUATION OF A BATTERY SYSTEM TO COLLECT POWER AND USE IN THE EVENING NIGHT TIME	decreased cost of installation EVALUATION OF A BATTERY SYSTEM TO COLLECT POWER AND USE IN THE EVENING NIGHT TIME	decreased cost of installation EVALUATION OF A BATTERY SYSTEM TO COLLECT POWER AND USE IN THE EVENING NIGHT TIME	decreased cost of installation EVALUATION OF A BATTERY SYSTEM TO COLLECT POWER AND USE IN THE EVENING NIGHT TIME
	low risk product	low risk and walkability				
	creditworthy/bankable product	5-10 years				
E P D (e n v i r o n m e n t a l p r	EPD	ISO 14025 Definitely, the data required by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials	ISO 14025 Definitely, the data required by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials	ISO 14025 Definitely, the data required by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials	ISO 14025 Definitely, the data required by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials	ISO 14025 Definitely, the data required by the EPD (Environmental Product Declaration scheme) is to be provided. This contains e.g. LCI= Life Cycle Inventory Analysis / bill of materials

o d u c t d e c l a r a t i o n)		and optionally LCIA= Life Cycle Impact Assessment.				
f e a s i b i l i t y	constructi on process conformit y	possibility to replace/reuse/ recycle individual panels in case of future requirements (example aesthetic changes, rennovation, partial damage etc.)				
s o c i a l c r i t e r i a	to gain recognitio n	correspondingl y the roof could be also a 'recognizable characteristic' for a building	correspondingl y the roof could be also a 'recognizable characteristic' for a building			
	compliance with ethic goals	The roof have to fulfill goals in CO2 saving, sustainability and renewability	The roof have to fulfill goals in CO2 saving, sustainability and renewability			

		BUT first of all must be WATEPROOFI NG	BUT first of all must be WATEPROOFI NG			
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5.7 Spanish national standards

		<u>Category A</u> Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	<u>Category B</u> Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	<u>Category C</u> transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	<u>Category D</u> transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	<u>Category E</u> cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
s a f e t y	safety in case of fire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention ● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention ● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention ● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention ● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention ● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic

		document SI: Safety in case of fire				
	safety in use	<p>●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HS: Health regulation + Basic document SUA: Safety in use and accessibility</p>	<p>●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HS: Health regulation + Basic document SUA: Safety in use and accessibility</p>	<p>●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HS: Health regulation + Basic document SUA: Safety in use and accessibility</p>	<p>●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HS: Health regulation + Basic document SUA: Safety in use and accessibility</p>	<p>●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HS: Health regulation + Basic document SUA: Safety in use and accessibility</p>
	mechanic al resistance	<p>●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-</p>				

	and stability	CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention ● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document SE: Structural safety	CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention ● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document SE: Structural safety	CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention ● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document SE: Structural safety	CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention ● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document SE: Structural safety	CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention ● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document SE: Structural safety
f u n c t i o n / p e r f o r m a n	noise protection	●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection	●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection	●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection	●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection	●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection

c e		<p>against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HR: Protection against noise</p>	<p>against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HR: Protection against noise</p>	<p>against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HR: Protection against noise</p>	<p>against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HR: Protection against noise</p>	<p>against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HR: Protection against noise</p>
	<p>Energy economy and heat retention</p>	<p>●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HE:</p>	<p>●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HE:</p>	<p>●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HE:</p>	<p>●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HE:</p>	<p>●Construction products directive (89/106/CEE-CPD) - Requirements for mechanical resistance and stability; safety in case of fire; hygiene, health and environment; safety in use; protection against noise and energy economy and heat retention</p> <p>● Código técnico de la edificación - Technical Building Code (TBC) - Basic document HE:</p>

		Energy economy	Energy economy	Energy economy	Energy economy	Energy economy
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5.8 Dutch national standards

		Category A Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	Category B Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	Category C transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	Category D transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	Category E cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
s a f e t y	electrical safety	<p><u>Photovoltaic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 7250 - Solar energy systems - Integration in roofs and façades - Building aspects ● NTA 8011 - Safety requirements for low-voltage installations - Solar photovoltaic (PV) power supply systems ● NTA 8013 - Procedure for checking PV-systems 	<p><u>Photovoltaic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 7250 - Solar energy systems - Integration in roofs and façades - Building aspects ● NTA 8011 - Safety requirements for low-voltage installations - Solar photovoltaic (PV) power supply systems ● NTA 8013 - Procedure for checking PV-systems 	<p><u>Photovoltaic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 7250 - Solar energy systems - Integration in roofs and façades - Building aspects ● NTA 8011 - Safety requirements for low-voltage installations - Solar photovoltaic (PV) power supply systems ● NTA 8013 - Procedure for checking PV-systems 	<p><u>Photovoltaic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 7250 - Solar energy systems - Integration in roofs and façades - Building aspects ● NTA 8011 - Safety requirements for low-voltage installations - Solar photovoltaic (PV) power supply systems ● NTA 8013 - Procedure for checking PV-systems 	<p><u>Photovoltaic:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 7250 - Solar energy systems - Integration in roofs and façades - Building aspects ● NTA 8011 - Safety requirements for low-voltage installations - Solar photovoltaic (PV) power supply systems ● NTA 8013 - Procedure for checking PV-systems

		<u>Electical Standard:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 1010+C1 - Safety requirements for low-voltage installations 	<u>Electical Standard:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 1010+C1 - Safety requirements for low-voltage installations 	<u>Electical Standard:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 1010+C1 - Safety requirements for low-voltage installations 	<u>Electical Standard:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 1010+C1 - Safety requirements for low-voltage installations 	<u>Electical Standard:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 1010+C1 - Safety requirements for low-voltage installations
	Lightning protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NPR 1014 - Protection against lightning - Guidance to the NEN-EN-IEC 62305 series 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NPR 1014 - Protection against lightning - Guidance to the NEN-EN-IEC 62305 series 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NPR 1014 - Protection against lightning - Guidance to the NEN-EN-IEC 62305 series 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NPR 1014 - Protection against lightning - Guidance to the NEN-EN-IEC 62305 series 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NPR 1014 - Protection against lightning - Guidance to the NEN-EN-IEC 62305 series
	safety in case of fire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6063 - Test method for external fire exposure to roofs ● NEN 6064 - Determination of the non-combustibility of a building product ● NEN 6065+A1 - Determination of the contribution to fire propagation of building products ● NEN 6066 - Determination of the smoke production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6063 - Test method for external fire exposure to roofs ● NEN 6064 - Determination of the non-combustibility of a building product ● NEN 6065+A1 - Determination of the contribution to fire propagation of building products ● NEN 6066 - Determination of the smoke production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6064 - Determination of the non-combustibility of a building product ● NEN 6065+A1 - Determination of the contribution to fire propagation of building products ● NEN 6066 - Determination of the smoke production during fire of building products ● NEN 6068+C1 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6064 - Determination of the non-combustibility of a building product ● NEN 6065+A1 - Determination of the contribution to fire propagation of building products ● NEN 6066 - Determination of the smoke production during fire of building products ● NEN 6068+C1 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6064 - Determination of the non-combustibility of a building product ● NEN 6065+A1 - Determination of the contribution to fire propagation of building products ● NEN 6066 - Determination of the smoke production during fire of building products ● NEN 6068+C1 -

	<p>during fire of building products</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6068+C1 - Determination of the resistance to fire movement between spaces ● NEN 6069 - Testing and classification of resistance to fire of building products and building elements 	<p>during fire of building products</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6068+C1 - Determination of the resistance to fire movement between spaces ● NEN 6069 - Testing and classification of resistance to fire of building products and building elements 	<p>Determination of the resistance to fire movement between spaces</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6069 - Testing and classification of resistance to fire of building products and building elements 	<p>Determination of the resistance to fire movement between spaces</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6069 - Testing and classification of resistance to fire of building products and building elements 	<p>Determination of the resistance to fire movement between spaces</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6069 - Testing and classification of resistance to fire of building products and building elements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NTA 8012 - Limitation of the damage due to fire of electrical wiring systems or flame spread along electrical wiring systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NTA 8012 - Limitation of the damage due to fire of electrical wiring systems or flame spread along electrical wiring systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NTA 8012 - Limitation of the damage due to fire of electrical wiring systems or flame spread along electrical wiring systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NTA 8012 - Limitation of the damage due to fire of electrical wiring systems or flame spread along electrical wiring systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NTA 8012 - Limitation of the damage due to fire of electrical wiring systems or flame spread along electrical wiring systems
safety in use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Bouwbesluit - Building code - safety, health, usability, energy conservation and environment ● NEN 3569 - Glass in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Bouwbesluit - Building code - safety, health, usability, energy conservation and environment ● NEN 3569 - Glass in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Bouwbesluit - Building code - safety, health, usability, energy conservation and environment ● NEN 3569 - Glass in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Bouwbesluit - Building code - safety, health, usability, energy conservation and environment ● NEN 3569 - Glass in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Bouwbesluit - Building code - safety, health, usability, energy conservation and environment ● NEN 3569 - Glass in

		building - Limiting the risk of physical injury by breaking and falling glass - Requirements	building - Limiting the risk of physical injury by breaking and falling glass - Requirements	building - Limiting the risk of physical injury by breaking and falling glass - Requirements	building - Limiting the risk of physical injury by breaking and falling glass - Requirements	building - Limiting the risk of physical injury by breaking and falling glass - Requirements
	slate, shingles and roofing tiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6707 - Fixing of roof coverings - Requirements and determination methods ● NPR 6708 - Fixing of roof coverings - Code of Practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6707 - Fixing of roof coverings - Requirements and determination methods ● NPR 6708 - Fixing of roof coverings - Code of Practice 			
	water tightness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 2778+A4 - Moisture control in buildings - Determination methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 2778+A4 - Moisture control in buildings - Determination methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 2778+A4 - Moisture control in buildings - Determination methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 2778+A4 - Moisture control in buildings - Determination methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 2778+A4 - Moisture control in buildings - Determination methods
	wind resistance and air tightness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 2686 + A2- Air leakage of buildings - Method of measurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 2686 + A2- Air leakage of buildings - Method of measurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 2686 + A2- Air leakage of buildings - Method of measurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 2686 + A2- Air leakage of buildings - Method of measurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 2686 + A2- Air leakage of buildings - Method of measurement
G	Terminolo gy, physical propertie s	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●NEN 2608:2011+C1 - Glass in building - Requirements and determination method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●NEN 2608:2011+C1 - Glass in building - Requirements and determination method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●NEN 2608:2011+C1 - Glass in building - Requirements and determination method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●NEN 2608:2011+C1 - Glass in building - Requirements and determination method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●NEN 2608:2011+C1 - Glass in building - Requirements and determination method

	Sealing	● NEN 3413 - Foam strips - Requirements and test methods	● NEN 3413 - Foam strips - Requirements and test methods	● NEN 3413 - Foam strips - Requirements and test methods	● NEN 3413 - Foam strips - Requirements and test methods	● NEN 3413 - Foam strips - Requirements and test methods
f u n c t i o n / p e r f o r m a n c e	noise protection	● NEN 5077+C1+C3 - Noise control in buildings - Determination methods for performances concerning airborne sound insulation of façades, airborne sound insulation, impact sound insulation, sound levels caused by technical services and reverberant time	● NEN 5077+C1+C3 - Noise control in buildings - Determination methods for performances concerning airborne sound insulation, impact sound insulation, sound levels caused by technical services and reverberant time	● NEN 5077+C1+C3 - Noise control in buildings - Determination methods for performances concerning airborne sound insulation, impact sound insulation, sound levels caused by technical services and reverberant time ● NPR 5272 - Noise control in buildings - Guidelines for the application of the prediction method for the sound insulation of façades according to	● NEN 5077+C1+C3 - Noise control in buildings - Determination methods for performances concerning airborne sound insulation, impact sound insulation, sound levels caused by technical services and reverberant time ● NPR 5272 - Noise control in buildings - Guidelines for the application of the prediction method for the sound insulation of façades according to	● NEN 5077+C1+C3 - Noise control in buildings - Determination methods for performances concerning airborne sound insulation, impact sound insulation, sound levels caused by technical services and reverberant time ● NPR 5272 - Noise control in buildings - Guidelines for the application of the prediction method for the sound insulation of façades according to

				NEN-EN 12354-3	NEN-EN 12354-3	NEN-EN 12354-3
	insulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NEN 1068 - Thermal insulation of buildings - Calculation methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NEN 1068 - Thermal insulation of buildings - Calculation methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NEN 1068 - Thermal insulation of buildings - Calculation methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NEN 1068 - Thermal insulation of buildings - Calculation methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NEN 1068 - Thermal insulation of buildings - Calculation methods

5.9 Austrian national standards

	Category A Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	Category B Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	Category C transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	Category D transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	Category E cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
s a f e t y	In Austria the federal states are responsible for the building law. So every federal state has his own building codes. In addition to these federal laws, there is the Austrian institute for Construction engineering, which publishes the ÖNROMs. These are valid overall the federal states.				
electrical safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OVE / ÖNORM E 8001 -4-712 - Erection of electrical installations with rated voltages up to AC 1000 V and DC 1500 V - Part 4-712: Photovoltaic power-systems - Erection and safety requirements Systems • ÖVE/ÖNORM E 8001-1 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OVE / ÖNORM E 8001 -4-712 - Erection of electrical installations with rated voltages up to AC 1000 V and DC 1500 V - Part 4-712: Photovoltaic power-systems - Erection and safety requirements Systems • ÖVE/ÖNORM E 8001-1 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OVE / ÖNORM E 8001 -4-712 - Erection of electrical installations with rated voltages up to AC 1000 V and DC 1500 V - Part 4-712: Photovoltaic power-systems - Erection and safety requirements Systems • ÖVE/ÖNORM E 8001-1 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OVE / ÖNORM E 8001 -4-712 - Erection of electrical installations with rated voltages up to AC 1000 V and DC 1500 V - Part 4-712: Photovoltaic power-systems - Erection and safety requirements Systems • ÖVE/ÖNORM E 8001-1 - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OVE / ÖNORM E 8001 -4-712 - Erection of electrical installations with rated voltages up to AC 1000 V and DC 1500 V - Part 4-712: Photovoltaic power-systems - Erection and safety requirements Systems • ÖVE/ÖNORM E 8001-1 -

	<p>Erection of electrical installations with rated voltages up to AC 1000 V and DC 1500 V - Part 1: Definitions and measures against electric shock</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OVE / ÖNORM E 2750 - Photovoltaic power-systems - Erection and safety requirements • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61730 - Design and material of the modules • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61215 - Design qualification and approval - crystalline modules • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61646 - Design qualification and approval - Thin-film modules 	<p>Erection of electrical installations with rated voltages up to AC 1000 V and DC 1500 V - Part 1: Definitions and measures against electric shock</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OVE / ÖNORM E 2750 - Photovoltaic power-systems - Erection and safety requirements • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61730 - Design and material of the modules • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61215 - Design qualification and approval - crystalline modules • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61646 - Design qualification and approval - Thin-film modules 	<p>Erection of electrical installations with rated voltages up to AC 1000 V and DC 1500 V - Part 1: Definitions and measures against electric shock</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OVE / ÖNORM E 2750 - Photovoltaic power-systems - Erection and safety requirements • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61730 - Design and material of the modules • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61215 - Design qualification and approval - crystalline modules • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61646 - Design qualification and approval - Thin-film modules 	<p>Erection of electrical installations with rated voltages up to AC 1000 V and DC 1500 V - Part 1: Definitions and measures against electric shock</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OVE / ÖNORM E 2750 - Photovoltaic power-systems - Erection and safety requirements • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61730 - Design and material of the modules • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61215 - Design qualification and approval - crystalline modules • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61646 - Design qualification and approval - Thin-film modules 	<p>Erection of electrical installations with rated voltages up to AC 1000 V and DC 1500 V - Part 1: Definitions and measures against electric shock</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OVE / ÖNORM E 2750 - Photovoltaic power-systems - Erection and safety requirements • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61730 - Design and material of the modules • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61215 - Design qualification and approval - crystalline modules • OVE / ÖNORM EN 61646 - Design qualification and approval - Thin-film modules
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	safety in case of fire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM F 2030 - Sign (signals) for fire protection - Requirements, designs, implementation and placing ● ÖNORM B 5300 - Windows - Requirements - Complementaries to OENORM EN 14351-1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM F 2030 - Sign (signals) for fire protection - Requirements, designs, implementation and placing ● ÖNORM B 5300 - Windows - Requirements - Complementaries to OENORM EN 14351-1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM F 2030 - Sign (signals) for fire protection - Requirements, designs, implementation and placing ● ÖNORM B 3800-5 -Fire behaviour of building materials and components - Part 5: Fire behaviour of façades - Requirements, tests and evaluations ● ÖNORM B 5300 - Windows - Requirements - Complementaries to OENORM EN 14351-1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM F 2030 - Sign (signals) for fire protection - Requirements, designs, implementation and placing ● ÖNORM B 3800-5 -Fire behaviour of building materials and components - Part 5: Fire behaviour of façades - Requirements, tests and evaluations ● ÖNORM B 5300 - Windows - Requirements - Complementaries to OENORM EN 14351-1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM F 2030 - Sign (signals) for fire protection - Requirements, designs, implementation and placing ● ÖNORM B 3800-5 -Fire behaviour of building materials and components - Part 5: Fire behaviour of façades - Requirements, tests and evaluations ● ÖNORM B 3800-6 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 6: Fire behaviour of box double façades (2-layer façade) - Requirements, tests and evaluations ● ÖNORM B 3806 - requirements for fire behaviour of
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						building products (building materials) for air handling shafts and ventilation ducts, building separation joints, double floors ● ÖNORM B 5300 - Windows - Requirements - Complementaries to OENORM EN 14351-1
	safety in use	● ÖNORM ONR 21990 - Eurocodes - Application in Austria ● ÖNORM B 5371 - Stairs, guard-rails and parapets in buildings and landscapes - Dimensions	● ÖNORM ONR 21990 - Eurocodes - Application in Austria ● ÖNORM B 5371 - Stairs, guard-rails and parapets in buildings and landscapes - Dimensions	● ÖNORM ONR 21990 - Eurocodes - Application in Austria ● ÖNORM B 5371 - Stairs, guard-rails and parapets in buildings and landscapes - Dimensions	● ÖNORM ONR 21990 - Eurocodes - Application in Austria ● ÖNORM B 5371 - Stairs, guard-rails and parapets in buildings and landscapes - Dimensions	● ÖNORM ONR 21990 - Eurocodes - Application in Austria ● ÖNORM B 5371 - Stairs, guard-rails and parapets in buildings and landscapes - Dimensions
	resistance against snow and ice loads	● ÖNORM B 5301 - Avalanche proof windows and doors - General principles, requirements	● ÖNORM B 5301 - Avalanche proof windows and doors - General principles, requirements	● ÖNORM B 5301 - Avalanche proof windows and doors - General principles, requirements	● ÖNORM B 5301 - Avalanche proof windows and doors - General principles, requirements	● ÖNORM B 5301 - Avalanche proof windows and doors - General principles, requirements

		and classification - Marking of conformity				
G I a s s	Terminology, physical properties,...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 2227 - Glazing work - Contract to provide services ● ÖNORM B 3725 - Glass in building - Glass edges - Definitions for shapes and design ● ÖNORM EN 12488 - Glass in buildings - Glazing recommendations - Assembly principles for vertical and sloping glazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 2227 - Glazing work - Contract to provide services ● ÖNORM B 3725 - Glass in building - Glass edges - Definitions for shapes and design ● ÖNORM EN 12488 - Glass in buildings - Glazing recommendations - Assembly principles for vertical and sloping glazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 2227 - Glazing work - Contract to provide services ● ÖNORM B 3725 - Glass in building - Glass edges - Definitions for shapes and design ● ÖNORM EN 12488 - Glass in buildings - Glazing recommendations - Assembly principles for vertical and sloping glazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 2227 - Glazing work - Contract to provide services ● ÖNORM B 3725 - Glass in building - Glass edges - Definitions for shapes and design ● ÖNORM EN 12488 - Glass in buildings - Glazing recommendations - Assembly principles for vertical and sloping glazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 2227 - Glazing work - Contract to provide services ● ÖNORM B 3725 - Glass in building - Glass edges - Definitions for shapes and design ● ÖNORM EN 12488 - Glass in buildings - Glazing recommendations - Assembly principles for vertical and sloping glazing
	types of glazing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3710 - Flat glass in building - Terms with definitions for types of glass and glass products ● ÖNORM B 3714-1 - Plateglass in building - Insulating glass - Part 1: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3710 - Flat glass in building - Terms with definitions for types of glass and glass products ● ÖNORM B 3714-1 - Plateglass in building - Insulating glass - Part 1: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3710 - Flat glass in building - Terms with definitions for types of glass and glass products ● ÖNORM B 3714-1 - Plateglass in building - Insulating glass - Part 1: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3710 - Flat glass in building - Terms with definitions for types of glass and glass products ● ÖNORM B 3714-1 - Plateglass in building - Insulating glass - Part 1: 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3710 - Flat glass in building - Terms with definitions for types of glass and glass products ● ÖNORM B 3714-1 - Plateglass in building - Insulating glass - Part 1:

		<p>Terms and definitions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3738 - Glass in building - Insulating glass - Requirements for visual quality 	<p>Terms and definitions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3738 - Glass in building - Insulating glass - Requirements for visual quality 	<p>Terms and definitions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3738 - Glass in building - Insulating glass - Requirements for visual quality 	<p>Terms and definitions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3738 - Glass in building - Insulating glass - Requirements for visual quality 	<p>Terms and definitions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3738 - Glass in building - Insulating glass - Requirements for visual quality
	Sealing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3722 - Sealing of glazings with sealants - Rebates - Terms, definitions, dimensions, requirements ● ÖNORM B 3724 - Sealing of glazings with sealants - Glazing systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3722 - Sealing of glazings with sealants - Rebates - Terms, definitions, dimensions, requirements ● ÖNORM B 3724 - Sealing of glazings with sealants - Glazing systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3722 - Sealing of glazings with sealants - Rebates - Terms, definitions, dimensions, requirements ● ÖNORM B 3724 - Sealing of glazings with sealants - Glazing systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3722 - Sealing of glazings with sealants - Rebates - Terms, definitions, dimensions, requirements ● ÖNORM B 3724 - Sealing of glazings with sealants - Glazing systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 3722 - Sealing of glazings with sealants - Rebates - Terms, definitions, dimensions, requirements ● ÖNORM B 3724 - Sealing of glazings with sealants - Glazing systems
	General technical rules for usage of glazing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 5305 - Windows - Inspection and maintenance ● ÖNORM B 3716-1 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part 1: Basics ● ÖNORM B 3716-2 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 5305 - Windows - Inspection and maintenance ● ÖNORM B 3716-1 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part 1: Basics ● ÖNORM B 3716-2 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 5305 - Windows - Inspection and maintenance ● ÖNORM B 3716-1 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part 1: Basics ● ÖNORM B 3716-2 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 5305 - Windows - Inspection and maintenance ● ÖNORM B 3716-1 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part 1: Basics ● ÖNORM B 3716-2 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ÖNORM B 5305 - Windows - Inspection and maintenance ● ÖNORM B 3716-1 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part 1: Basics ● ÖNORM B 3716-2 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part

	<p>2: Linear supported glazing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM B 3716-3 - Glass in building - Structural glass construction - Part 3: Vertical glazings with protective function against fall • ÖNORM B 3716-4 - Glass in building - Structural glass construction - Part 4: Accessible, walkable and trafficable glazings • ÖNORM B 3716-5- Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part 5: Point-supported glazing and special designs • ÖNORM B 3716- Bbl 1 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Supplemental 	<p>2: Linear supported glazing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM B 3716-3 - Glass in building - Structural glass construction - Part 3: Vertical glazings with protective function against fall • ÖNORM B 3716-4 - Glass in building - Structural glass construction - Part 4: Accessible, walkable and trafficable glazings • ÖNORM B 3716-5- Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part 5: Point-supported glazing and special designs • ÖNORM B 3716- Bbl 1 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Supplemental 	<p>2: Linear supported glazing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM B 3716-3 - Glass in building - Structural glass construction - Part 3: Vertical glazings with protective function against fall • ÖNORM B 3716-4 - Glass in building - Structural glass construction - Part 4: Accessible, walkable and trafficable glazings • ÖNORM B 3716-5- Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part 5: Point-supported glazing and special designs • ÖNORM B 3716- Bbl 1 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Supplemental 	<p>2: Linear supported glazing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM B 3716-3 - Glass in building - Structural glass construction - Part 3: Vertical glazings with protective function against fall • ÖNORM B 3716-4 - Glass in building - Structural glass construction - Part 4: Accessible, walkable and trafficable glazings • ÖNORM B 3716-5- Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part 5: Point-supported glazing and special designs • ÖNORM B 3716- Bbl 1 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Supplemental 	<p>2: Linear supported glazing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM B 3716-3 - Glass in building - Structural glass construction - Part 3: Vertical glazings with protective function against fall • ÖNORM B 3716-4 - Glass in building - Structural glass construction - Part 4: Accessible, walkable and trafficable glazings • ÖNORM B 3716-5- Glass in building - constructive glazing - Part 5: Point-supported glazing and special designs • ÖNORM B 3716- Bbl 1 - Glass in building - constructive glazing - Supplemental
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		sheet 1: Examples for types of glazings				
	mechanical resistance and stability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM S 1310 - Attack resistant materials and constructions - Test methods, requirements and classification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM S 1310 - Attack resistant materials and constructions - Test methods, requirements and classification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM S 1310 - Attack resistant materials and constructions - Test methods, requirements and classification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM S 1310 - Attack resistant materials and constructions - Test methods, requirements and classification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM S 1310 - Attack resistant materials and constructions - Test methods, requirements and classification
f u n c t i o n / p e r f o r m a n c e	noise protectio n	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM B 8115-1 - Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction - Part 1: Definitions and units • ÖNORM B 8115-2 - Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction - Part 2: Requirements for sound insulation • ÖNORM B 8115-4 -Sound insulation and room acoustics in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM B 8115-1 - Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction - Part 1: Definitions and units • ÖNORM B 8115-2 - Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction - Part 2: Requirements for sound insulation • ÖNORM B 8115-4 -Sound insulation and room acoustics in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM B 8115-1 - Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction - Part 1: Definitions and units • ÖNORM B 8115-2 - Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction - Part 2: Requirements for sound insulation • ÖNORM B 8115-4 -Sound insulation and room acoustics in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM B 8115-1 - Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction - Part 1: Definitions and units • ÖNORM B 8115-2 - Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction - Part 2: Requirements for sound insulation • ÖNORM B 8115-4 -Sound insulation and room acoustics in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM B 8115-1 - Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction - Part 1: Definitions and units • ÖNORM B 8115-2 - Sound insulation and room acoustics in building construction - Part 2: Requirements for sound insulation • ÖNORM B 8115-4 -Sound insulation and room acoustics in

		building construction - Part 4: Measures to fulfill the requirements on sound insulation	building construction - Part 4: Measures to fulfill the requirements on sound insulation	building construction - Part 4: Measures to fulfill the requirements on sound insulation	building construction - Part 4: Measures to fulfill the requirements on sound insulation	building construction - Part 4: Measures to fulfill the requirements on sound insulation
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6 Review of Standards and Guidelines for test methods for BIPB-Modules

On the following pages all relevant testing standards and guidelines for integrated BIPV-modules in building facade and roof are listed. Due to the huge number of standards, two variations of tables are shown in the present document. In chapter 6 the standards are listed in tables, optimized for paper size DIN A4. In attachment the original table is shown, optimized for work on computer screen.

6.1 European standards

		Category A Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	Category B Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	Category C transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	Category D transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	Category E cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
s a f e t y	electrical safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 61215 - Crystalline silicon terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval, tests • EN 61721 (withdrawn) - Susceptibility of a PV module to accidental impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 61215 - Crystalline silicon terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval, tests • EN 61721 (withdrawn) - Susceptibility of a PV module to accidental impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 61215 - Crystalline silicon terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval, tests • EN 61721 (withdrawn) - Susceptibility of a PV module to accidental impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 61215 - Crystalline silicon terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval, tests • EN 61721 (withdrawn) - Susceptibility of a PV module to accidental impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 61215 - Crystalline silicon terrestrial photovoltaic (PV) modules - Design qualification and type approval, tests • EN 61721 (withdrawn) - Susceptibility of a PV module to accidental impact

		<p>damage - Resistance to impact test</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 61730-1 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 1 - Requirements for the installation • EN 61730-2 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 2 - Requirements for the testing • EN 62108 - Concentrator photovoltaic modules and assemblies - Design qualification and type approval, tests 	<p>damage - Resistance to impact test</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 61730-1 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 1 - Requirements for the installation • EN 61730-2 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 2 - Requirements for the testing • EN 62108 - Concentrator photovoltaic modules and assemblies - Design qualification and type approval, tests 	<p>damage - Resistance to impact test</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 61730-1 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 1 - Requirements for the installation • EN 61730-2 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 2 - Requirements for the testing • EN 62108 - Concentrator photovoltaic modules and assemblies - Design qualification and type approval, tests 	<p>damage - Resistance to impact test</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 61730-1 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 1 - Requirements for the installation • EN 61730-2 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 2 - Requirements for the testing • EN 62108 - Concentrator photovoltaic modules and assemblies - Design qualification and type approval, tests 	<p>damage - Resistance to impact test</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 61730-1 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 1 - Requirements for the installation • EN 61730-2 A1 - PV-modules – safety qualification Part 2 - Requirements for the testing • EN 62108 - Concentrator photovoltaic modules and assemblies - Design qualification and type approval, tests
	safety in case of fire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1363-1 - Fire resistance tests- Part 1 - General Requirements • EN 1363-2 - Fire resistance tests- Part 2 - Alternative and additional procedures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1363-1 - Fire resistance tests- Part 1 - General Requirements • EN 1363-2 - Fire resistance tests- Part 2 - Alternative and additional procedures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1363-1 - Fire resistance tests- Part 1 - General Requirements • EN 1363-2 - Fire resistance tests- Part 2 - Alternative and additional procedures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1363-1 - Fire resistance tests- Part 1 - General Requirements • EN 1363-2 - Fire resistance tests- Part 2 - Alternative and additional procedures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1363-1 - Fire resistance tests- Part 1 - General Requirements • EN 1363-2 - Fire resistance tests- Part 2 - Alternative and additional procedures

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN1365-2 - Fire resistance tests for loadbearing elements - Part 2 - Floors and roofs • EN 12114 - Thermal performances of buildings - Air permeability of building components and building elements - Laboratory test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN1365-2 - Fire resistance tests for loadbearing elements - Part 2 - Floors and roofs • EN 12114 - Thermal performances of buildings - Air permeability of building components and building elements - Laboratory test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 1364-1 - Fire resistance tests for non-loadbearing elements - Part 1 - Test procedures, Walls • EN1365-1 - Fire resistance tests for loadbearing elements - Part 1 - Walls • EN 12114 - Thermal performances of buildings - Air permeability of building components and building elements - Laboratory test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 1364-1 - Fire resistance tests for non-loadbearing elements - Part 1 - Test procedures, Walls • EN1365-1 - Fire resistance tests for loadbearing elements - Part 1 - Walls • EN 12114 - Thermal performances of buildings - Air permeability of building components and building elements - Laboratory test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 1364-1 - Fire resistance tests for non-loadbearing elements - Part 1 - Test procedures, Walls • prEN 1364-3 - Fire resistance tests for non-loadbearing elements - Part 3 - Curtain walling - Full configuration (complete assembly) • prEN 1364-4 - Fire resistance tests for non-loadbearing elements - Part 4 - Curtain walling - Part configuration
						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN1365-1 - Fire resistance tests for loadbearing elements - Part 1 - Walls • EN 12114 - Thermal performances of buildings -

						Air permeability of building components and building elements - Laboratory test method
	safety in use					• prEN 13830 - Curtain wall - Product standard, test characteristics
	slate, shingles and roofing tiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 538 - Roofing tiles - Flexural strength test • EN 12326-2 - Slate and stone for discontinuous roofing and external cladding – Part 2 - Methods of test for slate and carbonate slate • EN 14437 - Determination of the uplift resistance of installed clay or concrete tiles for roofing - Roof system test method • CEN/TS 15087Determination of the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 538 - Roofing tiles - Flexural strength test • EN 12326-2 - Slate and stone for discontinuous roofing and external cladding – Part 2 - Methods of test for slate and carbonate slate • EN 14437 - Determination of the uplift resistance of installed clay or concrete tiles for roofing - Roof system test method • CEN/TS 15087Determination of the 			

		<p>uplift resistance of installed clay and concrete interlocking tiles for roofing - Test method for mechanical fasteners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 15601 - Hygrothermal performance of buildings - Resistance to wind-driven rain of roof coverings with discontinuously laid small elements - Test method 	<p>uplift resistance of installed clay and concrete interlocking tiles for roofing - Test method for mechanical fasteners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 15601 - Hygrothermal performance of buildings - Resistance to wind-driven rain of roof coverings with discontinuously laid small elements - Test method 			
	water tightness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 539-1 - Roofing tiles - Determination of physical characteristics – Part 1 - Impermeability test 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 539-1 - Roofing tiles - Determination of physical characteristics – Part 1 - Impermeability test 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 12155 - Curtain wall – Water-tightness - Laboratory test under static pressure • EN 13051 - Curtain wall – Water-tightness - Site test
	wind resistance and air tightness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method;

		<p>German version prEN 12211:2013</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 1026 - Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method 	<p>German version prEN 12211:2013</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 1026 - Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method 	<p>German version prEN 12211:2013</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 1026 - Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method 	<p>German version prEN 12211:2013</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 1026 - Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method 	<p>German version prEN 12211:2013</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 1026 - Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method • EN 12153 - Curtain wall – Air permeability - Test methods • EN 12179 - Curtain wall – Resistance to wind load - Test method
	<p>resistance against snow and ice loads</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 539-2 - Roofing tiles - Determination of physical characteristics - Part 2 - Test for frost resistance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 539-2 - Roofing tiles - Determination of physical characteristics - Part 2 - Test for frost resistance 			
	<p>types of glazing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1096–2 - Coated glass – Part 2 - Requirements and test methods for the durability under abrasion for class A and B coatings • EN 1096–3 - Coated glass – Part 5 - Requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1096–2 - Coated glass – Part 2 - Requirements and test methods for the durability under abrasion for class A and B coatings • EN 1096–3 - Coated glass – Part 5 - Requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1096–2 - Coated glass – Part 2 - Requirements and test methods for the durability under abrasion for class A and B coatings • EN 1096–3 - Coated glass – Part 5 - Requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1096–2 - Coated glass – Part 2 - Requirements and test methods for the durability under abrasion for class A and B coatings • EN 1096–3 - Coated glass – Part 5 - Requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1096–2 - Coated glass – Part 2 - Requirements and test methods for the durability under abrasion for class A and B coatings • EN 1096–3 - Coated glass – Part 5 - Requirements

	<p>and test methods for the durability under radiation for class C and D coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (pr)EN 1096-5 - Coated glass – Part 5 - Test method and classification for the self-cleaning performances of coated glass surfaces 	<p>and test methods for the durability under radiation for class C and D coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (pr)EN 1096-5 - Coated glass – Part 5 - Test method and classification for the self-cleaning performances of coated glass surfaces 	<p>and test methods for the durability under radiation for class C and D coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (pr)EN 1096-5 - Coated glass – Part 5 - Test method and classification for the self-cleaning performances of coated glass surfaces 	<p>and test methods for the durability under radiation for class C and D coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (pr)EN 1096-5 - Coated glass – Part 5 - Test method and classification for the self-cleaning performances of coated glass surfaces 	<p>and test methods for the durability under radiation for class C and D coatings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (pr)EN 1096-5 - Coated glass – Part 5 - Test method and classification for the self-cleaning performances of coated glass surfaces
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1279-2 - Insulating glass units – Part 2 - Long term test method and requirements for moisture penetration • EN 1279-3 - Insulating glass units – Part 3 - Long term test method and requirements for gas leakage rate and for gas concentration tolerances • EN 1279-4 - Insulating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1279-2 - Insulating glass units – Part 2 - Long term test method and requirements for moisture penetration • EN 1279-3 - Insulating glass units – Part 3 - Long term test method and requirements for gas leakage rate and for gas concentration tolerances • EN 1279-4 - Insulating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1279-2 - Insulating glass units – Part 2 - Long term test method and requirements for moisture penetration • EN 1279-3 - Insulating glass units – Part 3 - Long term test method and requirements for gas leakage rate and for gas concentration tolerances • EN 1279-4 - Insulating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1279-2 - Insulating glass units – Part 2 - Long term test method and requirements for moisture penetration • EN 1279-3 - Insulating glass units – Part 3 - Long term test method and requirements for gas leakage rate and for gas concentration tolerances • EN 1279-4 - Insulating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1279-2 - Insulating glass units – Part 2 - Long term test method and requirements for moisture penetration • EN 1279-3 - Insulating glass units – Part 3 - Long term test method and requirements for gas leakage rate and for gas concentration tolerances • EN 1279-4 - Insulating

	glass units – Part 4 - Methods of test for the physical attributes of edge seals	glass units – Part 4 - Methods of test for the physical attributes of edge seals	glass units – Part 4 - Methods of test for the physical attributes of edge seals	glass units – Part 4 - Methods of test for the physical attributes of edge seals	glass units – Part 4 - Methods of test for the physical attributes of edge seals
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 13022-3 - Structural sealant glazing – Part 3 - Sealants – Test methods • EN ISO 9142 - Adhesive - Guidelines for the selection of artificial-ageing conditions for the test of adhesive bonds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 13022-3 - Structural sealant glazing – Part 3 - Sealants – Test methods • EN ISO 9142 - Adhesive - Guidelines for the selection of artificial-ageing conditions for the test of adhesive bonds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 13022-3 - Structural sealant glazing – Part 3 - Sealants – Test methods • EN ISO 9142 - Adhesive - Guidelines for the selection of artificial-ageing conditions for the test of adhesive bonds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 13022-3 - Structural sealant glazing – Part 3 - Sealants – Test methods • EN ISO 9142 - Adhesive - Guidelines for the selection of artificial-ageing conditions for the test of adhesive bonds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • prEN 13022-3 - Structural sealant glazing – Part 3 - Sealants – Test methods • EN ISO 9142 - Adhesive - Guidelines for the selection of artificial-ageing conditions for the test of adhesive bonds
	• EN ISO 12543-4 - Laminated and laminated safety glass – Part 4 - Methods to test the durability	• EN ISO 12543-4 - Laminated and laminated safety glass – Part 4 - Methods to test the durability	• EN ISO 12543-4 - Laminated and laminated safety glass – Part 4 - Methods to test the durability	• EN ISO 12543-4 - Laminated and laminated safety glass – Part 4 - Methods to test the durability	• EN ISO 12543-4 - Laminated and laminated safety glass – Part 4 - Methods to test the durability
mechanical resistance and stability	• EN 1288-2 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 2 - Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens	• EN 1288-2 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 2 - Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens	• EN 1288-2 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 2 - Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens	• EN 1288-2 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 2 - Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens	• EN 1288-2 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 2 - Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens

	<p>with large test surface areas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1288-3 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 3 - Test with specimen supported at two points (four point bending) • EN 1288-4 - Determination of the bending strength of glass - Part 4 - Testing of channel shaped glass • EN 1288-5 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 5 - Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with small test surface areas • EN 12600 - Pendulum impact test - Method of testing and classification of flat glass 	<p>with large test surface areas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1288-3 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 3 - Test with specimen supported at two points (four point bending) • EN 1288-4 - Determination of the bending strength of glass - Part 4 - Testing of channel shaped glass • EN 1288-5 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 5 - Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with small test surface areas • EN 12600 - Pendulum impact test - Method of testing and classification of flat glass 	<p>with large test surface areas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1288-3 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 3 - Test with specimen supported at two points (four point bending) • EN 1288-4 - Determination of the bending strength of glass - Part 4 - Testing of channel shaped glass • EN 1288-5 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 5 - Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with small test surface areas • EN 12600 - Pendulum impact test - Method of testing and classification of flat glass 	<p>with large test surface areas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1288-3 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 3 - Test with specimen supported at two points (four point bending) • EN 1288-4 - Determination of the bending strength of glass - Part 4 - Testing of channel shaped glass • EN 1288-5 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 5 - Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with small test surface areas • EN 12600 - Pendulum impact test - Method of testing and classification of flat glass 	<p>with large test surface areas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EN 1288-3 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 3 - Test with specimen supported at two points (four point bending) • EN 1288-4 - Determination of the bending strength of glass - Part 4 - Testing of channel shaped glass • EN 1288-5 - Determination of the bending strength of glass – Part 5 - Coaxial double ring test on flat specimens with small test surface areas • EN 12600 - Pendulum impact test - Method of testing and classification of flat glass
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6.2 German national standards

		Category A Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	Category B Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	Category C transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	Category D transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	Category E cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
safety	Lightning protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DIN VDE 0185-600 - Protection against lightning - Part 600 - Testing of the suitability of coated metallic roofs as a natural components of the lightning protection system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DIN VDE 0185-600 - Protection against lightning - Part 600 - Testing of the suitability of coated metallic roofs as a natural components of the lightning protection system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DIN VDE 0185-600 - Protection against lightning - Part 600 - Testing of the suitability of coated metallic roofs as a natural components of the lightning protection system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DIN VDE 0185-600 - Protection against lightning - Part 600 - Testing of the suitability of coated metallic roofs as a natural components of the lightning protection system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DIN VDE 0185-600 - Protection against lightning - Part 600 - Testing of the suitability of coated metallic roofs as a natural components of the lightning protection system

	safety in case of fire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN V ENV 1187 - Fire resistance - Testing methods for the extraneous stress of fire to roofs • DIN 4102-07 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 7 - Roofing; definitions, requirements and testing • DIN 4102-13 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 13 - Fire resistant glazing; concepts, requirements and testing • DIN 18234-1 - Fire safety of large roofs for buildings - Fire exposure from below - Part 1 - Definitions, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN V ENV 1187 - Fire resistance - Testing methods for the extraneous stress of fire to roofs • DIN 4102-07 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 7 - Roofing; definitions, requirements and testing • DIN 4102-13 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 13 - Fire resistant glazing; concepts, requirements and testing • DIN 18234-1 - Fire safety of large roofs for buildings - Fire exposure from below - Part 1 - Definitions, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 4102-13 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 13 - Fire resistant glazing; concepts, requirements and testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 4102-13 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 13 - Fire resistant glazing; concepts, requirements and testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 4102-13 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 13 - Fire resistant glazing; concepts, requirements and testing
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		<p>requirements and tests; Roof areas without openings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18234-3 <p>- Fire safety of large roofs for buildings - Fire exposure from below - Part 3</p> <p>- Definitions, requirements and tests at roof penetrations and roof edges</p>	<p>requirements and tests; Roof areas without openings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18234-3 <p>- Fire safety of large roofs for buildings - Fire exposure from below - Part 3</p> <p>- Definitions, requirements and tests at roof penetrations and roof edges</p>			
	<p>resistance against snow and ice loads</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52251-2 <p>-</p> <p>Determination of frost resistance - Indirect methods of determining the frost resistance of roofing tiles; determination of water absorption</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52251-3 <p>-</p> <p>Determination of frost resistance - Indirect methods of determining the frost resistance of roofing tiles;</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52251-2 <p>-</p> <p>Determination of frost resistance - Indirect methods of determining the frost resistance of roofing tiles; determination of water absorption</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52251-3 <p>-</p> <p>Determination of frost resistance - Indirect methods of determining the frost resistance of roofing tiles;</p>			

		determination of coefficient of impregnation • DIN 52251-5 - Determination of frost resistance - Indirect methods of determining the frost resistance of roofing tiles; determination of drying shrinkage and firing shrinkage	determination of coefficient of impregnation • DIN 52251-5 - Determination of frost resistance - Indirect methods of determining the frost resistance of roofing tiles; determination of drying shrinkage and firing shrinkage			
	Cladding					• DIN 18516-1 - Cladding for external walls, ventilated at rear - Part 1 - Requirements, principles of testing
G l a s s	types of glazing	• DIN 1286-1 - Air-filled multiple-walled insulation glass units, requirements, aging test • DIN 18516-4 - Back-ventilated, non-loadbearing,	• DIN 1286-1 - Air-filled multiple-walled insulation glass units, requirements, aging test • DIN 52344 WITHDRAWN - Testing of glass - Weathering	• DIN 1286-1 - Air-filled multiple-walled insulation glass units, requirements, aging test • DIN 18516-4 - Back-ventilated, non-loadbearing,	• DIN 1286-1 - Air-filled multiple-walled insulation glass units, requirements, aging test • DIN 52344 WITHDRAWN - Testing of glass - Weathering	• DIN 1286-1 - Air-filled multiple-walled insulation glass units, requirements, aging test • DIN 18516-4 - Back-ventilated, non-loadbearing,

	external enclosures of buildings, made from tempered safety glass panels - Requirements, design and testing methods • DIN 52344 WITHDRAWN - Testing of glass - Weathering test for insulating glass units • DIN 52345 WITHDRAWN - Testing of glass - Determination of dew point temperature of insulating glass units	test for insulating glass units • DIN 52345 WITHDRAWN - Testing of glass - Determination of dew point temperature of insulating glass units	external enclosures of buildings, made from tempered safety glass panels - Requirements, design and testing methods • DIN 52344 WITHDRAWN - Testing of glass - Weathering test for insulating glass units • DIN 52345 WITHDRAWN - Testing of glass - Determination of dew point temperature of insulating glass units	test for insulating glass units • DIN 52345 WITHDRAWN - Testing of glass - Determination of dew point temperature of insulating glass units	external enclosures of buildings, made from tempered safety glass panels - Requirements, design and testing methods • DIN 52344 WITHDRAWN - Testing of glass - Weathering test for insulating glass units • DIN 52345 WITHDRAWN - Testing of glass - Determination of dew point temperature of insulating glass units
Sealing	• DIN 52452-1 WITHDRAWN - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, compatibility with other sealing	• DIN 52452-1 WITHDRAWN - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, compatibility with other sealing	• DIN 52452-1 WITHDRAWN - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, compatibility with other sealing	• DIN 52452-1 WITHDRAWN - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, compatibility with other sealing	• DIN 52452-1 WITHDRAWN - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, compatibility with other sealing

	<p>products</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52452-2 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility with chemicals • DIN 52452-3 WITHDRAWN - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility of hardened sealing with fresh sealing • DIN 52452-4 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility with other protection coatings • DIN 52453-2 - Testing of sealing compounds for sealing and 	<p>products</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52452-2 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility with chemicals • DIN 52452-3 WITHDRAWN - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility of hardened sealing with fresh sealing • DIN 52452-4 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility with other protection coatings • DIN 52453-2 - Testing of sealing compounds for sealing and 	<p>products</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52452-2 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility with chemicals • DIN 52452-3 WITHDRAWN - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility of hardened sealing with fresh sealing • DIN 52452-4 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility with other protection coatings • DIN 52453-2 - Testing of sealing compounds for sealing and 	<p>products</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52452-2 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility with chemicals • DIN 52452-3 WITHDRAWN - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility of hardened sealing with fresh sealing • DIN 52452-4 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility with other protection coatings • DIN 52453-2 - Testing of sealing compounds for sealing and 	<p>products</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52452-2 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility with chemicals • DIN 52452-3 WITHDRAWN - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility of sealing products, Compatibility of hardened sealing with fresh sealing • DIN 52452-4 - Testing of sealing compounds in building constructions - Compatibility with other protection coatings • DIN 52453-2 - Testing of sealing compounds for sealing and
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	<p>glazing in building constructions - Part 2 - Determination of the migration of binder by filter paper method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52455-1 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 1 - Conditioning in standard atmospheres, water, or increased temperatures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52455-3 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 3 - Influence of light through glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18545-2 <p>- Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 2 - Sealants,</p>	<p>glazing in building constructions - Part 2 - Determination of the migration of binder by filter paper method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52455-1 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 1 - Conditioning in standard atmospheres, water, or increased temperatures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52455-3 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 3 - Influence of light through glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18545-2 <p>- Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 2 - Sealants,</p>	<p>glazing in building constructions - Part 2 - Determination of the migration of binder by filter paper method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52455-1 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 1 - Conditioning in standard atmospheres, water, or increased temperatures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52455-3 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 3 - Influence of light through glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18545-2 <p>- Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 2 - Sealants,</p>	<p>glazing in building constructions - Part 2 - Determination of the migration of binder by filter paper method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52455-1 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 1 - Conditioning in standard atmospheres, water, or increased temperatures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52455-3 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 3 - Influence of light through glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18545-2 <p>- Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 2 - Sealants,</p>	<p>glazing in building constructions - Part 2 - Determination of the migration of binder by filter paper method</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52455-1 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 1 - Conditioning in standard atmospheres, water, or increased temperatures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52455-3 <p>- Testing of sealing compounds in buildings constructions - Adhesion and expansion test - Part 3 - Influence of light through glass</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18545-2 <p>- Sealing of glazing with sealants - Part 2 - Sealants,</p>
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		designation, requirements, testing	designation, requirements, testing	designation, requirements, testing	designation, requirements, testing	designation, requirements, testing
	General technical rules for usage of glazing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18008-1 - Design and rules of construction– Part 1 - Terms and general rules for design and construction and testing standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18008-1 - Design and rules of construction– Part 1 - Terms and general rules for design and construction and testing standards • E DIN 18008-5 - Design and rules of construction – Part 5 - Special requirements to accessible glazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18008-1 - Design and rules of construction– Part 1 - Terms and general rules for design and construction and testing standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18008-1 - Design and rules of construction– Part 1 - Terms and general rules for design and construction and testing standards • E DIN 18008-4 - Design and rules of construction – Part 4 - Additional requirements for drop-protecting glazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18008-1 - Design and rules of construction– Part 1 - Terms and general rules for design and construction and testing standards • DIN 18516-4 - Cladding, ventilated – Part 4: tempered safety glass - Requirements, design, testing method • E DIN 18008-4 - Design and rules of construction – Part 4 - Additional requirements for drop-protecting glazing
	technical rules for usage linear supporte d glazing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18008-2 - Design and rules of construction – Part 2 - Linear supported glazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18008-2 - Design and rules of construction – Part 2 - Linear supported glazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18008-2 - Design and rules of construction – Part 2 - Linear supported glazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18008-2 - Design and rules of construction – Part 2 - Linear supported glazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 18008-2 - Design and rules of construction – Part 2 - Linear supported glazing

<p>technical rules for usage point supported glazing</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E DIN 18008-3 - Design and rules of construction – Part 3 - Point fixed glazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E DIN 18008-3 - Design and rules of construction – Part 3 - Point fixed glazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E DIN 18008-3 - Design and rules of construction – Part 3 - Point fixed glazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E DIN 18008-3 - Design and rules of construction – Part 3 - Point fixed glazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E DIN 18008-3 - Design and rules of construction – Part 3 - Point fixed glazing
<p>mechanical resistance and stability</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52314 - Testing of glass - Tensile test for the determination of stress optical coefficient • DIN 52327-1 - Testing of glass - Determination of stresses in glass-to-glass sealing • DIN 18032-3 - Sport halls - Halls for gymnastics, games and multi-purpose use - Part 3 - Testing of safety against ball throwing • DIN 52338 - Testing method for flat glass in buildings - Falling ball test for laminated glass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52314 - Testing of glass - Tensile test for the determination of stress optical coefficient • DIN 52327-1 - Testing of glass - Determination of stresses in glass-to-glass sealing • DIN 18032-3 - Sport halls - Halls for gymnastics, games and multi-purpose use - Part 3 - Testing of safety against ball throwing • DIN 52338 - Testing method for flat glass in buildings - Falling ball test for laminated glass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52314 - Testing of glass - Tensile test for the determination of stress optical coefficient • DIN 52327-1 - Testing of glass - Determination of stresses in glass-to-glass sealing • DIN 18032-3 - Sport halls - Halls for gymnastics, games and multi-purpose use - Part 3 - Testing of safety against ball throwing • DIN 52338 - Testing method for flat glass in buildings - Falling ball test for laminated glass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52314 - Testing of glass - Tensile test for the determination of stress optical coefficient • DIN 52327-1 - Testing of glass - Determination of stresses in glass-to-glass sealing • DIN 18032-3 - Sport halls - Halls for gymnastics, games and multi-purpose use - Part 3 - Testing of safety against ball throwing • DIN 52338 - Testing method for flat glass in buildings - Falling ball test for laminated glass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52314 - Testing of glass - Tensile test for the determination of stress optical coefficient • DIN 52327-1 - Testing of glass - Determination of stresses in glass-to-glass sealing • DIN 18032-3 - Sport halls - Halls for gymnastics, games and multi-purpose use - Part 3 - Testing of safety against ball throwing • DIN 52338 - Testing method for flat glass in buildings - Falling ball test for laminated glass

f u n c t i o n / p e r f o r m a n c e	noise protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 4109 - Sound insulation in buildings - Requirements and testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 4109 - Sound insulation in buildings - Requirements and testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 4109 - Sound insulation in buildings - Requirements and testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 4109 - Sound insulation in buildings - Requirements and testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 4109 - Sound insulation in buildings - Requirements and testing
	insulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52611-1 WITHDRAWN - Determination of thermal resistance of building elements - Laboratory method • DIN 52619-3 - Testing of thermal insulation - Determination of the thermal resistance and the thermal transmission coefficient of windows; determination on frames 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52611-1 WITHDRAWN - Determination of thermal resistance of building elements - Laboratory method • DIN 52619-3 - Testing of thermal insulation - Determination of the thermal resistance and the thermal transmission coefficient of windows; determination on frames 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52611-1 WITHDRAWN - Determination of thermal resistance of building elements - Laboratory method • DIN 52619-3 - Testing of thermal insulation - Determination of the thermal resistance and the thermal transmission coefficient of windows; determination on frames 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52611-1 WITHDRAWN - Determination of thermal resistance of building elements - Laboratory method • DIN 52619-3 - Testing of thermal insulation - Determination of the thermal resistance and the thermal transmission coefficient of windows; determination on frames 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DIN 52611-1 WITHDRAWN - Determination of thermal resistance of building elements - Laboratory method • DIN 52619-3 - Testing of thermal insulation - Determination of the thermal resistance and the thermal transmission coefficient of windows; determination on frames

6.3 French national standards

		Category A Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	Category B Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	Category C transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	Category D transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	Category E cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
s a f e t y	water tightness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-505 - Windows and doors - Watertightness - Test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-505 - Windows and doors - Watertightness - Test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-505 - Windows and doors - Watertightness - Test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-505 - Windows and doors - Watertightness - Test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-505 - Windows and doors - Watertightness - Test method
	wind resistance and air tightness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-502 - Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method ● NF P20-503 - Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-502 - Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method ● NF P20-503 - Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-502 - Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method ● NF P20-503 - Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-502 - Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method ● NF P20-503 - Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-502 - Windows and doors - Air permeability - Test method ● NF P20-503 - Windows and doors - Resistance to wind load - Test method
G i a s s	technical rules for usage linear support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-501 - Test methods for windows ● NFB 30 101 - Glass - Bend Test Of A Dual- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-501 - Test methods for windows ● NFB 30 101 - Glass - Bend Test Of A Dual- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-501 - Test methods for windows ● NFB 30 101 - Glass - Bend Test Of A Dual- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-501 - Test methods for windows ● NFB 30 101 - Glass - Bend Test Of A Dual- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-501 - Test methods for windows ● NFB 30 101 - Glass - Bend Test Of A Dual-

	ed glazing	glass Test Specimen				
	mechanical resistance and stability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-506 - Methods of testing windows. Mechanical tests ● CSTB-Cahier 3228 - Guideline of the CSTB about shock test 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-506 - Methods of testing windows. Mechanical tests ● CSTB-Cahier 3228 - Guideline of the CSTB about shock test 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-506 - Methods of testing windows. Mechanical tests ● CSTB-Cahier 3228 - Guideline of the CSTB about shock test 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-506 - Methods of testing windows. Mechanical tests ● CSTB-Cahier 3228 - Guideline of the CSTB about shock test 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NF P20-506 - Methods of testing windows. Mechanical tests ● CSTB-Cahier 3228 - Guideline of the CSTB about shock test

6.4 Greek national standards

No testing standards available.

6.5 Swiss national standards

		Category A Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	Category B Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	Category C transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	Category D transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	Category E cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
G I a s s	Sealing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA V280/ SN 564280 - (Redommenda tion, not standard) - Tests and requirements for membrane and synthetic sealing (polymer-sealings) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA V280/ SN 564280 - (Redommenda tion, not standard) - Tests and requirements for membrane and synthetic sealing (polymer-sealings) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA V280/ SN 564280 - (Redommenda tion, not standard) - Tests and requirements for membrane and synthetic sealing (polymer-sealings) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA V280/ SN 564280 - (Redommenda tion, not standard) - Tests and requirements for membrane and synthetic sealing (polymer-sealings) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SIA V280/ SN 564280 - (Redommenda tion, not standard) - Tests and requirements for membrane and synthetic sealing (polymer-sealings)

6.6 Italian national standards

		Category A Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	Category B Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	Category C transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	Category D transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	Category E cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
s a f e t y	slate, shingles and roofing tiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UNI 8635-15 - Building. Tests of products for discontinuous roofing. Determination of number for area unit and areic mass. ● UNI 8635-16 - Building. Tests of products for discontinuous roofing. Determination of alkali enclosure in fine clay products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UNI 8635-15 - Building. Tests of products for discontinuous roofing. Determination of number for area unit and areic mass. ● UNI 8635-16 - Building. Tests of products for discontinuous roofing. Determination of alkali enclosure in fine clay products 			
	wind resistance and air tightness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UNI 8625-1 + A1 -Building. Tests of discontinuous roofing. Determination of water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UNI 8625-1 + A1 -Building. Tests of discontinuous roofing. Determination of water 			

		permeability.	permeability.			
	mechanical resistance and stability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UNI 8635-14 - Building. Tests of products for discontinuous roofing. Determination of mechanical resistance of fastener elements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UNI 8635-14 - Building. Tests of products for discontinuous roofing. Determination of mechanical resistance of fastener elements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UNI ISO 7892 - Vertical building elements. Impact resistance test. Impact bodies and general test procedures. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UNI ISO 7892 - Vertical building elements. Impact resistance test. Impact bodies and general test procedures. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UNI ISO 7892 - Vertical building elements. Impact resistance test. Impact bodies and general test procedures.

6.7 Spanish national standards

No testing standards available.

6.8 Dutch national standards

		<u>Category A</u> Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	<u>Category B</u> Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	<u>Category C</u> transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	<u>Category D</u> transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	<u>Category E</u> cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
s a f e t y	safety in case of fire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6063 - Test method for external fire exposure to roofs ● NEN 6069 - Testing and classification of resistance to fire of building products and building elements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6063 - Test method for external fire exposure to roofs ● NEN 6069 - Testing and classification of resistance to fire of building products and building elements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6069 - Testing and classification of resistance to fire of building products and building elements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6069 - Testing and classification of resistance to fire of building products and building elements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 6069 - Testing and classification of resistance to fire of building products and building elements
G l a s s	Sealing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 3413 - Foam strips - Requirements and test methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 3413 - Foam strips - Requirements and test methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 3413 - Foam strips - Requirements and test methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 3413 - Foam strips - Requirements and test methods 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NEN 3413 - Foam strips - Requirements and test methods

6.9 Austrian national standards

		Category A Sloped, roof-integrated, non-accessible from within the building	Category B Sloped, roof-integrated, accessible from within the building	Category C transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module non-accessible from within the building	Category D transparent warm façade with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module accessible from within the building	Category E cold façade in front of opaque wall with crystalline silicon PV cells embedded in a glass-glass-module
s a f e t y	safety in case of fire			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM B 3800-5 -Fire behaviour of building materials and components - Part 5: Fire behaviour of façades - Requirements, tests and evaluations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM B 3800-5 -Fire behaviour of building materials and components - Part 5: Fire behaviour of façades - Requirements, tests and evaluations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM B 3800-5 -Fire behaviour of building materials and components - Part 5: Fire behaviour of façades - Requirements, tests and evaluations • ÖNORM B 3800-6 - Fire behaviour of building materials and building components - Part 6: Fire behaviour of box double façades (2-layer façade) - Requirements,

						tests and evaluations
	mechanical resistance and stability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM S 1310 - Attack resistant materials and constructions - Test methods, requirements and classification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM S 1310 - Attack resistant materials and constructions - Test methods, requirements and classification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM S 1310 - Attack resistant materials and constructions - Test methods, requirements and classification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM S 1310 - Attack resistant materials and constructions - Test methods, requirements and classification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ÖNORM S 1310 - Attack resistant materials and constructions - Test methods, requirements and classification

7 References

7.1 References of Chapter 2 - Research of building requirements

- DETAIL Praxis, Photovoltaik; Technik, Gestaltung, Konstruktion
- Österreichischer Fachverband für hinterlüftete Fassaden - Planung und Ausführung von vorgehängten hinterlüfteten Fassaden - Ausgabe: 1. März 2011
- Technische Universität Dresden, Fakultät für Baukonstruktion, Institut für Baukonstruktion, Prof. Dr. Bernhard Weller, 'Gebäudehülle – Teil I, Systematische Planung und Konstruktion von Gebäudehüllen', Lehrbuch, Ausgabe 2010
- FVHF – Fachverband Baustoffe und Bauteile für vorgehängte hinterlüftete Fassaden e.V.
- 'Handbuch Fassadendämmsysteme, Grundlagen, Projekte, Details", Kai Schild, Michael Weyers, Fraunhofer IRB Verlag
- DIN 18516-1
- E DIN VDE 0126-21 (VDE 0126-21): 2007-07 (Draft version)
- DIN 18008-1
- DIN 18008-2
- DIN 18008-3
- Figure 1: Cladding wall according DIN 18516
- Figure 2: DETAIL Praxis, Photovoltaik; Technik, Gestaltung, Konstruktion
- Figure 3: Wind barrier according DIN 18516

7.2 References of Chapter 3 – Standardization iv BIPV

- Figure 1: BIPV-CIS, D2b European Survey on Regulations, Rights and Guidelines concerning PV Building Integration, Table 2.14

7.3 References of Chapter 4.3 - Greece

- Law 3468/2006: 'Generation of Electricity using Renewable Energy Sources and High-Efficiency Cogeneration of Electricity and Heat and Miscellaneous Provisions".
- Law 3734/2009: 'Promotion of Cogeneration two or more useful forms of energy, regulation of issues related to the Hydroelectric Project Mesochoira and other provisions".
- Law 3851/2010: 'Concerning The Acceleration Of The Development Of Renewable Energy Sources".
- Law 4067/2012: 'New Building Code".
- Legislative framework for photovoltaics in Greece: A review of the sector's development, Karteris M., Papadopoulos A.M., 2012

7.4 References of Chapter 4.4 - Switzerland

VKF:

- VKF 13-03: BRANDSCHUTZRICHTLINIE Verwendung brennbarer Baustoffe
- VKF 20003-12:2012: BRANDSCHUTZMERKBLATT Solaranlagen

SN:

- SN 564232/2 & SIA232/2:2011: Hinterlüftete Bekleidungen von Aussenwänden
- SN520329: Vorhangfassaden

SN EN:

- SN EN 13830:2003: Vorhangfassaden
- SN-EN 13022-1:2006+A1:2010 (D): 'Glas im Bauwesen - Geklebte Verglasungen -Teil 1: Glasprodukte für SSG-Systeme - Einfach- und Mehrfachverglasungen mit und ohne Abtragung des Eigengewichtes'
- SN EN 13116: Vorhangfassaden, Widerstand gegen Windlast; Leistungsanforderungen

Others:

- Swissolar, STP22001d: Stand der Technik Papier
- 933.0 Bundesgesetz vom 8. Oktober 1999 über Bauprodukte (Bauproduktegesetz, BauPG)
- STI 233.0710 Solar-Photovoltaik (PV) - Stromversorgungssysteme - Juli 2010, Swiss adaptation to the IEC 60364-7-12
- 219.0201 Parallelbetrieb von Energieerzeugungsanlagen (EEA) mit dem Niederspannungsnetz
- www.sia.ch
- www.kgvonline.ch
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7.5 References of Chapter 4.5 - Italy

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- <http://www.reluis.it/>
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- <http://www.gse.it/it/>
- <http://rinnova.gse.it/autorizzazioni/Pages/default.aspx>

7.6 References of Chapter 4.7 - Netherlands

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- <http://www.nen.nl/>
- <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Eurocode>
- <http://www.komo.nl>
- <http://www.kiwa.nl> part of the international organization www.1kima.com
- <http://www.ikobbkb.nl/>
- <http://www.bda.nl>
- http://www.bureauveritas.nl/wps/wcm/connect/bv_nl/local/home/our-services/certification
- <http://www.isso.nl/producten-winkel/isso-winkel/product/winkel/detail/ShopController/isso-handboek-hbze-zonne-energie/>
- www.depkn.nl
- EU Project FP6 Performance
- EU project Prescript
- Discussion with Mr. Valckenborg, from SEAC (NL)

8 Appendix

On the following pages all relevant testing standards and guidelines for integrated BIPV-modules in building facade and roof are listed. Due to the huge number of standards, two variations of tables are shown in the present document. In attachment the original table is shown, optimized for work on computer screen. In chapter 6 the standards are listed in tables, optimized for paper size DIN A4.

8.1 Review of Standards and Guidelines for Integrating BIPV-modules in Building Facade and Roof (Original Table for readers of the electronic version of this document)

Kategorie	Kernkompetenz 1: Fachwissen					Kernkompetenz 2: Fachkompetenz					Kernkompetenz 3: Sozialkompetenz					Kernkompetenz 4: Persönlichkeitskompetenz				
	Wissen	Verständnis	Methoden	Werte	Transfer	Wissen	Verständnis	Methoden	Werte	Transfer	Wissen	Verständnis	Methoden	Werte	Transfer	Wissen	Verständnis	Methoden	Werte	Transfer
1	[Detailed description of content for Category 1, Kernkompetenz 1]					[Detailed description of content for Category 1, Kernkompetenz 2]					[Detailed description of content for Category 1, Kernkompetenz 3]					[Detailed description of content for Category 1, Kernkompetenz 4]				
2	[Detailed description of content for Category 2, Kernkompetenz 1]					[Detailed description of content for Category 2, Kernkompetenz 2]					[Detailed description of content for Category 2, Kernkompetenz 3]					[Detailed description of content for Category 2, Kernkompetenz 4]				
3	[Detailed description of content for Category 3, Kernkompetenz 1]					[Detailed description of content for Category 3, Kernkompetenz 2]					[Detailed description of content for Category 3, Kernkompetenz 3]					[Detailed description of content for Category 3, Kernkompetenz 4]				
4	[Detailed description of content for Category 4, Kernkompetenz 1]					[Detailed description of content for Category 4, Kernkompetenz 2]					[Detailed description of content for Category 4, Kernkompetenz 3]					[Detailed description of content for Category 4, Kernkompetenz 4]				
5	[Detailed description of content for Category 5, Kernkompetenz 1]					[Detailed description of content for Category 5, Kernkompetenz 2]					[Detailed description of content for Category 5, Kernkompetenz 3]					[Detailed description of content for Category 5, Kernkompetenz 4]				
6	[Detailed description of content for Category 6, Kernkompetenz 1]					[Detailed description of content for Category 6, Kernkompetenz 2]					[Detailed description of content for Category 6, Kernkompetenz 3]					[Detailed description of content for Category 6, Kernkompetenz 4]				
7	[Detailed description of content for Category 7, Kernkompetenz 1]					[Detailed description of content for Category 7, Kernkompetenz 2]					[Detailed description of content for Category 7, Kernkompetenz 3]					[Detailed description of content for Category 7, Kernkompetenz 4]				
8	[Detailed description of content for Category 8, Kernkompetenz 1]					[Detailed description of content for Category 8, Kernkompetenz 2]					[Detailed description of content for Category 8, Kernkompetenz 3]					[Detailed description of content for Category 8, Kernkompetenz 4]				
9	[Detailed description of content for Category 9, Kernkompetenz 1]					[Detailed description of content for Category 9, Kernkompetenz 2]					[Detailed description of content for Category 9, Kernkompetenz 3]					[Detailed description of content for Category 9, Kernkompetenz 4]				
10	[Detailed description of content for Category 10, Kernkompetenz 1]					[Detailed description of content for Category 10, Kernkompetenz 2]					[Detailed description of content for Category 10, Kernkompetenz 3]					[Detailed description of content for Category 10, Kernkompetenz 4]				

8.2 Review of Standards and Guidelines for test methods for BIPV-Modules (Original Table for readers of the electronic version of this document)

